

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF HOW VIETNAMESE
ENTREPRENEURS IN THE OVERSEAS EDUCATION
RECRUITMENT SECTOR DEVELOPED THE
MULTIPLICITY IN PERSONAL NETWORKS TO
ADVANCE THEIR BUSINESSES, 2000-2020

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ABSTRACT

In the era of internalisation and globalisation, overseas international education is the inevitable trend in developing countries, leading to extensive studies on topics about international students' experience, host countries as well as host overseas educational institutions. Nevertheless, overseas educational recruitment (OER) companies, which have contributed considerably to the choice of international students, have been hardly mentioned in the extant literature. Recently, with the emergence of unprecedented events like Covid, the role of those companies is getting increasingly significant.

Accordingly, the thesis explored the OER companies in terms of their nascent entrepreneurial period, in which most of them had to face massive challenges of entering the OER competitive market. To overcome the trials, OER entrepreneurs had to call for support from their contacts as well as developed their own networks. In fact, entrepreneurship and networks have always been important topics in business and the literature. However, the complication and deep nature of personal network multiplexity (PNM) in the network of entrepreneurs was hardly explored in qualitative studies. Therefore, the thesis fills in the gap by capturing the entrepreneurial journey of Vietnam OER entrepreneurs using personal network multiplexity to advance their businesses with the support of empirical qualitative research.

The case study approach was used by interviewing seven Vietnamese entrepreneurial companies or agencies that have gone through the TEA stage (Total Early Entrepreneurial Activity), lasting at least 3.5 years in the period from 2000 to 2020. Based on the thematic analysis, five main themes emerged from the data, including entrepreneurial motivation and challenges, dimensions of personal network multiplexity, dimensions of developments, the dynamism of personal network multiplexity, and personal network multiplexity strategy.

The implication of the study is to give a better understanding of the PNM activities of entrepreneurs in the context of Vietnam and the OER sector. Furthermore, it also contributed to explaining the dynamic factor in PNM. Most importantly, the study will benefit entrepreneurs who desire to set up their own entrepreneurial company in the OER sector in Vietnam to develop PNM for their entrepreneurial survivability and development. The research also contributed to theoretical implications by filling in the gap about the lack of literature on the entrepreneurial experience of individuals sharing their networking stories in the OER

sector. Besides, the PNM strategies of entrepreneurs in the Covid period drawn from the findings will benefit the richness of the literature on OER entrepreneurship or entrepreneurs in general in unprecedented events.

Although the study is carried out on entrepreneurs in one specific country (Vietnam) and a particular sector, the findings are also valid in other countries, cultures, contexts, and sectors. Hence, it will leave much more potential areas for future research.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- PNM – Personal Network Multiplexity
- PCN – Personal Contact Networks
- OER – Overseas educational Recruitment
- TEA – Total Early Entrepreneurial Activity
- GEM – Global Entrepreneurship Monitor
- The UK – The United Kingdom
- The US – The United States of America
- Uni rep- University representatives
- IT – Information Technology

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I first arrived in the UK to study abroad on a rainy day in 2016. Before becoming an international student, I used to work as an overseas educational consultant in Vietnam. In that perspective, I had not been too worried about what was waiting for me ahead. However, everything seemed to be more challenging than my initial thoughts. Nonetheless, I consider myself fortunate when I have met so many fantastic people who have been supporting me, inspiring me, and never ignoring me when I am in need. Without them, I could barely finish the thesis, and I could hardly have a beautiful learning journey in the UK.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Chapter content

- 1.1 Research Context**
- 1.2 Rationale**
- 1.3 Research Aim and Objectives**
- 1.4 Structure of the Thesis**

1.1. Research Context and Motivation

1.1.1 Research context

Overseas educational sector

Studying abroad in education is undeniably vital to individuals' academic and professional development and the future success of developing nations such as Vietnam (Kaplan, 2019). With regards to the international students, besides academic and knowledge, they can gain work experience, overseas connections, high academic quality, foreign university reputation (Sophia, 2013). Besides, they can see the world, develop a better understanding of cultures, expand the network, gain essential skills and boost employability (Katie, 2019). Nevertheless, the substantial rise of the sector also contributed tremendously to the host country and educational organisations, including political, economic, and academic factors (Le, 2014; Chien, 2020). In terms of political contribution, international students usually develop a liking for the political system of the

destination countries and bring with them goodwill about the countries' politics and the good image of the educational organisations they studied.

Given that many good international students will become future leaders, the host country will be benefited politically, and the reputation of educational institutions will be increased. Economically, international students will bring massive revenue to the economy of host countries through tuition fees to the educational organisations and other fees paid to local communities. According to the Education Department of the United Kingdom, UK revenue from education related overseas increased to £23.3 billion in 2018, an increase of 8.9% since 2017 and 46.7% since 2010 (GOV.UK, 2020). In terms of culture, many different individuals who can act as cultural carriers of resources and links between cultures, leading to decreased hostility, discrimination, and prejudice amongst cultures.

Regarding academic contribution, international students are the new source of cultural diversity, and their studies (thesis, dissertation) will reinforce the academic library of the host country and the educational institutions. As a result, the two side beneficial relationships (Students and educational organisations and host countries) needed each other, and OER companies are agencies born to connect those parties.

As a result, the demand for overseas study is enormously increasing. According to a survey by HSBC (Kenedy, 2017; HSBC, 2017) about the phenomenon, 42% of parents wish to send their children abroad to study, compared to 35% in 2016. Vietnamese parents are no exception. Statistically, 130,000 Vietnamese students are studying abroad, ranking 5th in the US in the number of international students this year. Besides, there has been a rise of 8,7% of Vietnamese students studying in Australia (Thanhniem, 2018). It is also said that Vietnamese parents invest in overseas study for their offspring even much sooner than before for the children's ease in adapting to their new study life.

Entrepreneurship in Vietnam in the OER sector and in general

As a matter of fact, the development of entrepreneurs in overseas study recruitment has sprung up like mushrooms in recent years. According to the survey of the department of education and training in the two biggest cities in Vietnam (Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh), there are around 1000 overseas educational agencies in HCM city and about 300 agencies in Hanoi, making up most

overseas educational overseas agencies in Vietnam in 2013 (Trang, 2013). And in 2021, there were more than 1000 agencies established in Hanoi (Mai, 2021).

The development in entrepreneurship Vietnam occurred thanks to Doi Moi, or the economic reform process after the 1980s, which has changed the Vietnamese economy from a rigid central economic planning into a market economy. Since then, entrepreneurship has become a strong driving force for Vietnam's economic development (Conway, 2009; Diez et al., 2016; Nguyen and Mort, 2016), along with facilitating policies for entrepreneurs.

Belong to a young, dynamic, and developing country like Vietnam, entrepreneurs have faced many obstacles, threats, and opportunities to flourish. Not until the economic revolution in 1986 to the market economy (Revilla Diez, 2016) and the business reforms policy after 2005 (GEM, 2021); did the entrepreneurs in Vietnam start shining again and contribute tremendously to the Vietnamese economy. Three out of four Vietnamese people asked showed their desire to open their own business (GEM, 2021). Nevertheless, the success rate of Vietnamese entrepreneurs has always been put in question because more than 90% of entrepreneurial failure has been statistically recorded in recent years (Cuong, 2017; Chung, 2018; Vietnamnet, 2018; Thu, 2019; Nguyen and Dang, 2021).

There were many reasons for the failure, such as lack of market, finance, suitable co-founders (Dnes, 2021); however, one of the underlying roots of the failure of those entrepreneurs in Vietnam is the lack of a business eco-system, argued by Vietnamese business sharks (Thu, 2019). The lack of networks and personal contacts are the main troubles for new entrepreneurs, preventing them from achieving the mentioned resources to develop and survive.

Realising the importance of the networks and the complication of personal networks, especially in Oriental business culture, the personal network multiplexity (PNM) of Vietnamese entrepreneurs was chosen as the main topic of the dissertation. The PNM is more complicated than standard social networks because it refers “to the extent to which two actors are linked together by more than one relationship in a network” (Ferriani, Fonti, and Corrado, 2012), which can help entrepreneurs more at the first period of starting up to achieve supports and precious opportunities for business survivability.

The complications of the network in Oriental business culture are also mentioned by the concept “Guanxi,” originating from China and also influencing Vietnam. Accordingly, Guanxi creates an intricate network of many businesses into a web to help those companies sustain long-term social relationships (Luo, 2007). The concept is also mentioned in the thesis when discussing the networking activities of Vietnamese entrepreneurs so that these activities can be seen and explained rationally, emotionally, and culturally based on the context of Vietnam.

As mentioned, regardless of the development, Vietnamese entrepreneurs in general and those in the OER sectors have met a plenty of constraints and challenges. Some external issues are harsh competitions, the limitations from governments (financial support, the transparency, and bureaucracy) (Vo, Narjoko and Oum, 2010). Besides, many internal and controllable issues that entrepreneurs might cope with are lack of knowledge and skills, management capabilities, contacts, source of customers in the beginning of doing business (Vy, 2019; Dang et al., 2021). In the case of entrepreneurs in the sector of OER sectors, finding overseas partners, managing partner overseas, visa procedures are also challenges.

1.1.2 Motivation

With all the factors mentioned, Vietnamese entrepreneurs in general and those in OER sectors specifically need substantial resources to support them in survival and growth. And in order to do that especially in the beginning of doing business, many entrepreneurs shared with me about the importance role of networking and the complication of networking in a relationship that is scientifically called “networking multiplexity”.

Coming back to my motivation of doing the research, that my career background was employed as an overseas educational consultant for a Vietnam company back in 2013, combining my actual studying abroad experiences in the UK in 2016 inspired my interests in the sector. The company that I worked for in 2013 was a start-up, whereby I witnessed the development process and challenges and obstacles that a Vietnamese company had to face. When I was in the UK, I also worked for another OER (Overseas Educational Recruitment) company. By the time I got on board with the company, my boss had just set up a new office in Vietnam. So once again, I got a chance to see her entrepreneurship in Vietnam in the same sector. Those real-life working

experiences with those entrepreneurs and my passion in the sector motivated me to choose the sector to be my research object.

Also, during the time that I was working with my employers, I have noticed the significant roles of networking in their success. They did not only know how to make use of their networks both domestically and internationally to support them, but they also knew the way to maintain and develop their networks. For each of their contact, they usually received more than one kind of assistance and support, which made the contact become more roles to the entrepreneurs and as I mentioned, it is called network multiplexity that I am really interested and decided to write a thesis about it.

1.1.3 Covid context

By the time the research was conducted, the Covid-19 pandemic had swept through the globe, affecting almost business activities and sectors. OER sectors involving the mobility of students were also adversely affected (Waters, 2021). Many reports indicated that many OER companies had to eliminate many staffs or even went out of business because of the pandemic (West et al., 2021). In Vietnam, 90,000 companies had to withdraw from the market, increasing by 20% compared to previous years during the covid period (Bang, 2021; Vy, 2021).

The number of international students studying in the US, the UK, Japan, and Canada (top student choice for studying destinations) reduced by 63-90% in 2020-2001, compared to the 2017-2018 intake (Tuoitre, 2021). Similarly, the number of students and parents coming to OER agencies for international study consultation was reduced by two-thirds during the Covid-19 pandemic (Tuoitre, 2021). Simon Marginson (2020) - Professor of Higher Education at the University of Oxford, Director of the ESRC/OFSRE Centre for Global Higher Education (CGHE) speculated that it has to take at least 5 years for overseas educational sector to recover from the Covid-pandemic.

Regardless of the reduction in quantity, OER agencies are still expected to shine given that international education institutions will try to re-establish their images after the pandemic. Both those institutions and students will need more assistance than ever before in terms of health concerns (testing, health regulations...), travel restrictions (lockdown, visa) or study choices (virtual study) (Kartika and Wibowo, 2022). QS survey (2020) also indicated that students are

heavily influenced by study overseas agencies' suggestions regarding school choices, especially in the context of the Covid pandemic (Iyer et al., 2020; Martin, 2020).

During the time I conducted the research, two OER companies that I was researching started up during the pandemic period; therefore, the situation was also considered in the thesis.

1.2. Justification of the research gap

1.2.1. Industry gap

As mentioned before, there are many challenges entrepreneurs have to cope with in the first period of opening a business. (Alton, 2016) claimed issues they had to face, and most derive from a lack of personal contact multiplicity, including financing, teambuilding, loneliness, and dealing with the unknown.

In the context of Vietnam, Davis (2018)-an expert on Vietnam business and society, also mentioned the lack of angel investors and human capital as the main reasons for entrepreneurial issues. Vietnamese entrepreneurs even deal with more difficulties due to the lack of linkages between other businesses, support from the Vietnamese government, and the hesitation of lenders and investors (Gutterman 2018). In short, most new companies in Vietnam suffered initially due to insufficient sources of personal contact networks (PCN).

The personal network problem is even more critical in the overseas education recruitment sector due to the complexity of the business model given that the OER sector requires entrepreneurs to develop networks inside the country and overseas.

Sending children abroad is an essential decision for every family that may cost them a treasure or their savings. Therefore, selecting a trusted OER company is not an easy task. Since 2000 when the first OER companies were established, some fraudulent companies have deceived Vietnamese people (Nguyen, 2021) about studying abroad opportunities, which has led to a bad reputation for OER companies. The fact affected the entrepreneurs in the sector tremendously. Thus, OER entrepreneurs need personal networks to promote their companies, especially in the first stage, to gain more trust and reputation.

Although the number of OER companies has been increasing, the statistics indicate that entrepreneurs in the sectors only take around 5% of the total entrepreneurial companies in Vietnam (GEM, 2021). Accordingly, studies on the sector are limited in the context of Vietnam.

For all the above reasons, the research will be carried out on successful entrepreneurs in Vietnam's overseas education recruitment sector to explore how they utilise PNM to survive the beginning of entrepreneurship. New entrepreneurs can learn and build their PNM for their future success. I have accumulated great experiences in the sector as an educational consultant in my position. Still, I have never under the position of an entrepreneur to see the big picture. Hence, the thesis is also considered a knowledge bridge for me to achieve my dream of becoming a successful entrepreneur in the OER sector with the PNM strategies combined and condensed from real flourish case studies and academic literature.

1.2.2 Academic gap

The topics of international students, international education, and overseas study have always been popular because of the internationalisation and globalisation process (Henze and Zhu, 2012; Chien, 2020).

Most of the studies focused on the experience of international students, such as. the intentions of those students (Luo and Jamieson-Drake, 2015; Loz et al., 2016), factors affecting their decision of them (Griner and Sobol, 2014; Nghia, 2019; Netz, 2021), benefits of studying abroad (Kitsantas, 2004; Magnan and Back, 2008; Millian et al., 2015; Petersdotter et al., 2017; Giorgio, 2021; Netz, 2021), history, purpose, experience, and outcome of study abroad (Twombly et al., 2012; Tarrant, Rupin and Stoner, 2013; Langley and Breese, 2019); identity issue (Young et al. 2014); reflection after study abroad process (Christofi and Thompson, 2011; Kartoshkina, 2014; Costello, 2015).

Besides, study abroad-related topics were also often seen in the view of either international students' countries, such as brain drain (Oosterbeek and Webbink, 2011) or host countries (benefits (Le, 2014; Hong et al., 2020) as well as host overseas educational institutions (Netz, 2015) or at a macro level like globalisation and internationalisation (Cambridge and Thompson, 2004; Han and Zweig, 2010; Parey and Waldinger, 2011; Pietro, 2012).

Nonetheless, the overseas study abroad topic has been hardly seen and carefully studied in the opinions and views of study abroad consultancy companies, which has contributed considerably to the choice of international students. Although there has been a strong increase in the number of international students and universities using educational agents, little research has been done to understand the relationship between parties (Thomson et al., 2013). In fact, the important role of these agencies in developing countries has been mentioned in the literature in recent years to both institutions and international students, such as the journal about the role of intermediary recruiters in higher education preparation: Perceptions of Nepalese students in the United States of Bista (2017) or A study on the Role of Consultancy in Overseas Education in the context of international students in India by Kamble and Bobade (2020). However, hardly can be seen that overseas education consultant agencies are the main objects for research.

Besides the gap in the objects for research, the extant literature about the mechanism of networking is also limited. Many researchers mentioned business networks, but few personal network multiplexity or personal contact network keywords were found or described in detail in the literature. The mention of PNM usually stops at being explained by the definition of the multiplex ties in social relationships rather than business (Hoang and Antocic, 2003; Ferriani, Fonti and Corrado, 2012), not mentioned in relationships with the development of entrepreneurs.

In Ferriani and colleagues (2012) research, their work focused on dimensions of PNM (economic and social). However, they conduct their research not at the beginning of the entrepreneurship period, which is the most crucial time for entrepreneurs to formulate strategic plans.

Broad (2012) studied networking performance in terms of benefits to companies in the West Midlands of the UK. However, he also indicated his limitations in terms of the geography approach. He also highlighted the role of cultural factors as being taken into consideration when studying the topic in another region. Another limitation of the thesis is the single-level analysis of individual businesspeople, and he also suggested further research in investigating the multilevel network.

There were also two articles and one thesis which studied the relevance of PNM and firm growth on entrepreneurs, but all these three have different limitations or room for further research. Accordingly, while Bliemel and colleagues (2014) explained multiplexity in entrepreneurs' networks, they claimed that little attention to multiplexity was paid to exploring the values created

by flows in networks. So, the thesis will try to pay more attention to exploring the values created by PNM through qualitative methods.

In the research of Bratkovič Kregar and Antončič (2016) about the relationship between an entrepreneur's PNM and firm growth, the authors proved that the relationship is positive. However, the research gap can be found that the authors used the quantitative method to identify the relationship but did not study and explore the specific experiences of entrepreneurs deeply at the beginning of entrepreneurship by qualitative methods. They also said a more in-depth analysis is needed (Bratkovič Kregar and Antončič, 2016). Moreover, the researchers mentioned "internationalisation" variable in the PNM model as the following research suggestion. Therefore, in the thesis, the sector chosen is about overseas educational recruitment, so the "overseas" factor is also discussed to bring light to the factor.

In general, quantitative research studies are usually conducted on the topic of networking as well as PNM. Hence, a qualitative study will be appropriate and needed to understand more deeply the importance of PNM in advancing business in such a complicated context of an Oriental country like Vietnam.

Finally, the topic related to the international education sector or OER is hardly found in academics. Besides, the entrepreneurs in the sector used network PNM (Personal Network Multiplexity) strategies nationally and internationally in the context of Vietnam – an Oriental country with a distinctive culture, which is the first to be mentioned in the literature.

From the mentioned analysis, the relationship between the PNM of Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector and the business survivability and growth will be selected as the thesis's main topic and be seen through the prism of the qualitative method.

1.2.3 Theory development

As mentioned in the previous parts about the gaps, I carried out the research in the views of overseas educational recruitment companies instead of educational institutions or international students. These companies were looked at the nascent period of their entrepreneurship or start-up period, where the networking entrepreneurial process is easier to see. From the social networking

process, I came up with notions about network multiplexity, which is more suitable with countries that have high collectivism index like Vietnam. Accordingly, I planned to deeply research on network multiplexity to identify its components/ dimensions. Those components are variables influencing the business performance. I also identified the criteria to evaluate business performance and growth. Besides, I also acknowledged that the networking process would be changed after a period; therefore, I continued to research network multiplexity in dynamism to see the difference of that after the period. The topic of network multiplexity was also seen as the cultural prism; thus, I extended a bit to countries with high collectivism index like Vietnam to find out similar networking activities, and I found out Quanzi in Chinese business culture, which is quite similar to “Quan he” in Vietnam.

1.3 Research aim and objectives

Research aim

The research will try to explore and understand the PNM of Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the first period of entrepreneurship in the sector of overseas educational recruitment through the empirical study of seven Vietnam OER companies to investigate possible problems and challenges they may face, analyse the reasons for the problems and challenges, and give recommendations for new entrepreneurs entering the sector.

Research objectives can be summarised as follows:

- To identify potential network contacts for Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the overseas educational recruitment sector
- To understand how personal network multiplexity formulated from those contacts can help overseas educational recruitment companies grow
- To understand the nature and the impact of the change and dynamics in personal networks after the nascent entrepreneurial period
- To give recommendations and propose strategies for those entrepreneurs to develop personal network multiplexity effectively to sustain and develop the business in the long run.

1.4. Research questions

- Q1. Who are actors with various roles in the network of entrepreneurs in the education recruitment sector?
- Q2. What are multiple contents that entrepreneurs in the education recruitment sector and their network members exchange in the system?
- Q3. What are the development attributes after the process of network multiplexity activities of Vietnamese entrepreneurship in the OER sector?
- Q4. How do the networks develop after the start-up period (dynamism of network multiplexity)?
- Q5. What are personal network multiplexity strategies and recommendations for entrepreneurs in the educational recruitment sector to grow their business?

1.5 Structure of the Thesis

To structure my thesis, I followed the guideline of my university, UWS (2021) and the reference from PhD theses from previous researchers and professors (Brown, 2007; Broad, 2012; Le, 2014) who also researched education and business sector, like my topic. Nevertheless, the word limit for the DBA thesis is around 60,000, lower than a regular PhD's. Therefore, I had to calculate correctly to allocate the content appropriately in each part of the thesis. Besides the clear structure and meaningful content, a successful thesis also requires a consistent style, format, and, most importantly, cohesion, logic, and ease to follow. Therefore, I always bear in mind these factors to elaborate on my finding, contributing to readers' comfort. Back to the structure of the thesis, the first part of the thesis is the introduction.

Chapter 1: Introduction

Referring to other PhD researchers, I decided not to lengthen the introduction too much since I believed a short and precise introduction would convey better than a long one. My introduction covered the background and context of the research with three main keywords: entrepreneurship in Vietnam, personal network multiplexity and overseas educational sector in general and in the context of Vietnam. The research problem and academic gap were briefly introduced so that readers will know more the reasons behind the topic selected and the rationale of the thesis. The introduction also summarises the research aim, research objectives to achieve that aim, research questions, and the thesis structure.

Chapter 2: Literature review

As named, the role of the part is to examine the extant literature with keywords in my thesis, starting from the OER sector to the entrepreneurship phenomenon, then the social networking and PNM in specific as well as the brief mention of the guanxi concept- the networking activities in Oriental culture. At the end of the chapter, the conceptual framework and the justification are also mentioned.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The chapter describes the adopted method used in the thesis, which is qualitative. The method was used in an empirical/ case study with a sample of seven companies in Vietnam's OER sector. Snowball sampling selection and justification were also mentioned in recruiting participants for the method. The primary method of collecting data was using semi-structured interviews, which is also explained carefully with a list of detailed guidance before actual interviews. After that, the thematic analysis was selected for the data analysis purpose. Finally, the part's ethical considerations, limitations, and conclusions were offered at the end of the chapter.

Chapter 4: Findings

The chapter started with detailed backgrounds of the interviewees and my initial opinions on the participants' attitudes, behaviour, appearance and style. Then, the themes table was mentioned based on the analysis of codes and subcodes from participants' interviews. After that, the detailed findings were presented and explained carefully and deeply. Finally, the chapter concluded with a summary of the finding.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Analysis

Besides chapter 4, the chapter is also the core of the thesis. It began with answering research questions based on the extant literature and findings from the previous chapters. After that, the implications for the entrepreneurs were presented through the prism of PESTEL factors based on findings and existing literature. Finally, the chapter offered the opportunity to reflect on the conceptual framework and proposed an updated one and justification for the change.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

The chapter concludes the thesis with limitations, contributions, and room for further research. Besides, the DBA course's long journey and the thesis were also told in the self-reflexivity part. Finally, the last part of the conclusion is the summary of the entire thesis.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

The chapter sheds light on the research objects that the thesis focuses on, starting from the overview of the international education industry with the overseas educational recruitment sector, which is seen as the literature review about the context of the topic. The second keyword in the thesis is entrepreneurship, which will be viewed as many aspects including history, definition, role in society, characteristics, and entrepreneurs and their success traits and behaviours. Entrepreneurship here will also be seen in the context of international education industry to shed light on the sector that have not been given attention for many years. The context of the OER sector in Vietnam will be given to ensure the relevance of the literature to the research topic. After finding the main problem of entrepreneurship in the OER sector was lack of quality networking activities. I continued to bring up business network theories and justified my choice for social networks and personal network multiplexity. The definition, history and dimensions and evolution/dynamism of PNM and social networks are also mentioned with a bit comparison with guanxi – the network of Oriental culture. The chapter's end is the conceptual framework formulated from the relevant literature search.

2.1. INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION INDUSTRY

2.1.1. Overview

With the increase in profit-oriented private educational organisations worldwide, a broader range of educational services is created through supra-national interactions, including different forms of provision such as test services, education marketing, teacher training, recruitment of university students, etc. Verger (2016) as Global Education Industry.

The global aspect of international education was also mentioned before by King, Marginson and Naidoo (2013) as a facilitating factor for educational activities such as formal education and informal education. The factor also changes the outlook of academic teaching by aiming at an international focus to attract more students worldwide to come and study (Hansen, 2002).

Recently, according to AIEC (2019), International Education is defined as it “allows students to think with an international or global perspective through connecting them with different societies and belief systems which will help them understand and embrace

cultural differences and similarities”. This definition is relatively consistent with King, Marginson and Naidoo (2013) in terms of worldwide factors, which will help erase the barriers of geography to economic, social, and cultural arrangements. AIEC (2019) also listed activities in international education, including **international student recruitment**, international admissions, student mobility, international compliance and governance, international student administration and student experience, transnational education (TNE), **international partnerships, relations and networks**, internationalised curriculum, pathways and ELICOS.

The common opinion on the international education industry definition of mentioned educational experts is the global factor. While Hansen (2002) and King, Marginson and Naidoo (2013) analysed the true nature of international education, AIEC (2019) just defined international education in terms of the student perspective. Nevertheless, the group listed the activities in the international education sector quite thoroughly.

The dissertation will choose the international student recruitment and international partnerships, relations, and networks for the research target.

2.1.2 Overseas educational recruitment sector (OER)

With the demand for recruiting international students, as mentioned in the introduction, the business of overseas educational recruitment has developed so rapidly. International student recruitment is considered beneficial for both the study destination as well as the students who come to “gain a degree and valuable experiences from high-quality universities” (IDP Connect, 2021).

According to Studee (2019) and Migration Data Portal (2021), 5.3 million international students achieved their dream of studying abroad in 2019, and the figure is expected to increase to 8 million by 2025. The figure below indicates the number of international students in the most popular destination countries.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at <https://studee.com>

Figure 1: International student population by country in 2019, adapted from Studee (2019)

Accordingly, the USA makes up to one-fifth of the world's international student population, followed by other nine popular countries, namely the UK, China, Canada, Australia, France, Russia, Germany, Japan, and Spain. As a result, the ten countries constitute two-thirds of the international student population.

Besides the international student factors, educational organisations recruiting international students are also crucial. With the rapid increase in the number of international students and the competition from others, the organisations have to implement suitable strategies to approach those international students. Cheung and colleagues (2010) suggested 4ps in marketing to promote the services of those educational organisations to Asian markets. Accordingly, those organisations need to strengthen and diversify their course and adjust them to be suitable for international students. Moreover, flexible pathway courses need to be designed effectively to attract more international students. Besides, the course price should be favourable for international students with bursaries and scholarships.

On top of that, local agents are also mentioned as the most critical factor in connecting with international students because they will be in charge of conveying other Ps (products and price and places) to prospective students for those educational organisations.

Specifically, agencies will be the bridge connecting the ideas (educational products) to match the student's needs. They also have their voice with educational organisations if the price of courses is not appropriate in the market context. Agencies are also reps who can do the promotion the best by creating seminars, conferences or connecting students to meet directly with educational organisations. The offices of those agencies are also the “place factor” that the educational organisation can utilise. Therefore, the relationship between educational organisations and agencies or OER companies is mutually beneficial and reciprocal.

The thesis focuses more on the side of entrepreneurial OER companies. Therefore, many definitions and classifications will be introduced. Before comprehending entrepreneurship in the OER sector, the business model will be revealed for more insight. Accordingly, a company in the industry is considered an education agent, providing overseas study options advice for home students. ICEF (2012) classified education agents into three types: educational referral representatives, study abroad advisors, and travel agents with the **education department**.

Educational referral reps represent some chosen educational institutions with precedent agreements while study abroad advisors are usually public organisations giving general information about overseas study options. Regarding travel agents with the educational department, they are travel agents. Due to competition in their sector, they want to expand to the OER sector based on their experiences with visas and destinations. In the research, the companies mentioned are educational referral representatives because they are mainly SMEs, entrepreneurs, and private companies; their main business is recruiting international students.

Nowadays, the role of these agents is vital for both educational institutions and students. These agents will help students come to overseas study options decisions easier and support them more efficiently than done by students themselves. Similarly, those agents also help overseas institutions form a local presence in overseas markets (Cohortgo, 2018). Therefore, these agents can get profits and commissions from both sides, which is also their primary income for their business. Therefore, many entrepreneurs who are SMEs want to start their business in the sector.

2.2. ENTREPRENEURSHIP

2.2.1. Definition and History

It can be said that entrepreneurship is more than one concept. It is a combination concept created by many disciplines. If some researchers considered entrepreneurship as the notion of social and economics (Wadhvani and Lubinski, 2017), Casson and Casson (2014) posit that the phenomenon includes economics, sociology, and history as well. Regardless of the crucial role in multi-disciplines, the entrepreneurship concept was considerably ignored by economic theory until the recent thirty years (Jones and Wadhvani, 2006; Casson; 2009; Wadhvani and Lubinski,2017).

Entrepreneurship nowadays receives more attention from scholars and especially MBA students who have been showing more interest in the history of entrepreneurship rather than the history of large corporations (Casson, 2009; Casson and Casson, 2014).

History

Entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs have emerged and developed since the ancient period, around 20,000 years ago, even long before its definitions and conceptualisation. The first event recorded was the exchange of obsidian (volcanic stones with healing abilities) with tools, food, and human skins in New Guinea (Allis, 2018; Hur, 2019).

As can be seen, entrepreneurial history existed from 20,000 years ago, and the phenomenon occurred in all the countries, areas, empires etc. So, it is a broad topic. In the limitation of the thesis, I will mention just specific events: Entrepreneurship in Ancient Mesopotamia, Entrepreneurship in the medieval period of Europe, and entrepreneurship during the Industrialisation Revolution. They are all links of the chain to the context of entrepreneurship in Vietnam.

The book *The Invention of Enterprise* by Landes, Mokyr, and Baumo (2010) traced the history of entrepreneurial activities from ancient times. It introduced Entrepreneurship in Ancient Mesopotamia as an earliest form of entrepreneurship from 626 to 539 BC. Empires of Mesopotamia areas brought the entrepreneurial phenomenon to make wealthy Greece and Roman empires (Landes, Mokyr, and Baumo, 2010) in the latter periods.

In the medieval period of Europe, entrepreneurial activities were more visible; however, the role of individuals was not well recognised because Christian society appreciated the profit maximisation dedicated to collective goals rather than individuals' richness (Landes, Mokyr, and Baumo, 2010). Those entrepreneurs mentioned mostly are kings, bishops and abbots. While kings could not rely on taxpayers only, bishops and abbots could not count on gifts and faithful either. Therefore, kings had to make wars, and churchmen had to build cathedrals and other activities to maintain their upper-class lives (Casson and Casson, 2014).

Casson and his colleague (2014) also compared the difference between entrepreneurs in the period and later periods by institutional context. Before Industrial Revolution, entrepreneurship was not affected by taxes, banking, accounting, and other financial and economic constraints. Nonetheless, the challenges and opportunities of these two are pretty similar. The global economy also influences modern entrepreneurship, which has roots in the pre-industrial period, such as social instability, civil disorder, religious issues, climate change, and unexpected pandemics. The research of Casson and Casson (2014) about entrepreneurship in the medieval period of Europe is also well recognised by Dr. McCaffrey (2016) from Manchester University. They are also interested in economic theory and economic history.

After the medieval and renaissance period, we have seen a miracle growth of Western countries' economies (European countries and America) after the industrial revolution originated in Britain. With the invention of James Watt's steam engine in 1764, the good and commodity transportation and productivity significantly rose (Allis, 2018). In Britain, many scientists were also encouraged to discover new mechanisms and ideas to pump up the production process and mobilise goods and commodities besides inventors. Enlightened politicians also built an incentive environment to develop the economy during the period. That was why British entrepreneurs took advantage of the period with human capital, natural resources, and polity to shine (Landes, Mokyr, and Baumo, 2010). Following and inheriting the advancement of Britain, other countries like France, Germany and America also prospered.

The industrial revolution also brings to the concept the mass production and economy of scale, leading to the birth of titans (big corporations) in Western society (Allis, 2018).

After industrialisation in western countries in the twentieth century, entrepreneurs became more and more important in society. The term entrepreneur is now more linked to innovation (Landes,

Mokyr, and Baumo, 2010); especially with the help of the internet, entrepreneurial ventures grow vigorously and unprecedentedly (Thegrittifund, 2020).

Definition

The word “entrepreneur” itself is also derived from the period; it is a French loan word describing a commander in battles, probably showing that business is also a battle and entrepreneurs are also commanders (Landes, Mokyr, and Baumo, 2010).

There are many definitions of entrepreneurship based on entrepreneurs' function, role, characteristics, and behaviours (Casson and Casson, 2014). Nevertheless, defining entrepreneurship is always challenging, and there is a lack of consensus among researchers about it (Mokaya, Namusonge and Sikalieh, 2012). Since the 18th century, entrepreneurship was looked at through the prism of economics and more clearly defined in the 19th century (Oncioiu, 2012). The simplest way of defining entrepreneurship is the process of starting a business (Hur, 2019). The term was coined by Irish – French economist – Cantillon in the 18th century, describing entrepreneurs as people involved in exchange for profit in the face of uncertainty (buy at a specific price and sell again at an uncertain price) (Nagarajan, 2011).

Mokaya, Namusonge and Sikalieh (2012) also mentioned the definition of entrepreneurship explained by the French economist and the entrepreneur Jean-Baptiste Say in the 18th century. Accordingly, Say believed that entrepreneurship means inclining to take risks and managerial skills needed to integrate with entrepreneurs.

In the 20th century, economists continued to approach the phenomenon dominantly; Adam Smith posited that wealth in society occurs through the changes in divisions of labour. From that insight, Michael (2008) concluded and defined entrepreneurship as the study of human action about changes in divisions of labour.

Joseph Schumpeter – the greatest economist of the 20th, has definitions and research about entrepreneurship and innovation, which are universal and applied to the present time (Nagarajan, 2011; Śledzik, 2013; Jones and Wadhvani, 2006). Accordingly, he has two theories about entrepreneurship (first and second). In the first theory, he defines entrepreneurship as not a life-long process, and entrepreneurs are the ones who carry out innovation. Therefore, when entrepreneurs start organising their companies, they lose the entrepreneurial function (Śledzik,

2013). In the second theory, he depicts entrepreneurs more collectively rather than individually. Accordingly, countries can be considered entrepreneurs (Śledzik, 2013).

In modern economic theory, entrepreneurship receives more attention due to mega companies' economic crises and turbulence. Cole (1965) stated that entrepreneurship is inseparable from economics. Economics is nothing without entrepreneurs, technology, institutions, and time (cited in Hughes, 1983). Many scholars saw entrepreneurs as the centre of entrepreneurship; however, Shane and Venkataraman (2000) defined that entrepreneurship definition should be covered with both factors, which are “entrepreneurs” and “lucrative opportunities”.

After reviewing classic and modern definitions and concepts of entrepreneurship, Oncioiu (2012) gave out exciting ideas. He disagreed with Adam Smith about the advantages of entrepreneurs and capitalists in the economic system. He believed that not everyone gains self-interest and privilege in the economic system if there is an efficient governing mechanism taking action. Arguments between Schumpeter and Peter Ducker on the qualities of entrepreneurs are also justified. Oncioiu (2012) viewed that entrepreneurs have to possess innate abilities but only enough if those abilities are trained. In terms of risk-taking, he also believes that entrepreneurs do not intend to take risks, but they plan and prepare for them. Finally, his essential point is that besides economics, entrepreneurship should be seen in psychological – behavioural and sociological studies to understand more. That is why; social network and personal network multiplexity are also themes selected in the thesis.

Newest definition of entrepreneurship is found in The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM, 2018) as "Any attempt at new business or new venture creation, such as self-employment, a new business organization, or the expansion of an existing business, by an individual, a team of individuals, or an established business". Accordingly, entrepreneurship has many stages (Figure 1), and the thesis will focus on the Nascent Entrepreneurship period involving the beginning process of business start-up.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at <https://www.gemconsortium.org>

Figure 2: The process of entrepreneurship (GEM, 2018)

2.2.2. Entrepreneurship Classification

Fillion (2010) studied the history of entrepreneurial classification since 1967, as shown in the table below. Accordingly, he argued the typologies of Smith are the most classic and with validated tests. The reason was that Smith was able to distinguish between craftsman entrepreneurs and opportunist entrepreneurs – the foundation of later business entrepreneurs. He also indicated the key criteria to identify and develop entrepreneurial typologies: human behaviour such as the need for achievement, need for power, need for recognition, need for security, attitude to growth, attitude in interpersonal relations, attitude to profits, and attitude to risk. He also mentioned leadership and strategic styles as entrepreneurial behaviours, but I think they are more like the results rooting from the human behaviours rather than behaviours themselves.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Fillion, L. (2010) ENTREPRENEURIAL TYPOLOGIES: ARE THEY REALLY USEFU. Entrepreneurs and business prospects for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Figure 3: Entrepreneurial typologies by Fillion (2010)

Months later, Steve Blank (2010), a famous business expert and entrepreneur in Silicon Valley, has divided entrepreneurship into types based on personal risk, size, scale: small business entrepreneurship, scalable start-up Entrepreneurship, large Company entrepreneurship, and extensive company social entrepreneurship.

Meanwhile, Aulet and Murray (2013) classified entrepreneurial activities into two types, including SMEs (small and medium enterprises) and IDEs (innovation-driven enterprises), which is quite similar to the class entrepreneurial classification of Smith about craftsman entrepreneurship and opportunist entrepreneurship. Accordingly, opportunist entrepreneurs apply new opportunities (innovation) to drive their business.

In the scope of research, entrepreneurs will be understood as small and medium enterprises, and these SMEs will be the target for research. Besides, these SMEs (overseas educational recruitment entrepreneurs in Vietnam) can also be considered social entrepreneurs because they contribute to the solution for lacking talents in the country by sending students abroad for more knowledge and skills.

2.2.3. The characteristic of entrepreneurship and successful entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurial companies mentioned in the thesis mostly are SMEs. Therefore, they are also featured as fast mechanisms in decision-making, flexibility, adaptability, and changeability. They are at a small scale, so they are not affected much by market fluctuations and economic crises. These companies are assumed to operate in domestic markets and contribute inconsiderable value to the development of the economy (Hoa and Khoi, 2017).

Some characteristics mentioned by them were quite right; however, the sector factor was not considered. In the thesis, entrepreneurs studied are in the sector of overseas educational recruitment. Therefore, they did not only operate in domestic markets but also involved transnational activities with foreign partners and international customers. The sector is also influenced by economic crises or unprecedented events like pandemics and wars because of the high cost that customers must pay for overseas study trips, so the argument that entrepreneurs are not affected much by the crisis is not convincing.

Suppose Shane and Nicolaou (2015) assumed that successful entrepreneurs should have sense of achievement, autonomy, proactivity, and stress tolerance. In that case, Viinikainen and colleagues (2017) assume that resources like finance, social and human capital contribute to entrepreneurial capital. And the ability to achieve them depends on an individual's entrepreneurial intention and success through motivation. Similar to Hoa and Khoi (2017), Viinikainen and colleagues (2017) also believed that successful entrepreneurs should know how to discover and exploit opportunities and make rapid decisions with a certain level of risk. They also added that entrepreneurs should be jacks-of-all-trades to perform entrepreneurial tasks.

In short, as Fillion (2010) argued, social behaviours decide entrepreneurship classifications. Hence, the characteristics of entrepreneurs are also rooted in individual social behaviour. And the success of an entrepreneur also depends on the behaviours.

2.2.4. Importance of Entrepreneurship

According to the evolved definitions of entrepreneurship mentioned before, entrepreneurship is permanently attached to innovation, opportunities, and new ideas. Therefore, the role of entrepreneurship is the stimulation of better changing in the economy, industry, and society.

Mayer and De Jongh (2018) posited that entrepreneurship contributes to sustained economic development because of employment creation, spending increase in markets and innovation. If Mayer and De Jongh (2018) merely mentioned the role of entrepreneurship in economic growth, then Byjus (2020), despite agreeing with Mayer and Jongh (2018) on the opinion of innovation and employment creation, affirmed that entrepreneurial activities should impact society and community development, raise standards of living and contribute to research and development.

More specifically, entrepreneurship has contributed considerably to job creation. In America's entrepreneurial and dynamic business environment, SMEs have taken up to 50% job creation and become the engine for US job growth (Decker et al., 2014). In Vietnam society, with a population of 96.9 million, entrepreneurship has the same function and even means more to the country. SMEs in Vietnam take up 97% of the economy, and they use more than 51% workforce of the country and contribute to 40% of the country's GDP (Ha, 2018).

Moreover, entrepreneurs help increase competitive competencies in industry, increasing productivity and developing the economy in general (Carree and Thurik, 2005; Phuong and Au, 2017). The statement is true in the Vietnam economy, where many governments or giant companies worked not so efficiently; the encouragement for entrepreneurship would be the solution for renovating the economy.

Last but not least, entrepreneurship is also stimulating changes in society and contributing to community benefits. Thompson and colleagues (2000) re-confirmed the vital role of social entrepreneurs in society by saying that social entrepreneurs will be the bridge between individuals and community, governments, and citizens to understand each other and together achieve synergy, contributing to the development of society. In the scope of research, overseas educational recruitment entrepreneurs are not only social entrepreneurs but also business entrepreneurs.

2.2.5. Overseas Education Recruitment in the context of Entrepreneurship

As mentioned, the new definition of the entrepreneurship is defined as “Any attempt at new business or new venture creation, such as self-employment, a new business organisation, or the expansion of an existing business, by an individual, a team of individuals, or an established business” (GEM, 2017). Presently, “education has become a global industry and education

institutions of all kinds have become involved in international education for financial and non-financial reasons” (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2008). Furthermore, seeking international students requires domestic relationship and network, which may not be the strength to most colleges (Chou, 2012) while OER agents can speak local languages, can liaise with the student in person, and have relevant networks in the country (Robinson-Pant and Magyar, 2018). Therefore, the emergence of OER entrepreneurs in students’ home countries in the sector is inevitable.

Besides, many educational institutions trust OER companies in students’ home countries by making them become “one-stop shops” (Pimpa, 2003). Accordingly, OER companies are not only marketing agencies for those educational institutions, but they also are providing the prospective students with varieties of support including counselling, application, visa procedures. Furthermore, they also realise the demand of the prospective students to offer extra services ranging from language courses, study skills trainings to travel support, accommodation search or part-time job search and so on (Pimpa, 2003; Pant and Magyar, 2018). The freedom in supporting auxiliary services to prospective students have opened many opportunities for OER start-up companies become entrepreneurs with innovative business ideas.

Besides being innovative with business ideas, OER companies normally receive commission from 10-15% from educational institutions for recruiting students for them (Pant and Magyar, 2018). Moreover, they are also charging prospective students with different amount of fee based on case-by-case basis. The freedom and flexibility in charging clients with the intangible products like study abroad services are components for OER companies to become different and competitive with other competitors.

The entrepreneurial feature of OER companies is also reflected in the freedom of choosing universities to work with. Previously, “universities would have appointed their own agents, now the majority of agents work independently and will represent a suite of universities” (Pant and Magyar, 2018).

With the fully assistance of OER companies, as a result, many international students have been choosing them to support for their study abroad applications more and more compared to the past decades (Kartika and Wibowo, 2022). Australia and the United Kingdom are pioneering countries relied heavily on foreign representatives to recruit students to entice students in a global marketplace where opportunities to study abroad are plentiful (Kirsch, 2014). Statistically, “About

one in three international students in the UK is thought to be introduced to their university by an agent and combined institutional spend on commission payments topped £89 million in 2013-14.” (Times Higher Education, 2016). As a result, the strong development of OER companies in the internationalisation of education is understandable.

Similar to other business sectors, OER entrepreneurs in the international educational sector also have to face with the ethical issues when they can get profit from both sides including the educational institutions and students. The financial interests might affect the counselling of OER companies to the destination choices of students (Brabner, 2013). Therefore, it will be challenging for education consultant agencies to start-up to become entrepreneurs to balance between financial interests and real value for clients.

In summary, there are not so many articles or journals mentioned international education recruitment companies the context of entrepreneurship. However, it can not be denied that the opportunities for those recruiters are much brighter than future as aforementioned reasons.

2.2.6. Entrepreneurship in the overseas educational recruitment sector in Vietnam

2.2.6.1. Entrepreneurship in Vietnam

Doi moi, or the economic reform process after the 1980s, has changed the Vietnamese economy from a rigid central economic planning into a market economy. Since then, entrepreneurship has become a strong driving force for Vietnam's economic development (Conway, 2009; Diez et al., 2016; Nguyen and Mort, 2016), along with facilitating policies for entrepreneurs.

The graph below indicates a positive wave of entrepreneurship in Vietnam, especially after the event Vietnam joined WTO (World Trade Organisation) in 2007. The year 2011 marked the starting point of starting Vietnamese business when they attracted considerable investments (Ha, 2018). Averagely, more than 50,000 enterprises are established annually. The Vietnam Association of Small and Medium Enterprises (2016) data show that the number of SMEs has increased remarkably in recent years in Vietnam: 20,510 businesses entered the market in the first nine months of 2016, which is over 59.6% compared to the same period last year. If we consider 81,451 businesses registered within nine months of 2016, the total number of new businesses is nearly 102,000, with 370 new businesses established per day. The newly registered capital increased by 49.5% compared to the same period in 2015. The average registered capital has

increased by 25.4%. Overall, there are about 600,000 SMEs, which accounted for 97.5% of the total number of enterprises (700,000) in 2016.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Ha, N. (2018) *Khởi Nghiệp Và Cơ Hội Cho Doanh Nghiệp Việt Nam*. Available: <http://tapchicongthuong.vn/bai-viet/khoi-nghiep-va-co-hoi-cho-doanh-nghiep-viet-nam-54290.htm>

Figure 4: Number of entrepreneurs receiving significant investments in Vietnam from 2011- to 2017 (Ha, 2018)

Talking about economic sectors, SMEs represent wholesale, retail, processing, and manufacturing, including some areas predominated by the state enterprises, namely, electricity, gas, water supply, mining, information and communication, etc. In the public service sector, SMEs account for about 5% of activities in education, health, and others (GEM, 2017; Ha, 2018). In 2016, SMEs contributed 40% of GDP, 61% of employment, 31% of exports, approximately 30% of budget revenues and 38% of social investment. The capital turnover rate on productivity, which indicates the effectiveness of SMEs, is 0.7 times higher on average compared to foreign investments, and it is 2.3 times higher than the relevant rate of state-owned enterprises (Vietnam Association of Small and Medium Enterprises, 2015). In the first six months of 2019, Vietnamese small start-up companies attracted 246 million USD investments, equal to the whole of 2017 (Vy, 2019).

Although entrepreneurship has contributed considerably to the economy, entrepreneurship in education is still limited, consisting of only 5% along with health and others. Therefore, the study

is also beneficial to start-up companies in education and, more specifically, overseas educational recruitment.

According to Lê Hoàng Uyên Vy (2019), the director of EPS capital, the investors for start-ups in Vietnam and South-East Asian Countries, the entrepreneurship in Vietnam is divided into three generations. Although they are different, the common trait is persistent, resilient, creative risk-taking, and a never-give attitude.

The first generation is from 2000 to 2006. Start-up and entrepreneurship were pretty new at the stage, and the competition was not too fierce. Therefore, right after discovering potential business models, founders at the state will not stop but extend horizontally to different sectors. The common feature of these founders is trying to promote mainly in Vietnam instead of other countries.

The second generation started from 2007 to 2014. Most companies achieved 100 million USD, and their products became familiar parts of Vietnamese daily life. At first, they had to cope with the stronger competition than the previous generation and needed more time to penetrate markets. After getting some success, these founders (second generation) mainly focus on fortifying their business sectors. Besides, they also invested in other auxiliary businesses to support the core business. Although their primary resources were still in Vietnam, these entrepreneurs tend to search for opportunities in various markets in neighbouring regions outside of Vietnam.

The third generation started in 2015 till now. They mainly experience working in many big companies like Google, Facebook, Microsoft, etc. Their products are usually developed with the support of deep technology. Their strengths are experience, knowledge, and operation management skills, which can help these founders scale their business very fast. They also can extend their business to the global level. Vietnamese start-ups and entrepreneurs have successfully maintained and developed their businesses, bringing value to millions of consumers.

Despite mentioning the entrepreneurs and start-ups in Vietnam, Vy tends to focus on tech companies more than other sectors. Unlike Vy (2019), Nguyen and Dang (2020) analysed Vietnam's entrepreneurship based on government and business law policy in different periods. The first stage is after doi moi and the 6th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam (1986-1990). In turn, the non-state sector was able to compete with the state in terms of economy, resulting in the reborn of Vietnamese entrepreneurs (Hay, 2008). The next stage observed the Law

on Company and Law on Private Enterprises; nevertheless, the unclear articles and stipulations prevented the fast development of Vietnamese entrepreneurs, leading to the modest number of 32,000 SMEs founded all over Vietnam. The third stage lasted from 2000 to 2014; the period saw a boom in private entrepreneurs thanks to the new law about the enterprise. Accordingly, business registration and other related procedures became easier. The attitude toward entrepreneurs was also more positive by society. The most recent stage commencing in 2014, witnessed more freedom in the business policy. Accordingly, Vietnamese entrepreneurs can engage in more business in most sectors except for some prohibited by law. And after the 2000s, Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector started to grow in number, possibly because of the new law.

2.2.6.2. Vietnamese Entrepreneurship characteristics

Understanding the features of Vietnamese entrepreneurs is the key to being aware of how they create a social network, forming multiplexity. Vietnam entrepreneurs are characterised by fortitude (Startupuniversal, 2019). Although Vietnam has a long history of war and people have suffered much, they are very optimistic with a positive mindset and focus on the future. Vietnamese entrepreneurs are the most **optimistic, bold, and risk-taking**.

Vietnam is still a communist country, but 95% of the population advocates a free-market economy regardless of poor and rich status (Devlin, 2015). After 1986, economic renovation helped Vietnam diversify the business structure and encouraged entrepreneurs to do their own business (Conway, 2009; Diez et al., 2016; Nguyen and Mort, 2016). They are also **less susceptible to the fear of failure and burning their entrepreneurial spirit with loads of passion after economic renovation** (Startupuniversal, 2019).

Similarly, GEM (2017) posits that besides being courageous, ambition is the driving force pushing Vietnamese entrepreneurs to higher levels. While the older generation owns a small business to provide for their family, the new generation is more motivated to go further. The reasons lie in the youth spirit and tech-savvy. Young Vietnamese entrepreneurs are pretty aware of the latest technology and desire to utilise it to serve the market. Nevertheless, the scope is mainly in the domestic Vietnamese market, as the GEM report above (2017).

Being optimistic about the ambition of Vietnamese entrepreneurs, the report (GEM, 2017) also indicated that **the perception of Vietnamese people about entrepreneurial capabilities tends to be lower; awareness of business opportunities is also decreasing**. These reasons led to the increase in fear of failure to 46.6 %, much higher than other least developed countries (average of 36.6%). However, the percentage of Vietnamese people who actually started up in the period 2013-2017 is the highest thanks to society's appreciation for the career (74.8 %, ranking 15th out of 54 economies).

The weak points of entrepreneurship in Vietnam are innovation and international factors (foreign partners or customers), according to GEM (2017). Suppose the ranking of innovation in entrepreneurial companies in Vietnam is around 48/54. In that case, the percentage of companies with 25% of international clients is only 1.8%, much lower than the average 8% of other countries' entrepreneurial companies. According to Danny Goh (Hrnetwork, 2020), a tech company CEO in Vietnam stated that Vietnamese entrepreneurs lack innovation and long-term visions. They tend to borrow ideas from other countries than having their innovative breakthrough ideas.

Tran – CEO at RBNC, a global firm providing services in Business Advisory, showed Vietnamese entrepreneurs' mistakes **for not being able to distinguish between start-up and entrepreneurship** (Nguyen, 2020). Entrepreneurs are defined as ones opening their business because they do not want to work for someone else. In that case, the start-up is more about innovation with breakthrough technology or innovative products to make a difference in the market. He also indicated another mistake of **Vietnamese entrepreneurs that they might have good business ideas. Still, they did not have a strategic plan to develop their ideas, which weakened their power with other investors.**

Another characteristic of Vietnamese entrepreneurs is the casualness. It might be not positive, but young Vietnamese entrepreneurs have turned it into a solid point for efficiency and faster progress. The informality also helps in making the decision process, and it also motivates the openness and collaboration between staff in team (Vy, 2019).

Besides, a strong focus on education in Vietnam is a foundation to leverage entrepreneur capability. Vietnam youngsters have recently performed so well in international tests (Dang et

al., 2021). Their parents also take a central part in their education and direct them to study scientific subjects, especially Maths, which supported those later entrepreneurs tremendously.

On the other hand, Vietnamese entrepreneurs also have some traits that can hinder some critical missions. **The first one is ambiguity in doing business.** Binding contracts are always a problem with the country and people based on much more trust than anything else. Most entrepreneurs do not respect intellectual rights when these are pretty new to Vietnam's business' policy. So imitation is pervasive here. **The second trait mentioned here is a lack of commitment.** Vietnamese entrepreneurs find it hard to find motivation for a long time when Vietnam doesn't have many successful entrepreneurs in the previous generations to follow and look up to. Hence, the rate of failure and change to another business is high.

As mentioned before, Vietnam's business behaviours and other southeast Asian countries and East Asian Countries (Korea and Japan) are pretty influenced **by Confucianism philosophy.** Wei and Ling (2015) described the characteristics of CEOs and entrepreneurship as quite similar to Vietnam's. Accordingly, the CEO and chairman are usually one person or board of directors who have a personal relationship with the firm's CEOs. That's why CEOs retain concentrated power on their side better. Market and legal institutions are not yet developed due to their short history and inadequate financial management practice, which makes the company so difficult to disclose information.

Constraints to entrepreneurs in Vietnam

International Labour Organization (2015) reports the three biggest constraints to entrepreneurs' growth across countries: access to finance, **electricity, and competition from the part of informal enterprises.**

In Vietnam, additional limitations to SMEs to be mentioned in the previous research are **a lack of knowledge and skills of employees** (Clarke and Gibson, 1998; Ntsika, 2001); **a lack of management capabilities** (Megginson, Byrd and Megginson, 2003; Kuratko and Welsch, 2004; Rwigema and Venter, 2004), as well as **limited access to markets and restrictions on capital and market shares** (Ntsika, 2001). **The limitation in financial resources** is one of the significant

barriers for SMEs in terms of integration (Vo, Narjoko and Oum, 2010). Capital restrictions make SMEs unable to invest in infrastructure and master newer technologies to expand their production or enhance their export (Rundh, 2007; Zhang, Sarker and Sarker, 2008; Wengeland Rodriguez, 2006) to achieve high efficiency (Rahman and Ramos, 2013).

It is worth mentioning that Vietnamese entrepreneurs have minimal **legal knowledge** in fundamental business (Tran, 2015), which has led to a significant number of commercial business disputes (NCSEIF, 2015). SMEs' prestige, capacity and competitive edge are much affected due to frequent trading disputes, lawsuits, court proceedings or losing trademark copyrights, information scams related to the evaluation of the legal status and financial status of foreign partners because of the lack of information either about them or their representatives (Dang Thi Phuong Hoa, 2016). The abovementioned problems of Vietnam's SMEs lead to many other obstacles to the market-entering capacity package, which results in business risks in the market.

In the aspect of constraints from the government, Narjoko and Oum (2010) indicated that the business environment, such as macroeconomic policy and barriers (tax, technical, etc.), are obstacles to Vietnamese entrepreneurs. Congruent to them, VCCI (2020) also highlighted law barriers, tax and bureaucracy as constraints to the development of Vietnamese entrepreneurs.

Challenges and obstacles of Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector

The OER sector in Vietnam is highly competitive because Vietnam is the 8th country to have the most students studying abroad (Halo, 2016). As mentioned before, there are around 1,500 OER companies in Vietnam, located in three big cities, including Hanoi, HCM and Danang (Nhat, 2015).

The advantage of OER companies at the moment is the current removal of certification requirements from the Vietnamese government, leading to fairness in competition and more options for students and overseas institutions (ICEF, 2016). However, both sides have to research carefully before selecting reliable agents.

Simultaneously, the challenges that Vietnamese OER companies have to cope with are high competition, the lack of contacts, and the limitation of educational institutions that they are processing because they are new entrepreneurial SMEs without sufficient resources. One of the

highly prestigious in Vietnam – Linh (2016), revealed some challenges that OER companies have to face.

The first is the true intention of students. Vietnamese students need a visa to study in most countries. However, some of them take advantage of the study visa type for working purposes or illegal stay in more developed countries such as Japan, the UK, Korea, America, Canada and Australia (Jae-heun, 2018; Giang, 2019). This caused severe problems to the image and reputation of OER SMEs.

The second challenge is policy. The constant changes in policy in Vietnam and visa policy from overseas countries are also significant challenges for the entrepreneurs in the sector. Besides, more than 5000 business requirements are allocated for 243 sectors in Vietnam; however, many requirements and stipulations are not appropriate. Many of them are restraints and barriers for market entrants. This will reduce the market's competitiveness and lead to monopoly if not solved (Anh, 2019).

The third is the perception of Vietnamese society toward the sector due to many fraudulent study-abroad counselling agencies that have deceived students and parents; therefore, entrepreneurs in the sector will have to struggle more to convince parents and students to use their services (Ashwill, 2014; VTV, 2019).

2.3. BUSINESS NETWORK THEORIES AND JUSTIFICATION FOR CHOOSING SOCIAL NETWORK THEORY AND NETWORK MULTIPLEXITY

There have been quite a few network theories in business and entrepreneurship mentioned in extant literature focusing on the content of network relationships, governance, and structure (Hoang and Antoncic, 2003). Therefore, choosing one of the business networking approaches was challenging. In this part, network theories in business will be listed and explained why they were not chosen for my topic, and I will also shed light on why I have selected the networking approaches for my thesis.

IMP Group has defined a business network as a set of two or more connected business relationships. They also explained business networks in the AAR model, including activity links, resource ties, and actor bonds. Accordingly, activity links refer to networking in operations between or within firms. Meanwhile, R refers to resource ties that companies exchange or access resources of each other to carry out activities. Finally, A refers to actor bonds whereby an individual and an organisation form a relationship with each other. They concluded that a single dyadic relationship is connected with a web of actors, which will comprise a business network (Welch and Wilkison, 2002; Gebert-Persson et al., 2014).

The theory is quite sufficient when indicating the actors and the content (activities and resources) that actors exchange in the network. They also mentioned the change in the bond of actors in the network. Nevertheless, the components are quite basic and will not be able to explain more difficult situations like culture, context (international networks), or the complication in each dyadic relationship in a network.

Another network approach is the internationalisation process of firms derived from Johanson and Mattsson (1988). Accordingly, the international factor was taken into consideration in network activities. This theory highlighted the role of building long-term interactions with entities from the foreign environment and characterised the internationalization process as determined by the entity-diverse foreign environment and the development of a formal and informal relationship with the entities in it (Iheanachor and Ozegbe, 2021).

The approach is more distinct from the ARA model, explaining when and how the company enters a foreign country and has a business-to-business focus rather individual-business network (Gebert-Persson, 2014). The approach is very suitable for my thesis because all OER companies work with educational institutions from foreign countries. However, international partners are not the only party OER entrepreneurs need to develop networking activities with. They also needed more domestic network contacts to support their nascent entrepreneurship. Therefore, only focusing on the internationalisation process of the network approach would have led to the lack of an overall picture of network activities of entrepreneurs. Besides, the approach is more business-to-business than individual, while my topic is more about the personal relationships between entrepreneurs and individuals.

Another approach is inter-organisational networks coined by Achrol and Kotler (1999). Accordingly, inter-organizational networks describe the new reality created by complex social, economic, and technological changes. This network approach also emphasises the importance of the whole company's contacts with the environment, forming an extensive network of connections (Barczak et al., 2021). The approach looks at not only the complication of social factors but also mentions the economic and technological changes, which are considered more updated than previous traditional network approaches. However, I did not go with the approach because it is quite broad in terms of my topic when it requires understanding the whole company's contacts rather than the single level of an individual (entrepreneur).

Based on the aforementioned critical analysis, I chose the social network in entrepreneurship and personal network multiplexity to be the literature framework for my research. Susomrith and Suseno (2017) viewed the social network as a sub-network of the main business network; therefore, a social network is not very broad like a business network but not too narrow like the approach of the network in the internationalisation process. Moreover, my research object is entrepreneurs who are individuals in organisations; thus, approaching social networks will help me to understand more about individuals conducting business exchanges overtimes to form bonds and trust between parties (Iheanachor and Ozegbe, 2021). Furthermore, social network theory in entrepreneurship also provided me with quite sufficient literature on how entrepreneurial individuals access their personal network contacts socially to develop their businesses.

Mentioning the choice of personal network multiplexity among the networking approach because PNM indicated exactly what I needed to study entrepreneurs about how they do networking activities at the personal level. The degree of network mentioned is multiplexity, meaning the multiple roles of actors in providing resources and activities to entrepreneurs in the nascent entrepreneurial period in which entrepreneurs lack plenty of resources. Besides, most social relationships are multiplexity because they are often based on more than one dimension (Diviák et al., 2019). The last reason is based on a cultural and contextual factor; Vietnam is a country with high collectivism index and high context (Hofstede, 2021); thus, establishing different multiple different relationships between contacts is important to do business. In a nutshell, multiplexity in personal networks is significant enough to study in the approach of business networking study.

2.4. SOCIAL NETWORK IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

2.4.1. Definitions and history

Many definitions have been formed to understand the nature of social networks in entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, it is necessary to trace back the history of the concept to see the evolution of the new phenomenon. In the mere aspect of sociology, Emile Durkheim and Ferdinand Tonnies were accredited as those who pioneered in forming the concept of “social networks” during the late 19th century, where members share values, beliefs and even conflicts in social groups (Aldous, Durkheim and Tonnies, 1972; Edosomwan et al., 2011).

During the current blooming period of the entrepreneurial era, the social network concept received more attention on account of its role and position in the success of entrepreneurs. There have been many scholars and researchers mentioning and popularising the topic. The very first to be mentioned is the empirical research of Granovetter (1973) and Granovetter (1983) (revisited) on strong and weak ties in social networks. The research is necessary because it is still validated and brought his name to light as one of the first pioneers studying social network theory (Harper, 2016). Accordingly, Granovetter (1973, 1983) posited that weak ties are even more critical to being bridges than strong ties to access new people in the network. Besides, his social network concept in entrepreneurship denied the traditional view of entrepreneurs as “free agent” and not affected by any factors except their beliefs and cognitions (Aldrich & Zimmer, 1986).

Burt (1992, 2000, 2010, 2015) also mentioned the concept of “structural holes” and “reinforced structural holes” in the network. Accordingly, those actors creating a structure hole may know each other, but they focus on their own activities and different information flows. From the view of structural holes, Alhaji and Rokne (2014) believe that they are opportunities for brokers and avoid information redundancy compared to cohesive contacts. The concept is quite similar to the weak ties theory of Granovetter (1973, 1983) that entrepreneurs can utilise those to connect with more new information and contacts and avoid overlapping information.

Granovetter (1983) also argued that social networks are not fixed. They are the social context of businesses and can be activated according to different needs. Entrepreneurs have to know how to use these connections in their business decisions, which was also supported by Burt (1992; 2015).

Since the 1990s, the entrepreneurial network has been more discussed, and the successful entrepreneurial network assumingly depends on the ability to be well-connected (Vissa, 2010). Many researchers and economists believe that networking activity is the process in which entrepreneurs acquire information about novel entrepreneurial ideas through relationships with those who can provide necessary resources. (Johannisson, 1988; Birley, Cromie & Myers, 1991; Larson, 1991). These ideas contrast to traditional views that the main success factors of entrepreneurship are only land, capital, and labour (Das and Goswami, 2019). To reinforce the idea of social networks, Hansen (1995) also defined social networks as a tool for entrepreneurs to get support, knowledge, and access to distribution channels through links and interactions.

In recent years, social networks have been receiving plenty of attention. An entrepreneurial network is summarised as the collection of contacts that entrepreneurs utilise to make the best of exchange ties (Vissa, 2010; Bensaou et al., 2014; Engel et al., 2017).

Naoko (2012), based on the analysis of Granovetter (1985) on strong ties and weak ties in the networks, clarified more components of the strong personal relationship of entrepreneurs, including family, friends, and business acquaintances. Those relationships are tied through money transactions, shared knowledge, values, blood ties and emotional ties.

(Sabuhilaki, 2016) did not point out the specific relationship of entrepreneurs, but he agrees with Naoko in terms of definition. The author defined a network as the collection of people who communicate via certain relations with each other to implement functions for establishing companies, including the ease of thought conversion to a whole scheme, increasing motivation, provoking thoughts, presenting the practical help and support.

Adding to the definition of the social network, Bliemel and colleagues (2014) emphasised an entrepreneurial network as the set of interrelations between entrepreneurs and their direct contacts to boost and develop enterprises. (Das and Goswami, 2019) highly appreciated the word interrelations because they believe that the relationship between entrepreneurs and their network is dynamic and mutually affected.

According to Sabuhilaki (2016). The networks consist of three general properties by which the network's efficiency can be measured: concentration, accessibility, and centrality. Concentration

is the plurality of communication between people. Accessibility is the network domain and the number of communicative interfaces or groups. Centrality is the distance of a person from other people and the number of people who can access them.

Kapucu and Hu (2014) classified networks as the purpose and value that network brings, such as social networks, knowledge networks, resource networks, and interorganisational networks, while not directly talking about factors affecting entrepreneurial networks.

Chandrasekhar (2014) revealed factors affecting the success of entrepreneurship, including internal factors and external factors. Accordingly, internal factors are motivation and risk-taking; meanwhile, external factors are economic, demographic, cultural, social, and environmental, which are crucial in choosing partners and formulating networks.

In cultural studies, because network concepts belong to the sociology paradigm, social factors are also vital in the formulation of network multiplexity, including age, experience, social status of entrepreneurs, and external social factors such as education infrastructure and social and cultural environment (Sabuhilaki; 2016).

(Hoang and Antoncic, 2003) revealed that over 70 papers on this topic have been published in the past 15 years. They included papers about the development and consequences of networks in the new venture creation process or focused on small to medium-sized firms. They organised the literature by defining and illustrating the three essential components of networks: **the content of the relationships; the governance of these relationships; and the structure or pattern** that emerges from the cross-cutting ties.

There were some studies about network structure and network flow in the entrepreneurial network (Bliemel et al., 2014). Accordingly, the objects of the network (who) were identified, and their positions in the network were revealed; however, the diversity in the relations was not carefully researched.

2.4.2. The role of social network

Most researchers agree that social networks are crucial to small firms and entrepreneurs in developing their businesses during the entrepreneurial period.

Researchers Donckels and Lambrecht (1995); Hansen and Wernerfelt (1989) all argued that small firms' success is dependent on the network of people who can supply them with the necessary support for developing firm performance. (Capelleras and Rabetino, 2008) also mentioned the beginning stage of entrepreneurship as the "gestation period". They believed that ventures will grow faster if entrepreneurs could use their suppliers and customers as sources of support.

The failure rate of entrepreneurship is much more than the success rate; that is why many researchers believe entrepreneurs can reduce the unwanted rate with support from the entrepreneurial network (Das and Goswami, 2019) and sustain their new firms (Hansen, 1995). The reason is that many new entrepreneurs cannot acquire resources on their own; therefore, they need to access external resources to develop their business.

So, the next important role of social networks is to provide entrepreneurs with opportunities and resources. Greve and Salaff (2003) affirmed that entrepreneurship is significant in establishing enterprises. Besides establishing the business, (Zheng, Ahsan and Denoble, 2019) also believe that an entrepreneurial network will create the flow of resources affecting new ventures at the beginning period. The process is compulsory but not merely an option. Sullivan and Ford (2013) even described entrepreneurs' networks as the principal source for gaining essential necessary to meet new demands. (Semrau and Werner, 2013) also discuss the indispensable role of network relationships in providing essential resources at good deals. De Carolis, Lizky and Eddleston (2009) indicated a new vital resource, contacts, and they also mentioned the reduced risk and newness mitigation when having good networks.

Teece (1987) emphasised the importance of entrepreneurial networking by providing resources. However, he did not reckon that business ideas, knowledge, and competence gained are mainly from external sources. Then later, Gulati, Nohria and Zaheer (2000, 2006) assume that entrepreneurial networking is also a strategic activity to access resources and other opportunities like markets, information, and technologies. Hansen (1995) also mentioned support, knowledge, and distribution channels are benefits that entrepreneurs can obtain through social networks. He even believed that the network could help the business widen its existing resources.

Lastly, the entrepreneurial network will help the entrepreneurs implement and facilitate activities (Arregle et al., 2013), understand better the performance (Capelleras & Rabetino, 2008) and bring effectiveness to those newly found organisations. Bhattacharyya and Ahmad (2010) stated, “any entrepreneurial initiative involves competent use of networks that could generate business or increase the effectiveness in business processes.”

Greve and Salaff (2003) and (Das and Goswami, 2019) also mentioned the role of family members, relatives, friends, institutions and other firms, and ones in their relationship circle as the critical parts. Because they can provide entrepreneurs with different kinds of support and help, we will research more in the network multiplexity part.

In summary, entrepreneurs who rarely possess sufficient resources and competencies need to develop and maintain entrepreneurial networks to access those external resources to establish, implement and facilitate entrepreneurial activities effectively and efficiently, then finally survive and sustain in the long run.

2.5. PERSONAL NETWORK MULTIPLEXITY

2.5.1. Definition of personal network multiplexity

The term multiplexity was coined in the 1950s in sociology (Kregar and Antončič, 2016). Scott (2000) defined multiplexity as the structural feature of social networks measuring the degree of tie overlaps. More specifically, Ferriani, Fonti and Corrado (2012) also defined social network multiplexity as the extent to which two actors are linked together by more than one network in a network, including playing different roles, maintaining different roles, affiliations and exchanges. (Diviák et al., 2019) assumed that most social relationships are multiplexity because they are often based on more than one dimension. He also illustrated the example between individuals who might be both friends and co-workers. Paul (2017) also mentioned multiplexity as a concept to describe several heterogeneous relationships in social network research.

Unlike uniplex relationships, multiplexity relationships constitute many roles rather than single-layered relationships (Kregar and Antončič, 2016). Although, in the context of entrepreneurship, the personal contact networks of entrepreneurs are not too many, the diversity of relationships at the beginning of the period is also worth noticing (Shipilov, 2012).

In entrepreneurial and firm context, Shipilov (2012) also defined multiplexity as involving different relationships between firms and a group of partners and different relationships with distinctive groups of partners. Similarly, and briefly, Bliemel and colleagues (2014) explained multiplexity as “the interaction of exchanges within and across relationships”. They also gave an example that a supplier is also an employer in an organisation. So, there are two relationships between the firm and one of his contacts: buyer-supplier and employer-employee.

Shipilov (2012) also argued that multiplexity in a business network could be created at different levels. With the example, an employee can have a relationship with other colleagues in other companies, combining the formal network multiplexity formed by entrepreneurs to contribute to the company. In the perspective of the thesis, the personal network multiplexity of entrepreneurs will be taken into more consideration rather than networks of staff at the lower level.

Kapucu and Hu (2014) defined multiplexity as multiple types of interactions among organisations. They also compared network multiplexity with standard networks by the higher level of tie strength. Similar to some researchers, they did not mention network multiplexity at the personal level, but he saw it in the scope of big organisations. They argued that friendship networks are multiplexity, but not formal collaborations and entrepreneurs must ensure the relationship will be aligned with the organisational objectives.

Bliemel proposed four levels of multiplexity and Maine (2016), including social multiplexity, relational multiplexity, strategic multiplexity and closed multiplexity. In social multiplexity, the dyad business relationship is being multiplexed by the social dimension. Meanwhile, relational multiplexity includes multiple interdependent layers of business and social exchanges rather than one business transaction in social multiplexity. In terms of strategic multiplexity, it was developed from relational multiplexity. Accordingly, the level of a dyad will become a pair of dyads (Shipilov, 2012). An example of that is an entrepreneur will be the centre of the vertical flow of the network, and they will decide the interdependence of actors. Finally, closed multiplexity refers to the circle relationships in which multiple relationally or strategically multiplex relations become interconnected. In another way, their collective resources can be combined for a more significant and mutually beneficial whole. Each level of multiplexity will be connected with different dynamism and value creation levels.

Accordingly, in the scope of the research, the networking activity of Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector will be seen as strategic multiplexity, meaning that entrepreneurs will be the centre of the vertical flow of the network.

On the other hand, Kregar and Antoncic (2016) viewed multiplexity as three dimensions, including multiple relationships among network members, the overlap between social and economic dimensions of exchange and the degree to which two network members are mutually related via multiple relationships. The opinion on multiplexity is obvious but lacks dynamism, as mentioned by Bliemel and Maine (2015)

In summary, personal network multiplexity can be understood in the scope of the research as the personal relationship diversity of entrepreneurs toward different groups of partners during the nascent period (the setting up business period).

2.5.2. The significance of personal network multiplexity in entrepreneurship to business growth

First and foremost, it is undeniable that the benefits of personal network multiplexity are pretty similar to the benefits that social networks bring to entrepreneurs mentioned in the previous because PNM is also a form of networking. However, in this part, the role of PNM will be taken into consideration more specifically.

Most researchers agree that the most significant role of network multiplexity is contributing to the strategic goals of the organisation and helping the ventures grow (Lee and Tsang, 2001; Shipilov, 2012; Bliemel et al., 2014; Engel et al., 2016)

Besides, due to the limitation of resources at first, external resources would be essential for the firm growth (Bratkovič Kregar and Antončič, 2016). Bliemel and colleagues also think that network multiplexity will help entrepreneurs access resources and exchange them and transform them to form and develop the business.

HÖLSCHER (2019) believed that the multiplexity network is an essential factor contributing to the long-term success of every firm. Apart from the general role of business networks, network

multiplexity will contribute to the formation of closed business networks, which will help companies to sustain and bring more added value to them. The critic of his article on the benefit of network multiplexity is that he only mentioned multiplexity under the scope of B2B context. He did not present personal network multiplexity in private and informal networks such as friends and family, who contributed tremendously with many roles to the survivability and development of new entrepreneurs.

Kapuku and Hu (2014) compared standard business networks and network multiplexity by the strength factor in ties. He also affirmed that network multiplexity would help exchange information and coordinate effort easier and contribute to long terms growth and evolution of companies. Quite similar to HÖLSCHER (2019), the researchers mentioned long-term growth with the help of network multiplexity. Still, the network multiplexity they mentioned was between organisations more than the personal level, which is in turn explored in the thesis.

Isett and colleagues (2011) mentioned friends as the informal source of personal network multiplexity. They can serve as venues for organisations to share information, and solve problems contributing to the resources collection. And they also affirmed that informal structure is the hidden power of networks and might become formal in the future.

Another significance of PNM is that network ties can contribute to the innovation process of the organisation (Huggins and Thompson, 2016). This is vital because innovation will be the weapon for gaining competitive advantages in the high competition context. The innovation here is about technology and the new ways of operating business and new business ideas. The diverse role of actors in the networks will bring more value to innovation.

Entrepreneurs are newcomers to the market; that is why they need support from their network more than anyone else, especially in terms of financing, team-building, strategy from experienced advisors and so on (Alton, 2016). Therefore, personal network multiplexity will be the key to success in the challenging period of entrepreneurship. One actor in the network can play as many roles as possible and contribute many resources to entrepreneurs.

De Hoyos-Ruberto and colleagues (2013) showed the conceptual model of entrepreneurship success based on entrepreneurial social network multiplexity and inter-organisational networking as follows: (Figure 2)

Figure 5: Conceptual model of entrepreneurial success (Ruberto et al., 2013)

Accordingly, entrepreneurial success comes from networking activities inside and outside of the organisation. And the networking activities are under the influence of systematic factors (opportunities, national mindset and education) and individual factors (social competence and self-efficacy of entrepreneurs). The advantage of the entrepreneurial success model is that they mentioned entrepreneurial social networking at a personal level than at the level of organisation because, at the beginning period of starting up, entrepreneurs are the only ones who can count on their personal network multiplexity to survive and develop.

2.5.3. Guanxi (interpersonal relationship) business- the Chinese business philosophy affecting Vietnamese entrepreneurs' network

Guanxi has been an essential and pervasive part of Chinese business for centuries (Luo, 2007). Guanxi has been defined as “relationships or social connections based on mutual interests and benefits, which is achieved by exchanging favours and giving social status between guanxi partners” (Chi and Seock-Jin, 2017). Besides the aspects of mutual interests and benefits, Chen, Chang and Lee (2015) defined Guanxi as a group of people connected by particularistic interpersonal ties cultivated and maintained through trust, obligation, and reciprocity. So, Chang and Lee emphasised trust and obligation as importantly as reciprocity. To be more exact, Guo and Miller (2010) distinguished clearly between guanxi and guanxi webs by defining that guanxi is just a dyadic interpersonal relationship achieved by an individual while the guanxi webs concept refers to the total ties owned by an individual. So the guanxi webs concept is more similar to the social network construct.

Guanxi helps create an intricate network of million of Chinese businesses into a web where implicit obligations, assurance, and understanding are implemented to help those companies on the web sustain the long-term social relationship (Luo, 2007). It is also affirmed that no Chinese company can go far without an extensive guanxi network, and it is considered the lifeblood of both macro-economy and micro-business (Luo, 2007). And Shanshan (2012) also concluded that micro firms and entrepreneurs need a strong guanxi network to access resources that they cannot achieve alone. Guo and Miller (2010) also prove a strong association between guanxi ties and entrepreneurial success in China.

Why Guanxi is mentioned because Vietnamese business society and ethics have been under the dominant cultural influence of Chinese Confucianism for centuries, and Guanxi is a product of Confucian culture (Chi and Seock-Jin, 2017). Accordingly, Confucian social theory highlights the family's important role, which is the basic social unit and kinship is the most significant relationship to an individual. However, family ties are generally based on unconditional loyalty and social obligations but not on mutual benefits (reciprocity). That is why the Guanxi concept was born to serve and cultivate non-kin relationships Guo and Miller (2010). Nonetheless, some scholars argued that Guanxi is evitable for an economic reason because new entrepreneurs must expand their relationships to do business (Scott et al., 2014).

Regarding the network characteristics, Scott and his colleagues (2014) mentioned guanxi typology as family ties, familiar persons, and strangers. In another approach, Chen, Chang and Lee (2015) and other previous researchers posited that the networks are constituted by four relational ties: family ties, business ties, community ties, and government ties. So the second typology seems to be more exact and talks more about the business context of entrepreneurs.

So the difference between Chinese guanxi in Oriental culture and networking in Western culture is that if networking in business in Western culture is more about the agreement in contracts or closing a deal, then, Guanxi is more than that. It is more in terms of long-term period, more trust, more complicated, and basically, it is friendship after all. Furthermore, individuals or organisations must invest more time, dedication, and effort to build guanxi rather than just meeting new partners and exchanging business cards with them (Veem, 2017).

According to the research on the difference between guanxi and networking (Chua, Morris and Ingram, 2008), the most typical similarity between guanxi and western social network is trust. However, the degree of trust is quite variable between those two societies. Accordingly, in guanxi ties in Chinese business culture, affection and cognition-based trust are intertwined in-network relationships, while it is not the case in Western business culture. In addition, the role of indirect ties and personal connections in guanxi is also vital in the Chinese business environment. Therefore, the researchers also warned the westerners doing business in Chinese or Oriental culture to consider these factors.

In a nutshell, the multiplexity business network is even more subtle and complicated in Oriental society under the influence of Guanxi, and Vietnam's business environment is not an exception.

2.5.4. Personal network multiplexity in entrepreneurship in the context of Vietnam

As mentioned before, both Vietnam and China have similarities in the root of Confucianism culture and are under the influence of Guanxi in the business context. This is also illustrated in the cultural dimension model of Hofstede (2020) (Figure 3)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Hofstede (2020) Country Comparison - Hofstede Insights [Online]. Hofstede Insights. Available: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/china,vietnam>

Figure 6: The cultural dimension model comparing Vietnam and China (Hofstede, 2020)

Accordingly, both Vietnam and Chinese score 20 in the individualism dimension, meaning that the society is collectivism and social relationship and self-image are favourable in the society. Besides, family, extended family or extended relationships are valued. Loyalty is vital and overrides other social rules and regulations. People in society take responsibility for other members; employer and employee relationships are under the influence of moral aspects more than rules. Hiring people and promotions are also based on the closeness of relationships such as family or friends. Personal relationships are even highlighted more than tasks (Hofstede, 2020).

Besides, both Vietnam and Chinese are transition economies. If the Chinese government started that after 1978 then Vietnam did it after 1986 (Nguyen, Weinstein and Meyer., 2005). The problem of that period is how to strengthen the private sectors to help them get opportunities and resources to survive and thrive. The business context for those companies is quite adverse, which can be listed as the underdeveloped infrastructure, ambiguous market institutions, not much-

established reputations and history of partnering (Tan, 2007; Nguyen and Rose, 2009). That is why those newly entrepreneurs rely on extensive network multiplexity strategy and trust-based partnerships.

In personal network multiplexity in entrepreneurship in Vietnam, trust is the locus of social networks, which grows personal relationships in the context that a strict circle of kinship or tight social networks are overwhelming (Nguyen and Rose, 2009). Vietnam is growing at a fast rate and witnessing a solid increase in the number of new businesses. Therefore, the demand for doing business with new partners is becoming more apparent. Vietnamese entrepreneurs struggle to go beyond the small circles of relationships in the *guanxi* network (Nguyen, Weinstein and Meyer., 2005). And to implement that well, the adjustment in the level of trust in personal network multiplexity is necessary. Hence, trust is also the issue raised in the interview questions for Vietnamese entrepreneurs to understand more about their personal network multiplexity.

2.5.5. Dynamism and Evolution of network and personal network multiplexity

In the literature, networks are always seen as dynamic relationships and changing (Granovetter, 1985; Chell and Baines, 2000; Anderson and Jack, 2002; Jack et al., 2010; Soetanto, 2019).

Granovetter (1985) argued that social network ties are activated according to need and are hence not fixed. Similarly, Johannisson (1988), for example, argues that establishing and developing a business requires business needs which are different contacts and different resources over time; therefore, the change is inevitable. Meanwhile, Chell and Baines (2000) posited that networks, as entities, can best be considered as a bundle of dynamic relationships facilitated by process-driven factors.

Jack and his colleagues (2010) re-affirmed the resources base views as the reason for the network changes as prior research. However, they also criticised those who stated that the resources-based view is the main reason for network change is narrow. Accordingly, they argued that networks should be based on social factors and network activities are emotional. Therefore, after a period, the bonding will be reinforced more, leading to less reciprocity of resources but more social exchange and mutuality between actors in the network (Figure 11). As mentioned earlier, the view on network change is relatively accurate to the Vietnam context, where collectivism and social relationship are favourable in society.

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Figure 7: Process and changing nature of the network (Jack et al., 2010)

According to the four levels of network multiplexity that Bliemel and Maine (2015) indicated, he showed the difference in dynamism (rate and degree of change between those levels). Accordingly, the social multiplexity level (only two ties in one relationship) is represented by high dynamism, while relational multiplexity (more than two ties in one relationship) is decided by moderate dynamism. The low levels of dynamism belong to strategic multiplexity levels (more than two ties in many relationships) and closed multiplexity (interconnection between actors in the network with multiple ties).

The most recent on the network and network multiplexity changes, Soetanto (2019) stated that networks constantly evolve based on needs, which is congruent to Granovetter (1985) and Johannisson (1988). Nevertheless, he identified development stages where networks are vital for entrepreneurs, including opportunity exploration, resource gathering incubation, early market entry, and growth (Figure 12).

He also explained the change in networks from initial networks to support-based networks, market-based networks then core networks, based on the changes in the strength of ties, density, and size of networks. Accordingly, during the growth period, entrepreneurs will be able to create core networks with almost strong ties in low-density networks and not many new contacts needed, leading to the low dynamism in networks. As a result, the networks became closed during the period, congruent to the highest level of multiplexity that Bliemel and Maine (2015) mentioned. The theory of network change is holistic when considering many factors. Nevertheless, as Jack and his colleagues (2010) indicated, the social factor was not mentioned, so the change in the strength of ties was not fully understood.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263237318300641>

Figure 8: Findings of Soetanto (2019) on the change in networks through the stages in the entrepreneurial journey

The theory of the network changes will be used to ask questions to Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector to shed light on how their network multiplexity changed after the TEA period.

2.6. Conceptual Framework

Based on literature reviews and academic gaps, conceptual models will be formulated as below. This is also the design for the research and formulating of research questions. Accordingly, entrepreneurs will be selected at TEA (under 3.5 years). The context is in the OER sector and

located in Vietnam after doi moi (the economic transition). The topic for research is the personal network multiplexity. This PNM is seen as the role, the content, the activities, and the degrees, which is put under the context of Oriental culture where factors of guan xi such as trust, reputation and relationship are significant. Literature also suggested the evolution of networks or PNM after having supported entrepreneurial growth in the first period. Business growth is usually mentioned in the literature by the factors such as revenue, staff, and sales figures. Finally, the framework will be updated again after the finding extracted from the participants.

Figure 9: Conceptual Framework

2.7. Summary of the literature review

There have been numerous studies researching social networks and entrepreneurs. However, studies on the OER sectors and qualitative research on PNM are hardly found. Regardless of the researcher's efforts, the theory on social networks and entrepreneurs might not be incomprehensive. Nevertheless, the main keyword here is PNM and the OER sectors; therefore, I

allocated appropriately and selectively content and theories relevant to my research object to present in the literature review part. I also tried to search for Guanxi- an Oriental business network, to compare with PNM and the evolution and the change of PNM. Nevertheless, the concepts mentioned were merely definitions and simple explanations due to the size of the thesis. Therefore, the new thesis can focus on those important keywords to support the literature review.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

As mentioned in the literature review, network in general or personal network multiplexity is undeniably a key for the development of any entrepreneur. My primary purpose of the thesis is not to prove this again but explore what is really behind all the networking processes, the complex of the personal network multiplexity created by entrepreneurs at the first stage of entrepreneurship in the overseas educational recruitment sector. The setting of the research is Vietnamese entrepreneurs in Vietnam. A case study approach will involve seven in-depth one-to-one interviews with seven targeted entrepreneurs combined with the data collected from the secondary data (Social media pages, websites, etc.) of those companies and entrepreneurs mentioned. Cross-sectional data were used at the time of interviewing; however, this research requires the interviewees to recall the process of the entrepreneurial period back to two to three years so that the data can also be considered longitudinal. The research also comes up with the research design, and apparently, the research philosophy will be reviewed. After that, the method of collecting and analysing data with thematic analysis will be formulated and justified. Finally, the limitations of the research are also put forward.

3.2. Research philosophy

3.2.1 Research paradigm and philosophical stances

Terre Blanche and Durrheim (1999) developed a paradigm of three philosophies shaping the entire research process: **ontology, epistemology, and axiology (Figure 1)** (Saunders et al., 2016). I based on those philosophies to identify the method that I plan to use for my research.

Accordingly, ontology reflects the nature of reality (Blanche et al. (2014); Saunders et al., 2015). According to the topic that I conducted, I had believed that the reality should be multiple. I thought that each OER entrepreneur will have different ways of networking as well as different opinions on the entrepreneurship based much on their own experiences, backgrounds, and perception.

As to epistemology, it is defined as knowledge philosophy and the origin of knowledge in the context of the research; this knowledge will mostly come from the stories, perceptions, and experiences of interviewees (managers/entrepreneurs) as well as the interpretations of the researcher. The nature of my research is explanatory; thus, stories, experiences, perceptions of participants (entrepreneurs) will all be valuable to my research.

Regarding axiology, the research will be value-bound because the researcher is also the one who works in the industry, analyses cases, and interprets what the interviewees answer. Therefore, subjectiveness is somehow unavoidable.

Considering my research questions and objectives, the interpretivism philosophical stance will be the most suitable because this philosophy emphasises the rich and complexity of reality. That is appropriate for my exploratory purpose to understand entrepreneurs' activities because each entrepreneur will have different views and perspectives about the successful way to develop personal network multiplexity. Satay (2016) also argues that the social world is changing; thus, different points of view will matter rather than just one true reality in positivism.

Based on the selected philosophy, the inductive research approach was chosen because of the nature of exploratory research and the newness of the research problem about personal network multiplexity in OER entrepreneurs in Vietnam.

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Figure 10: Major research philosophies (Saunders et al. 2016, p.178)

3.2.2. Research Approaches - Inductive vs Deductive reasoning

Tracing back to the original paradigm of scientific research, Dewey (1993 cited by Gray 2017) mentioned induction and deduction. Accordingly, the deduction begins with general views and ends with particulars, while induction starts from sporadic details to synthesise into a connected situation (Gray 2017).

As suggested in the correspondent with interpretivism research philosophy of Saunders and colleagues (2016), inductive should be used. Some justifications are that the explanatory research does not require many theories from the beginning. Secondly, the theories in the research are not sufficient and specific enough to understand and explain the phenomenon. Therefore, via collecting data, patterns and meanings or even theories will be generated. It is also the method of inductive approach (Gray 2017)

Practically, the PNM of entrepreneurs in OER companies is unknown to me. I used to be the staff in some companies of that type. However, I have not been in the position of the entrepreneurs in the sector to understand and experience what they have gone through, so I choose the inductive approach to generalise common themes and draw interesting conclusions later on.

3.2.3. The case study approach

“A case study is a research approach that is used to generate an in-depth, multi-faceted understanding of a complex issue in its real-life context” (Crowe et al., 2011)

The case study method is widely and frequently utilised in qualitative research (Baskarada, 2014); Yazan, 2015). In the business case study, a real-time phenomenon will be discovered in business, considering that context will create a difference (Rashid, 2019) or explore the phenomenon through various lenses (Baxter and Jack, 2018). In my thesis, the phenomenon here is the personal network multiplexity with entrepreneurs, and the context is the Vietnamese entrepreneurial background in the OER sector.

The case study also let me approach lenses to capture information on more explanatory 'how', 'what' and 'why' questions (Crowe et al., 2011), which can help me to answer the research question “how personal network multiplexity helped Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector to grow their business?”

Crowe and colleagues (2011) and Hyett, Kenny and Dickson-Swift (2014) mentioned three kinds of cases, including the intrinsic case, the instrumental case, and the collective instrumental case from the theory of Stake (1995). Accordingly, the intrinsic case is used to understand a single case; the instrumental case highlights the issue or refines the theory. Then, in the collective instrumental case, multiple cases will be selected to compare, and five or more cases will be suggested if the theory is subtle (Crowe et al., 2011). In my thesis, the collective instrumental case will be chosen to understand personal network multiplexity (phenomenon) in multiple Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector.

Access is the central consideration of the case study approach that requires researchers to work closely with the case (Crowe et al., 2011). The case should be developed in a relationship between the researcher and informants (Hyett, 2014). I, who had good relationships with some

Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector, decided to choose the approach. The approach also gave me the right to select cases to choose Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector that are interesting and hospitable to my inquiries (Crowe et al., 2011).

Because of selecting the approach, besides the data extracted from the interview with those entrepreneurs, more sources of evidence will need to be present. Therefore, during the time of research, I also observed and followed their companies based on activities on their website, Facebook, and other social media to understand more about their company and the entrepreneurs' characteristics. Although I could not get their financial reports in the beginning years of entrepreneurship, they did not hesitate to mention the figure in approximation, thanks to my relationships with them.

3.3 Research design

3.3.1. Justification of adopting the qualitative method

There are many methods to collect data in the onion model about research strategy. However, all of them can be generalised into „qualitative method“ and „quantitative method“. Each has different responsibility in theoretical and scholarly investigations (Walle, 2015). If quantitative researchers use numerical data and structured, predetermined questions to collect facts, relationships with facts, and quantify conclusions, then qualitative researchers are more concerned about individual viewpoints, perceptions with non-numerical unstructured data (Punch, 2013; Bell and Water, 2014). Qualitative research is also defined as “a form of a social inquiry that focuses on the way people describe and make sense of their experiences and the world in which they live” (Holloway and Wheeler, 2017, p.3)”.

The purpose of the chapter is not to show the distinctions between adopting qualitative or quantitative methods but give justifications for why I (the researcher) choose the qualitative method as the approach for the research. The approach is not seen in contrast to the quantitative method as they complement each other, and each approach has different purposes in answering different questions (Mason, 2002; Brown, 2008).

The qualitative method is considered a popular methodological option in business research to gain insights into organisational behaviours by using unstructured data (Campbell and Göritz, 2014; Creswell and Poth, 2016; (Ting and Tan, 2021).

The reasons for adopting the qualitative method are firstly matching with the aforementioned research philosophy (interpretivism) and research approach (inductive) due to the exploratory purpose of the entire research. I am an educational consultant recruiting students for universities worldwide; however, I wish to become an entrepreneur in the sector instead of being a staff. That is why I want to investigate those entrepreneurs who have their own experience in building networks, especially at the first stage of doing their own business in the sector. Each entrepreneur will have their own subjective experiences, feelings, and networking strategies that I want to capture to find common patterns that can help people who intend to become an entrepreneur in the sector. The process of networking in the early period of entrepreneurship might be not so different. However, each entrepreneur with distinctive characteristics, experiences, and backgrounds might have various actions, reactions, and unique strategies toward the networking process, which would be interesting to explore, and the qualitative method is the most effective way to do so (Holloway and Galvin, 2017). I (the researchers) approach the qualitative method with previous assumptions and theories about networking multiplexity via reading literature reviews. Still, with the approach, I will set aside what I assumed before to do the research with curiosity (Brewer, 2012). Therefore, the participants' information from the successful entrepreneurs will be the most critical data for me to keep conducting the research.

Secondly, the qualitative method is used because the research is about human beings (entrepreneurs), so it will be more convenient, comfortable and spontaneous for those participants (Domegan and Fleming, 2007; Brown, 2008). Besides, close interaction between the researcher and informants via in-depth interviews will show more feelings, emotions, perceptions, and enthusiasm, which is precious to my research when I can understand and realise more what is significant for entrepreneurs' networking process or which is just trivial. For the aforementioned reason, I believe that the quantitative method hardly can deliver. Furthermore, using the case study approach in the qualitative method, I expected to receive specific answers, directions or solutions from informants (entrepreneurs). This helped my research become more interesting and more helpful to myself and the ones who intend to do

business and implement the PNM process during the first stage of opening their own business in the sector of recruiting students.

When choosing a quantitative or qualitative approach for the thesis, I did not purposely choose the qualitative method. This approach convinced me because of its effectiveness in exploring the social business world. The informants (the entrepreneurs) in the sector will reveal the secret of personal networking multiplexity to me subjectively and individually, which numeric data barely conveys.

The last reason is from the justification of Creswell (2013), the qualitative method is used when a particular population is studied, and there is a need to listen to “unheard voices”, and detailed pictures can be only achieved by talking directly to people. In this research, I wished to listen to unheard voices, experiences and feelings of entrepreneurs through their networking process in the OER sector.

There have been criticisms of using the qualitative method involving bias, lack of rigour, subjectivity, time-consuming matters, small sample size and ethical issues (Oppong, 2013; Galdas, 2017; Queirós, Faria and Almeida, 2017). However, Maxwell (2008) and Ting, H. and Tan, K. (2021) argued that qualitative is there not to test measurable hypotheses but to work with the multi-layered realities under the universe of meaning, attitudes, values extracted from expressions, interactions, and experiences that qualitative method cannot merely measure. They also concluded that the qualitative method is concerned with exploring social relations, which is suitable for the networking topic in business that I chose for the thesis.

3.4. Data collection

3.4.1. Population and choice of sample

The population of research objectives is the collection of Vietnamese entrepreneurial SMEs in the OER sector. The population is selected by the fact and the setting mentioned in the chapter one, which is the number of OER companies doubled only in one to two years (Nhat, 2015) and the very high failure rate of start-up companies in Vietnam (from 95% to 97%). Therefore, the population will be interesting for me to carry out research. However, it is impossible to research the entire population, so the sampling method was used.

The sampling method is defined as a “complex process which is informed by the research question, practical and theoretical considerations, and of course, it is guided by the phenomenon under investigation as well as by ethical principles.” (Holloway and Galvin, 2017, p.141). Sampling is used because it is nearly impossible and unnecessary to look at the whole population in the qualitative method due to the limitations of resources (time, efforts, money) and the theory saturation (Mack et al., 2005). Saunders and colleagues (2016) also agree that sampling is an optional but effective technique to reduce the time, cost, and accessibility compared to the research on the entire population. It is impractical for me to research all employers and CEOs in the sector when there is always a deadline for research and the availability of informants. Therefore, the sampling technique is as important as other thesis works. If the sampling process is not done correctly, no further steps can be achieved.

In terms of sample size, I planned to recruit 8 to 12 entrepreneurs, or directors of existing OER companies will be selected for interviews. The number is given based on the advice from Sandelowski (2015). Accordingly, the sample size should not be small, leading to difficulty in supporting claims and categorising. Nevertheless, if the sample size is too large, it would lead to theoretical saturation, difficulty in coming up with conclusions and challenges to implementation. The number is quite rational because the entrepreneurs selected mainly are existing companies and working from one year to seven years. So they are considered on the right track and have the same secrets for network multiplexity experience to be successful.

Nevertheless, the interviews should be continued for further research because networking multiplexity experience is different for each individual. The way of networking will change dramatically soon for entrepreneurs, so it would be great if the topic is still exploited to facilitate people who plan to start up in the sector. Within my limited capabilities, I will try my best to carry out the small but potential research and still waiting for more researchers to extend this.

I am lucky enough to have been working in the OER sector for more than six years, which helped me quickly access entrepreneurs in the sector. The fact that I used to work with some companies in the sector at the early stage of doing their business from the perspective of staff helped me understand more when interviewing those entrepreneurs.

It is advised that the characteristics and briefs of the participant are essential for readers to locate and become familiar with them in research (Brown, 2008; Enago, 2020). However, my sample is

primarily entrepreneurs, who are pretty strict and careful about keeping their identities confidential. This required me to describe them adequately so that they and their company would not be identified. Therefore, I tried to brief them with information including Name (In initials, age, marital status, location when starting up, years of establishment, education, and work experience), I purposefully chose samples based on these criteria: (1) Who are entrepreneurs of OER company in Vietnam (2) have been working in the sector for a minimum of 2.5 to 3.5 years, and (3) starting from 2000- to recent years.

However, only seven companies responded to my topic when it comes to reality. Some of them were not interested in the topic. Some of them were busy with their schedule and could never make appointments with me, and two of them went bankrupt by the time of research, so they were not willing to give answers or attend my interviews. The high refusal rate of interviews also indicates that it is pretty tough to have information from the people in the high positions. It can be understood that information like entrepreneurship or networking is also considered sensitive or business secrets of those businesses or individuals.

3.4.2. Snowball sampling

As mentioned, I have been working in the OER sector for many years, so I formed some relationships with employers and entrepreneurs beforehand, which can provide me with the primary data for research. Nonetheless, I was in the United Kingdom at the time of the research, so it was hard for me to access those entrepreneurs who are pretty busy and have plenty of things to take care of.

I used a method called “snowball sampling”, a nonprobability method applied when the research target is difficult to approach (Mertens, 2010; Naderifar, Goli and Ghaljaie, 2017). This method is also called the chain method. In this method, my first informants or participants will introduce those who they might know and have the same situations (who are also OER entrepreneurs) to me. This method is considered cost-effective and efficient because the research will not take much time to look for, and those who are introduced will be more willing to attend the interview (Naderifar, Goli and Ghaljaie, 2017). As mentioned, these groups that I am approaching to interview will be all entrepreneurs, and it will be difficult to contact them. Therefore, I planned to ask for help from the first or two entrepreneurs to connect with them. After talking to them, I

realised that it might be more challenging because most of them (entrepreneurs) are competitors in the sector. They were not so willing to introduce other entrepreneurs to me or just gave me contacts. I had to contact myself, which I considered better than nothing.

Besides, I pushed another step by asking for help from some of my friends who are university representatives. Although not valid for my research, the group used to work with agents and entrepreneurs in the OER sectors, and luckily, they managed to help me connect with many potential entrepreneurs for my research.

Regardless of any introduction, it was never an easy task to connect with CEOs or employers of the companies. That is why I had to engage closely and regularly interact with them on the online social platforms with a belief that rapport with informants could lead to easier connection and open the window onto their feelings and perception (Brewer, 2000; Brown, 2007). My networking process is quite exhausting because of many reasons. The first one was caused by Covid-19, so I could not fly back to my own country as well as ask them for face-to-face meetings to warm up initial rappings. The second reason was related to the nature of business people who are extremely busy with their job and always set priorities for any tasks. Lastly, the lockdowns and travel restrictions adversely affected the sector, leading to my difficulty approaching and networking with those figures.

Fortunately, I managed to have seven interviews with all the challenges above, and their profiles are shown below. Wolcott (2001, 2006) and Lorraine (2007) agreed that the description of each interview should be offered so that the reader feels comfortable with the stories, locates the participants better and is more familiar with the characters in the thesis. I also use pseudonyms instead of real names so that their true identities cannot be identified.

Cam, male, 44, married with two children, a CEO and director founding his company for eight years, studied a Master's degree in the UK, then worked for Education and Training Ministry in Vietnam before starting up.

Ha, female, 40, single mom – a founder establishing her company for four years, once taught English in schools, used to work for OER company before starting her own.

Quynh, female, 33, married with a son, a CEO and director establishing her own company for seven years, studied Master and living permanently in the UK, used to work in accounting, then real estate sector before changing to OER sector.

Nha, female, 55, divorced with a daughter, a co-founder and CEO establishing her company for 22 years, worked as Literature Teacher, English teacher, and a Master student in Education in Australia before starting up.

Tung, male, 29, newly married, a CEO and co-founder with his wife for his newly established company for 2.5 years. (This case is relatively new, under three years compared to my criteria; however, it was still valid because I still had the time to talk to him and review his responses when his company passed three years, and I had yet to submit my thesis at that time).

Tra, female, 42, married, co-founder and director of her company established for 17 years, working as a Marketing lecturer, and studying Master in the UK beforehand.

Phuong, female, 45, married to a foreigner husband, founder and CEO of her own company. Her company has been established for seven years. She got a 100% scholarship at Toulouse 1 University in France and studied there before returning to Vietnam to become a lecturer. She had been working with Vietnamese universities till 2016.

3.4.3. Collecting data using a semi-structured interview

The interview is considered the most common format of data collection in qualitative research (Jamshed, 2014) because the method can contribute to discovering participants' feelings, perceptions, experiences, values, and thoughts (Holloway and Galvin, 2017). The interview process is also defined as “asking purposeful questions and carefully listening to the answers”, which helps researchers “gather valid and reliable data that are relevant to research questions and objectives (Saunders et al. 2016, p. 388). The research explored entrepreneurs’ experiences using PNM, which is considered a secret of business. Therefore, interviews will be the most suitable for sharing. Brown (2008) also argues that the interview method is ideal for understanding participants' experiences and helps them express themselves in their own words and own pace.

Regarding the typology of interviews, Bells (2005) grouped structured interviews and semi-structured interviews into a group and considered unstructured interviews as another group that requires many efforts and skills to implement and the demand on the expertise of interviewees. However, the method will create a wealth of valuable data for interviewers. Meanwhile, Saunders and colleagues (2016) left the structured interview in the standardised group and put other interview types in the non-standardised one. I prefer the classification of Saunders and colleagues (2016) more because he argued more clearly that the structured interview would be suitable with the quantitative method while the other two will be more appropriate with the

qualitative method. Besides, Saunders and colleagues (2016) also mentioned internet interviews (figure 11), which are very important in the era. It is also how I used to do interviews with my participants during the Covid-19 period.

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Figure 11: Forms of interview (Saunders et al. 2016, p.167)

In the qualitative research, I chose a semi-structured interview for the following reasons: First, I planned to choose a non-structured interview based on some arguments from experienced researchers. Accordingly, unstructured interviews allow participants a greater voice and reduce the interviewer's influence (Brown 2008). Besides, it will bring to interviewers more valuable data thanks to participants' expertise (Bell, 2005). However, I realised how much time I needed

to allocate for the thesis and the need for academic skills and expertise to control (Bell 2005). I decided to use a semi-structured interview, which allows me to set guidelines and control the data I planned to collect (Jamshed, 2014; Saunders et al., 2016) while still retaining the essence of an unstructured interview.

The second reason is that if I conduct unstructured interviews with participants, it would be a lack of professionalism given that our interviewees are all CEOs and entrepreneurs and heads of companies because, in the interview type, predetermined questions will not be prepared first. Saunders and colleagues (2016) also highlighted that the unstructured interview is considered informal.

My choice to change to semi-structured interviews was also received advocates from Holloway and Galvin (2017). They argued that a semi-structured format is widely used in qualitative research because it helps researchers collect similar data types to reduce the time and lower the drop rate.

Questions formulated were based on the conceptual framework and existing literature review so that, at the end of the research, I can compare the findings with the literature. There are seven main questions proposed besides small questions incurred when participants' answers are not clear or need more clarification. Besides, informants were also asked about their backgrounds and the history and overview of their companies. Regarding the languages, all participants agreed on using Vietnamese, although some can speak English well. As they mentioned, expressing their ideas in their mother tongue was more comfortable for them.

Unfortunately, the face-to-face interviews were unable to be implemented in Vietnam because I was in the UK at the moment of researching— so I used an internet-mediated interview format – Skype audio chat, as guided by Saunders and colleagues (2016). I also used notes to summarise the main ideas or interesting statements from interviewees. I applied this technique because of its usefulness in making significant notations (Thomas, Nelson, and Silverman (2011). The audio recording function embedded in Skype was also helpful for me to replay and observe participants more carefully via audio.

I applied one-to-one semi-structured interviews and took notes and audio-recording on Skype for the data collection procedures. According to Oakley (1998) (cited by Jamshed, 2014), “qualitative interview is a framework type in which the practices and standards are not only recorded but also achieved, challenged and as well as reinforced”. Therefore, besides the usual standards of interviews, I also re-examined the data collected and implemented follow-up interview sessions with some participants when some items needed clarification.

3.4.4. Interview questions guideline

The purpose of the interview is to listen to participants but not make them listen to interviewers (Menzies et al., 2016; Roberts, 2020), especially in the qualitative method where everything should be explored, and answers from informants would be the primary data. However, it is necessary to have a general guideline for questions to ensure the time to be allocated correctly, avoid wasting participants' time, and avoid the conversation being dried up (Brown, 2008). I was also advised to share the guideline with participants so that they will have a big picture of what I (the researcher) plan to ask and reduce the stress for them (Roberts, 2020). These types of questions adapted from Brown (2008) and Roberts (2020) are illustrated below:

Questions	Example
<p>Orientation questions.</p> <p>These questions are usually raised at the beginning of the interview so that they will feel more comfortable and know as well as expect what kind of interview they are attending</p>	<p>- How do you understand the networking multiplexity from your point of view?</p> <p>Could you please become my manager and explain your point of view about the networking process at the beginning stage of doing business?</p>
<p>Main questions (Grand tour questions)</p> <p>The questions should be aligned with the research questions and objectives. These also need to be general broad and open-ended, so the participants can feel free to answer. Each question should cover each key theme of the research.</p>	<p>Can I ask you to remember the groups of people you contacted when you first started your own business and how did they help you and your company?</p> <p>- What are the significant achievements that you and your company have gained after the networking activity?</p>

<p>Follow up questions (mini-tour questions) Raised when having received answers from main questions to clarify things or understand more about the answers. These questions can appear thorough the interview.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What was your reaction after being successful thanks to the network multiplexity? - Was your wife/husband also an inspiration source besides helping you fund the business?
<p>Example questions and Experience questions These questions are raised to make the answers more vivid and to add the emotional factors to the interview process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you help me to answer what are the most difficult things to utilise your network multiplexity? (Example) - What was it like when you got successful thanks to a network contact? (Experience)
<p>Debriefing questions These questions are usually asked at the end of the interview to help interviewees reduce stress and display their needs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Would you like to add any more information about network multiplexity that you haven't mentioned yet? - What is your feeling after the interview?

Figure 12: Questions guideline (adapted from Brown, 2008; Roberts, 2020)

3.5. Type of data and data collection method

3.5.1 Primary data

The author will collect primary data in the research via interviews and notes with entrepreneurs, CEOs, and chairpersons of OER company. Besides, the data is also gathered by the observation method permitted by one newly founded OER company.

More specifically, semi-structured interviews will be used because they serve well the research purposes, “asking purposeful questions and carefully listening to the answers” (Saunders et al.,2016, p. 388). Besides, semi-structured interviews help participants freely express their views with some guidance. So, the response returned will be under some control and still ensure the characteristics of an unstructured interview.

Besides semi-structured interviews, the field note method was also used in interviews with participants to benefit from contextual information (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2017).

In addition, company websites, brochures, and other media social networks of those companies were also reviewed to understand the company's background and overall situation objectively, as suggested by Guo and Miller (2010).

3.5.2 Secondary data

Secondary data is data collected by someone else rather than the author for other primary purposes (Johnston, 2017). In the research, entrepreneurs' data would be extracted from Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) because they have updated information each year for the entrepreneurship situation in each country, including Vietnam.

Besides, ICFE Monitor is also a reliable secondary data trust because they objectively produce international study trends and data reports serving the benefit of the sector. And the source is also used in the research.

3.6. Qualitative Data Analysis

Data analysis is one of the most critical steps in research, requiring an appropriate method. Based on the nature of the qualitative and case study approach and the justification of the method, the **thematic analysis** will be selected to “search for themes or patterns across a data set” (Saunders et al., 2016, p. 388). Since then, I can extract some practical theories about networking multiplexity from Vietnamese successful and prestigious entrepreneurs in the OER sector.

This technique will be illustrated in six steps listed by (Braun and Clarke (2006), including familiarising data, generating codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report (Figure 13).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. [Online] Vol.3 (2), pp.77-101. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

Figure 13: Steps of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke (2006))

I did follow exactly the steps to analyse the data.

Step 1: Familiarising myself with my data.

First, after getting approval from the entrepreneurs who are my research target, I recorded all the answers from them with their permission. Then I transcribed all the data because I believed that I could miss important information if I did not do so. Besides, because the participants are all Vietnamese, and they were required to speak Vietnamese when attending the interviews, so besides the steps listed, exact translations are also vital. I also did not forget to make some notes about the unusual feelings or reactions of informants, such as excitement and hesitation, because I thought it could help me interpret more accurately.

Step 2: Generating initial code:

The coding was also an exciting part of this. I had to turn what entrepreneurs said into codes to search for themes more easily; those themes that I found will be reviewed and put on a thematic map. Each transcript was separately analysed and coded manually one at a time (Please see Appendix E for the subthemes and codes table). The coding and theme parts were challenging and somehow subjective since I had to use my hunches, insights, past experiences, and intuition to interpret most of the time (Creswell, 2013). This phase has been reviewed twice or three times to make sure comprehensive coding. Fortunately, I used to work in the sector; therefore, I could quickly detect codes.

Step 3: Searching for themes

Fortunately, I had accessed literature before that, so I accumulated and learned quite a few terms to support the process of naming themes. An illustration of that is the way that I group close family and friends of entrepreneurs into “strong-tie relationships” and other partners of entrepreneurs into “weak- tie relationships”.

Then after naming themes or defining them as the new theory, and those are what I wanted to help me answer research questions and objectives and reinforce or compare with what I had found in the literature part. The detailed codes and subthemes are illustrated clearly in the Appendix E.

Step 4: Reviewing themes

Phase four regards the refinement of themes on level one and level two. At level one, I reviewed all the collated extracts for themes and checked if they formed a coherent pattern. To do so, I had to re-read all the data in the code groups and re-check if they fit within the proposed theme. At level 2, I looked at the themes created, then put them in relation to the whole dataset, and checked again if the preliminary thematic map reflected the data set.

For example, when I re-read again the data set about the reason why the participants wanted to start up as entrepreneurs, they said that they wanted to be called boss or director and to be admired by other people when starting up. So, I first just put these into a bigger theme which is the passion for opening a company. But when I reread it, I decided to put them in a sub-theme called desire for power and status to make their ideas more clearly.

Step 5: Defining and naming themes:

In step number 3, I also named themes; however, there were some changes and amendments from step 4 as well as I wanted to make sure the theme names represented the perspective of participants in the best way, so I changed theme names again in order to convey the “story” behind them names of themes effectively.

For example, in sub-theme five, I named it “Personal Network Multiplexity strategy in the Covid period” beforehand. However, after re-reading the data set, I decided to name it again as “Personal Network Multiplexity strategy in unprecedented period (Covid)”. This will help the reader still to be able to know that the unprecedented period here is the Covid, but also help the reader to have thoughts about how OER entrepreneurs do networking activities in the period of other unprecedented events apart from Covid.

Another illustration is I re-named a sub-theme with a question mark to stimulate readers when mentioning the change of network multiplexity, which is “Unchanged relationships – Do they remain unchanged?”. This theme will talk to readers that there will be relationships will be unchanged after the period of networking activities. Still, they will be curious and wonder if any changes in those seemingly unchanged relationships are there.

Step 6: Producing the report

This step involved the write up of the data analysis, which I have presented in the findings chapter. This was the last opportunity for me to select important extracts, so I constantly went back to the literature and research questions to make sure the selected extracts were meaningful and able to convey the messages of participants.

Mentioning the process of data analysis, I could have used NVIVO software to improve the quality of the qualitative process, manage data easily, find themes easier, and save time and energy for data classification (Dollah, 2017). However, I did not implement the software because I did not manage to learn properly during the short period of DBA. The second reason is that NVIVO is not able to interpret data, and I still had to read the transcripts many times to understand fully the content. From all of the above, I decided to analyse the data manually. In the future, I totally believe that with the qualitative method, NVIVO or other qualitative method software will be extremely useful, especially with a large number of samples.

3.7. Pilot study

Hassan and colleagues (2006) highlight the crucial roles of a pilot study by claiming that a pilot study will assist in testing the proposal's feasibility, including the research process, sample strategies, and data collection method. It is also important for the quality improvement and

efficiency of the study (In, 2017). Nevertheless, Williams-McBean (2019) cited some previous researchers saying that a pilot study might not be necessary because the entire process of data collection includes improving the research process, so even a pilot study could be used as the main data. However, it was also Williams-Mc Bean (2019) as well as Mollas and his colleagues (2019) admitted that a pilot study is essential for novice researchers because it could help to raise confidence, help the training and practice, help to identify the areas for improvement and most importantly, help to increase the credibility of entire qualitative researching theses.

In my thesis, Ms. H was the one selected for a pilot study. At first, I sent her some general questions for her to prepare because I believed that there were some questions she needed to prepare before answering. Nevertheless, it took me an hour and a half to finish the interview, exceeding the time that I told them. At the end of the interview, she suggested me the interview time should be exact, as I had stated, participants are all CEOs and time is their money. Ms. H also suggested me to explain the question about the different roles of stakeholders supporting entrepreneurs because it was hard for her to understand. Thanks to her questions and suggestions, I could be able to adjust the questions and make necessary changes to the research process. One more important thing added is the suggestion about Covid-19. I had not planned to go deeper into it; however, her company is one of the companies succeeded in surviving and still developing in the Covid-19 period. Then, she suggested me to put more questions regarding network multiplexity development in the context of the pandemic and unprecedented events. If I had not done the pilot test with her, I could have lost the opportunity to go back to check my questions as well as missed the important idea about the international educational recruitment situation of companies under Covid-19.

3.8. Ethical Considerations

Nowadays, the role of ethical principles is more salient than ever to protect the dignity of participants and information publication (Mantzorou, 2011). Therefore, researchers must face ethical challenges in all the stages of the thesis, especially with the nature of the qualitative method (Sanjari et al., 2014), including anonymity, Informed consent, confidentiality, beneficence- do not harm, privacy, and other researchers' potential impacts on the informants and vice versa.

Similarly, UWS (2021) also has five principles that every researcher of the Uni must comply with before implementing research, including beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, justice, and truthfulness, which are quite the same as researchers' opinions.

In terms of beneficence, I believe that my thesis is beneficial to entrepreneurs who plan to start up their businesses, especially in Vietnam or Asian countries. This also contributes to the literature for those who would like to refer to qualitative research about network and network multiplexity and entrepreneurship. It does not harm the participants because each experience of an entrepreneur is different. It is difficult to imitate the success of my participants because their success came from many factors, not only the networking theme exploited.

Besides, I was required to submit an ethics review application before carrying out the data collection process. I have adhered to the regulations of UWS about research ethics by sending my participants informed consent letters. In the letter, my participant knew the interview's topic and content. They also knew about the time allocation, a description of risks, a description of benefits, disclosure of alternate procedures, and a statement about confidentiality (pseudonyms used for their true names). Besides, their participants' rights were also notified, along with contact information and a statement regarding voluntary participation.

I also referred to the journal "The ethics of action research participant" by Davidson and colleagues (2020) and closely followed the framework in the journal because I believed that ethics issue in action research is even more important than general research because it involves client organisations. Accordingly, there are four ethical attentions that I took into consideration, including collaboration, competence, persistence, and consent. Associating with for ethical participation issues, I ensured that ten criteria were followed.

As for the collaboration issue, I did ensure that all my interviewees knew about the research process and the changes that I made during the research period. An illustration of this is when the outbreak of Covid-19 has stopped, and companies have gradually recovered from Covid-19; I came back to ask about the business situations of the companies which had just started up before Covid (Ms. Ha's and Mr. Tu's). I interviewed them again to find out how the business situation and the networking strategy have changed after the pandemic. I also expected that some companies of the interviewees might go bankrupt or stop operating because of the pandemic. Also, associating with collaboration, I explained carefully the academic parts,

including the notions and clear examples, so that my interviewees could be confident and well-known about the research that they were planning to take part in.

In terms of the competence issue, I have been in the sector for seven years, and I was quite confident in terms and activities of the sector. Nevertheless, regarding the professional experiences of CEO, I found myself inexperienced. That is why I did read and research quite a few business-case studies in my country to make sure that I could interview those high-level participants in the most effective way before doing it. Davidson and colleagues (2020) did not encourage “fake it until to make it” technique, but fortunately, my participants are all in my connection, so they understood enough to teach me something that I was not fully aware of. Also, regarding the competence issue, English is not my mother tongue and not my participants’, so I used my own language to interview them to ensure that they understood all the questions, whereby they could answer the questions without any barriers. I also asked for help from a senior professor to help me proofread for the perfection of the formal thesis.

Regarding the persistence issue, I did try my best to make interview arrangements with my participants, given that they were too busy with their schedules. I could have given up some follow-up interviews after the covid faded, but I still managed to do so because I believed there would be plenty of surprising results after the pandemic. And above all, I complete the thesis with perseverance.

Finally, the consent issue is the focal point of ethical consideration. My participants were all CEO, so they had experience in many types of research and interviews, making them easier to agree and participate in my research. I also made sure that their names were replaced by pseudonyms. Finally, all participants were well informed that they could withdraw at any point in the research as well as they could refuse to answer some of the questions if they want.

3.9. Reflexivity on research process

3.9.1 Researcher’s Role and Influence on Research Process

I had quite a few experiences in the sectors when I was with those entrepreneurs in the first stage of doing their business in the OER sector. Being a student studying overseas also helps me understand much or less about the personal networking multiplexity of those entrepreneurs.

My research roles in the research process were firstly conceptualising the theories about entrepreneurs in the OER sectors, network theories and choosing the theories suitable the most to my thesis. Afterward, based on suggestions from extant literature, I came up with research aim and questions. My second role is gathering data from selected samples to enlighten the theory as well discover new contributions to the theories. The last role is writing up and connecting all the parts to become a completed piece of research.

In the research, I stood in the position that I am an international student who has understood the OER sector in the perceptions of clients. I am also an experienced consultant who has got seven years of working experience in the field of recruiting international students for international educational institutions, and worked mostly with small and medium start-up companies; thus I could understand somehow the way my employers do networking activities to develop their entrepreneurship. Finally, I am also a researcher who can conduct research design to find the answers to my questions and see the problem scholastically.

Some limitations of the research method

The first drawback of the qualitative method, as other research uses the same method, is the small sample size, so it might not be too convincing to apply to all populations. However, the objective of my qualitative method is to seek out the secrets of entrepreneurs in the OER sector in using network multiplexity to develop their businesses, so we never can find a common answer to the questions. That is why this sample choice may be still valid.

Similarly, using case-study approach did not produce results typical for all Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector. Nevertheless, the approach is based on my good relationships with entrepreneurs in the sector; hence, the information collected consists of a high level of honesty and sincerity. Although each case study is an individual identity with specific stories, they also have some common personal network multiplexity recipes to share.

During the interview, the timeframe 30min to 1 hour was a barrier because some content was not conveyed fully. However, sometimes I was unable to extend the time because all of my informants are entrepreneurs, so they are very strict with time management and very busy with their schedules.

I also believe that personal networking multiplexity in entrepreneurial business is very important, intricate, and complicated in the Asian culture and Vietnam, as mentioned in the literature review. It is also considered one of the successful secret recipes for entrepreneurship. That is why I reckon those entrepreneurs could not share every detail openly with me.

During transcribing, the translation part seemed to be the most challenging because the difference in language might have led to some misunderstandings or information leakage. After that, when I analysed data, it might have some misinterpretations because I was never an entrepreneur. I might have put some subjective assumptions and perceptions on the informants' ideas. I might also have misunderstood some answers in the perceptions of those entrepreneurs, as I mentioned in the research role and bias part.

The Covid-19 pandemic is also a factor affecting the opportunity to go back to Vietnam for the interviewing process. The face-to-face interviews would have a much more practical understanding of the topic and build up the closeness between the participants and me.

Finally, although I mentioned that I have been working in the OER sector for more than seven years, however, most of the time, I stood in the position of staff but not an entrepreneur. So, I still consider myself an outsider. I could not feel what those entrepreneurs have suffered, and hardly understand how happy they were when they succeeded in utilising personal networks or how disappointed they felt when they were unable to achieve networking opportunities.

However, I believe what I knew about the networking multiplexity in the sector is far beyond what those entrepreneurs have experienced. On the other hand, I was not in Vietnam for many years, and many companies have been set up. So, I believe some of my assumptions or perception might be outdated. Therefore, bias may exist in the study, especially regarding the interpretations. Nevertheless, I tried to be as objective and based on context awareness as I could to relate to them to the fullest.

3.10. Summary

The informants for the qualitative method were selected based on a set of prior criteria. Many complex data were collected from the interviews with those seven participants via in-depth interviews. Applying snowball sampling and the help from the relevant people, the researcher managed to recruit appropriate participants for interviews. The language used was Vietnamese; therefore, transcribing and translating were mandatory. After that, coding and naming themes were implemented to develop new findings on personal network multiplexity for entrepreneurs in the OER sector. The case study approach was used with the assistance of the Thematic Analysis method. There were challenges and difficulties as well as limitations across the method. However, with the enthusiasm and support of the participants, I (the researcher) was able to conduct this properly.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS

4.1. Overview

The study explores how Vietnamese entrepreneurs developed their personal network multiplexity to advance their business in the overseas educational recruitment sector. Areas to be discovered included the motivation of entrepreneurs in the OER sector, difficulties and obstacles in starting up, the role of personal network multiplexity in coping with entrepreneurial challenges, the evolution and dynamism of PNM and reflections on the network-building strategies of those entrepreneurs. In this chapter, the participants' backgrounds will be revealed for readers to understand and locate them better. Finally, a brief overview of major finding themes is also provided.

4.2 Background of Participants

Starting up as an entrepreneur was a life-changing experience for all the entrepreneurs in the study. They all had the same goal of being successful entrepreneurs in the OER sector; however, their perceptions, motivations, and attitudes are quite different. Recognising these differences helped me understand more the essence of their entrepreneurial journey and how their characteristics and background could affect their network multiplexity strategy.

To do so, I based on the first interview question, which is an introduction about yourself and your company, to give the first evaluations. Then I also use my interview notes to discover the personality and communication styles. Moreover, I did not only interview one time but also followed up with the cases that I thought I needed to explore more.

A point to note here is that those seven participants are somehow related to me. Some were close to me before, some were more distant but also knew me, and some were introduced to me by the snowball sampling method, as mentioned earlier. Fortunately, all those informants were CEO, so they were knowledgeable, professional, polite, and willing to help. They also knew how to deliver the helpful and valuable information that I was looking for. As a result, their background will be revealed below.

Ha

Before starting up, **Ha** was my colleague at the previous OER company. At that time, she was the head of Sales and Marketing in the Vietnamese branch of the company. She just started up three years ago, but she does advance to a long step in her career to be a successful entrepreneur in the OER sector. She is a cheerful and friendly lady who is easy-going and open-minded. She is over 40s, but she looks much younger than her age. I set an appointment with her online like other candidates because I could not fly back to Vietnam, where travels were restricted under the influence of Covid 19. When I interviewed her, I felt that she was very positive, and perhaps Covid 19 could not strike the strong will women sitting in front of my screen.

She told me about her journey with all her excitement. She has always loved education, and she had been teaching English for 20 years before working for an OER to find scholarships for her son. When she had more opportunities and the companions from three other friend co-founders, she decided to start up in May 2018. She did not hesitate to share with me about her marital status as a single mom, and she is also proud that a woman might fail in a marriage, but she won't fail in the business. She has two children, one of them studying abroad and a 9-year-old girl. Besides recruiting students for overseas educational institutions, she also has a small English department in the company to teach students wishing to study abroad. Moreover, she also connected with immigration law companies in other countries to support immigration issues for her client.

Cam

Cam used to be my ex-boss in Vietnam, so I entirely understand his characteristics and the journey he started up. After three to four years of entrepreneurship in the OER sector, his company expanded quickly. After eight years, it has become one of the leading companies in the OER sector in Vietnam, with the only branch in Hanoi. When I left Vietnam, I worked for the other company and did not contact him much; therefore, it was hard for me to direct message or call him. Hence, I composed a lengthy email hoping that he could help with the interview, and he agreed.

Like Ha, Cam is a man having nerves of steel. Although he lost his left arm in an accident, I felt he always had to struggle two to three times compared to ordinary people to become successful. When I worked with him, he made use of all the time he had to work and exercise to get fit. He is an icon that I admire the most.

In 2000, Cam was sent abroad to study Master in Investment at Brighton University, the UK, thanks to his achievement in the study, which inspired his love for UK education. When he returned to Vietnam in 2002, he worked for the Ministry of Education and Training as the head of the International Education office – in charge of connecting Vietnamese students with foreign schools and universities. Ten years later, in 2012, he decided to start up his own business and left the Ministry.

His company's strategy was that he only focused on the OER sector and other visa support services in one office only in Hanoi but did not extend to other services like English classes and immigration services. Cam's co-founder is his wife. However, his wife is working full-time in a bank in Vietnam.

Quynh

Quynh was my ex-boss when I studied in the UK. I worked part-time for her company as an educational consultant for students in Vietnam, so I heard many entrepreneurial stories from her. She was born in 1989, in her early 30s. She is young but has eight years of starting up. Mentioning her personality, she is swift, shown in her ability to grab opportunities, deliver services to customers, and the way she talked to other people and me. She told me that she only sleeps for 4 -5 hours per day and can sit 9 hours in a car without any sickness. She is also straightforward and friendly, which helps her connect effortlessly with anyone, even strangers.

Unlike other entrepreneurs in their studies, she graduated in the UK with an accounting and finance major and decided to stay permanently in the UK to start up a company supporting Vietnamese people in the UK in terms of immigration, accounting, and study abroad service for their family members in Vietnam in 2014. Two years later, she returned to Vietnam to start up another company in the OER sector. She co-founded with her cousin to help her direct the office in Vietnam, and she will manage from the UK. She got married to a Vietnamese professor teaching at Cambridge University before she started up.

Quynh has more advantages than other entrepreneurs because she has an office in Vietnam and the UK. Therefore, she used that to provide students with many services besides studying abroad, which are accounting and finance for students who would like to start up after study, immigration, and real-estate service.

Nha

Through a network with a university representative, I texted Nha on Facebook about the possibility of my interview. After talking about my topic, she showed interest in my study and appointed an interview day with me. Nha is over 50s, and she is one of the first person starting up a good OER company in Vietnam, established in 2000. My first impression is that she is around my mother's age, but she knows technology very well. She is also very good at using Facebook and other online social platforms. Perhaps they are the requirements of the job.

I knew she belonged to an ethnic minority in Vietnam through the interview. She said she had to overcome many obstacles and challenges of discrimination to become a successful entrepreneur. After getting two degrees in literature and English in Vietnam, she was fortunate to get an AusAid scholarship from the Australian government. Then, she chose Education Management at New South Wales University to study in 1998. After returning to Vietnam, she decided to start up with her friends studying with her in Australia in the OER sector.

An incident occurring in her life is that she divorced her husband one year after starting up. However, she still stood firm and maintained her company as one of the leading agencies in the OER sector, with global markets and four branches in Vietnam.

Tung

Through a relationship in the sector, I was introduced to Tung. He and Quynh were two participants belonging to millennials, people who were born from the 1980s to the 1990s. Tung is even younger than Quynh. When interviewing him, I could sense his vibrant energy and the enthusiasm of youth, although he was not very much talkative. I also felt that being young makes him quite creative, expressed in how he answers my questions. Instead of answering those directly, he told me to let him tell his entrepreneurial journey from the beginning, making him feel more comfortable.

Tung was not interested in the OER sector before, but the job came to him like destiny. Beforehand, after graduating from Law University in Vietnam, he wanted to study Master abroad, so he came to one OER company to ask for information. However, he postponed the plan and decided to work for the company instead. After that, he also worked for other companies in the sector, and he realised that he liked the sector. After accumulating enough experience, he thought he needed to study abroad; he just quit and stayed at home. However, his previous customers kept introducing new ones to him, plus the fact that his wife also worked in the sector, he decided to start up with his wife instead of studying abroad.

Starting up at the age of 25 and at the beginning of Covid 19 (2019), many people thought he was insane, but his entrepreneurship showed otherwise after three years. He also shared with me that “I did not think much before starting up. I just felt that it was the right time to do so”, and he also believed that Covid 19 could reduce the competition gap between other companies.

Tra

Like the case of Nha, Tra and her co-founder started up quite early, around 2005. She was my Marketing teacher and my supervisor at the university back in 2011 in Vietnam, and when I shared my wish to interview her, she was very willing to assist. When I studied with her, I knew that she was a strict teacher but had a good sense of humour. When I contacted her, she was around her 40s already after ten years we had not met, but she looked relatively young, neatly, and energetic.

Tra used to study Master of Marketing at the University of East of Anglia in the UK with distinction. Before starting up in the OER sector, she worked for many event companies in the UK. When returning to Vietnam, she co-founded with her friends to start up the company. However, at that time, she still maintained many other jobs, such as a business consultant for SME companies and a university lecturer.

She had the first office in Hanoi, and then five years later, she had another office in Ho Chi Minh City. Her company recruits students from English-speaking countries, similar to other study CEOs. Besides, she also offered auxiliary services to clients such as scholarship hunting, insurance counselling, money transfer, accommodation, visa support and the flight ticket purchase.

Phuong

I knew Phuong's company before because one of my friends used to work there, but I never talked to her. Hence, to approach her, I had help from a university representative. Through the first impressions via video call, I sensed that she was like a combination of Asian and western styles, expressed in her straightforward answers, her appointment with the punctuality of western culture and the flexibility and subtleness of Asian. During the talk, I answered my own question knowing that she got married to a French man.

She used to study at Foreign Trade University with the ambition of working with foreigners. With her diligence, she managed to get two bachelor's degrees in World's Economic and International Economic Relations and fluency in both English and French. Thanks to her efforts, she got a 100% scholarship at Toulouse 1 University in France. Her course there was about the relationship between employment and education. When she returned to Vietnam, she followed the profession of lecturing university students until 2017, then during the time she taught at university and the experience outside Vietnam. She realised that setting up the OER company would be her subsequent effort to support Vietnamese students to develop academically and professionally.

The unique point of her company is that she always incorporated cultural knowledge, customs and manners, and practical experiences in consulting students with enthusiastic support from her foreign husband. He was willing to return to Vietnam with her. Therefore, she could gain trust from people for her company. So far, her company is going well, and she is planning to open another branch in HCM city besides the main one in Hanoi.

4.3. Theme introduction

My entrepreneurs brought their personality, characteristics, perceptions, background and especially their dreams and motivation on the journey of starting up. However, starting up in the OER sector is even more challenging because of foreign factors. Fortunately, all my entrepreneurs knew how to use the multiplexity of the personal network to help them develop their nascent entrepreneurship to success. Nevertheless, relationships and network multiplexity are dynamic and constantly changing. Therefore, maintaining networks is also as important as other business activities, especially during the unprecedented period (Covid, travel - restrictions, diseases). Based on the sharing and reflections of my participants, five major themes emerge, including motivation and challenges of entrepreneurs, dimensions of PNM, dimensions of entrepreneurial development, the dynamism of personal network multiplexity, and personal network multiplexity strategies in standard and unprecedented periods.

Motivation factors and challenges	Dimensions of personal network multiplexity	Dimensions of entrepreneurial development	Dynamism of personal network multiplexity	Personal Network Multiplexity strategy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •1.1 Passion and motivation •Passion in business and education •Social Responsibility •Personal Gain •Resources Utilisation •1.2 Challenges •Reputation and trust •Forming team •Finance •Entre skills •Network •Emotional health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •2.1 Strong tie relationship •Family •Friends •Weak tie relationship •Partners •Customers •Staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •New networks •Revenue and customers •Reputation •Other developments: Expansion, scale, staff etc., 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •3.1 The changes •Staffs •Customers •3.2 Unchanged relationships •Family •Co-founders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4.1 Standard PNM strategy •Strong-tie •Weak-tie •4.1 PNM strategy in unprecedented period

Figure 14: Major themes and sub-themes

4.4. Theme One: Motivation factors and challenges faced by Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector

Starting up or entrepreneurship is always one of the most critical decisions. It is the ambition of businesspeople who desire to utilise all the resources they have in hand to bring values to themselves, their networks and society. Our participants, CEOs and founders of their companies, revealed their great motivation and intense passion, stimulating them to open their businesses in the OER sector.

Nevertheless, starting up in Vietnam is not an easy task. Statically in Vietnam, only 5% of start-up companies can blow the second-anniversary candle (Phan Anh, 2021). The part also shows the hardship that our participants had to deal with during their TEA (Total Early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity). However, the greater hard to get, the greater enjoyment and success the entrepreneurs can achieve.

4.4.1. Subtheme One: Strong Passion and great motivation for entrepreneurs in the OER sector.

4.3.1.1. Satisfying Passion and Ambition

Harriet Tubman once said, “Every great dream begins with a dreamer”. Our CEO used to have dreams of doing business or starting up when they were tiny. Those dreams are the successful seeds that they planted and watered in their hearts.

The business has always been my passion since I was a young girl. I binge-watched many episodes of Apprenticeship (a TV show about business) when I was at the university in Vietnam. I decided I needed to go abroad to study to satisfy my dream!
Tra

When Tra was small, she did not know that she would work in the OER sector, but she knew she loved business. Unlike her, many of those entrepreneurs were not interested in business early. Still, they developed a passion for education instead and then realised business is the gate that can help them achieve their dreams.

Before I decided to do this (OER sector), many of my friends suggested I do other business, including online sales. However, I used to be a teacher previously. I have always loved education, so the OER sector is more suitable for me. Ha

Like Ha, Thu also shared the same passion for education and business with foreign partners.

The first reason was I love doing business with foreign partners and the second reason is I always have had a passion for education. Phuong

Unlike them, Quynh studied Accounting and Finance and did not have a strong interest in the OER sector or education. Still, she realised her chance when she was in the UK, and her passion for her business turned into actual action, which was starting up.

Before that, when I worked in the accounting and finance sector, I just worked for other companies. However, I later found out that I had more passion for setting up my business myself. Quynh

Unlike anyone mentioned, Tung only realised his business desires and the dream sector he wishes to work for after working for an OER company.

Basically, I started liking the overseas educational sector when I worked in the company recruiting students I mentioned before. I found it quite suitable for me. During the time I worked there, I learned a lot. And I realised the meaning of the business. Tung

In short, these entrepreneurs who decided to start-up in the sector either have a passion for education, business, or both. Even some entrepreneurs only realised their passion when they were grown up and experienced some working environments. In the research literature, most theoretical entrepreneurial frameworks highlight the importance of passion and emphasise that passions are inspirations for entrepreneurial efforts and vice versa (Gielnik et al., 2011).

4.3.1.2.Social Responsibility

When asked about the strong motivations for their start-up decisions, social responsibility is always put forward first. Social responsibility, scientifically called “corporate social responsibility” (CSR), was not a new term. It appeared for the first time since 1953 (Bowen, 2013; Križanová, Moravčíková and Klieštková, 2018). Accordingly, CEOs and business people seek to harmonise their business relationships with stakeholders by identifying and

implementing activities beyond legal and ethical standards (Anna et al., 2017). Let us look at how they identified their CSR when deciding to start up.

I knew the demand of students and parents for studying abroad and the fact that they could not access reliable information sources about studying abroad even though they had gone to many agents. The more agencies they visited, the more confused they got. So, I wanted to support them. Ha

As I mentioned, not many people have set up those kinds of company previously and many overseas educational companies were considered scams but not genuine ones. They kept their deposit of students and parents, then vanished or used tricks to take those deposits. Nha

To be honest, there were many centres recruiting students, but many of them are not genuine, or the directors of those companies are not prestigious enough. Many of them did not only recruit students but also exported labour to other countries. That is why they did not verify students. Tra

Some of the CEO mentioned above were encouraged because they want students to find a good place to be consulted about studying abroad in the context that there are quite a few untrustworthy companies or scams in the market.

Other CEO worries that unprepared students will have to struggle with the difficulty and challenges when studying broad, so they wanted to help students with that.

I really wanted to do that to help international students achieve their dreams, and I set up the company in the UK first so that I could help students study abroad and deal with their problems in the country they plan to study. Quynh

As I mentioned, I used to study abroad in the UK; therefore, I know how difficult Vietnamese students suffer and struggle with the study abroad experience if they are not prepared well enough. So, at that time, I really wanted to set up a business that can help Vietnamese students have a smooth and seamless experience of studying abroad. Cam

Many wrong centres recruited students, but they did not fully support students in preparation for a strange country to study. Tra

Studying abroad is never easy for Vietnamese students, especially with financial matters. That is why many CEOs opened their business with the desire to bring back many good scholarships for Vietnamese students.

Because I got a scholarship and learnt the best education in both Vietnam and Australia environment, what I wanted at that time was to help more Vietnamese students get scholarships. Nha

More importantly, the dream to develop talents for Vietnam to help the country by sending them to study abroad is also the inspiration for their starting up.

The most important thing is I want to connect Vietnamese students to better educational organisations (Uni, schools) so that they can be the future leaders leading our country to overcome poverty and become a rich and powerful country with the knowledge and skills that they can acquire during the time they study and live there. Phuong

As previous study abroad students, we really hope that more and more Vietnamese students can experience themselves and acquire more knowledge, skills, and new mindsets learned from developed countries. When they are back in Vietnam, they can support the development of Vietnam. Tra

Because I was given the best education in both Vietnam and Australia, I want to be the bridge connecting students to a leading University in the world. In the future, Vietnamese will have more talented people to contribute to my country. Nha

All participants have various ways of supporting students and society, and someone even traded off financial benefits for other jobs to choose the sector.

In comparison with the real estate sector that I used to work in, I personally think it is not comparable. I mean real estate sector can help me get more money than the sector, but I think the value to society and humanity of the education sector is better. Quynh

Bussard and colleagues (2004) emphasise CSR into seven characteristics involving “willingness, active collaboration and open dialogue with all stakeholders, corporate engagement, systematicity and long-term time horizon, company operation concerning three main pillars (economic efficiency, environmental responsibility and social engagement) and responsibility towards society and companies’ commitment to contribute to the development of life quality.

And via interviews, It can be implied that most of our CEO identified the social issues, which are scams in the market, financial issues of Vietnamese students, and talents for the country. Therefore, they set up their business to deal with those issues, satisfying the two pillars (economic efficiency and social engagement). However, they have not mentioned the long-term horizon and environmental responsibility. It is still understandable because they are offering services more than products, so the environmental element might not have been mentioned, and at that time, they were just in the first phase of starting up. Hence, it was hard to think about the long-term horizon.

4.3.1.3 Personal gain

Besides social responsibility, our informants also shared personal reasons that contributed to their decisions to start up, including family support, financial gain, knowledge and status in the business and OER sector.

Family support

Interestingly, four out of seven informants were or have been teachers in Vietnam. They told me that because they were teachers, they really know how important education is. First and foremost, they wanted to start up in the OER sector to help their children, sisters, brothers, and students get easy access to study abroad opportunities.

My son was the direct reason for me to be an entrepreneurship in the sector. I wanted to help him study abroad; then, after that, I thought, why did not I start-up to support other students because I am also an English Teacher. Ha

When I set up, I thought about my sister and my children (at that time, I didn't have any children, though). Still, I have always wanted that my sister or my children in the future could have the best education that I, in the position of the mother and the sister, could facilitate. Quynh

Financial gain

OER or education is the choice of sector, but for entrepreneurs to be successful, business is the gate, and finance is the key. Without money and financing, it was difficult to sustain a business and achieve any dreams. The fact that many of our entrepreneurs mentioned finance is the validation of the previous sentence.

Profit is also essential to survive myself, make wealthier, and pay staff. And the reason I chose the sector was because of the low initial cost. I didn't need to have too much capital to start up, and I could easily have profit from the beginning. Tung

I studied MSc. Investment in Brighton University before coming back to Vietnam. So, I did believe in the profit prospect of the sector. However, I always share the profits with staff and even my customers (like giving visa fee or some cash) so that everyone can benefit from my business. Cam

Working with foreign companies or organisations has always been great in finance. Tra

I love business, especially foreign business. Working in the OER sector with foreign partners is more beneficial than Vietnamese partners in terms of finance. Phuong

Working with foreign partners will benefit us more than our domestic counterparts. But more than that, we would like to build a company with good images first. It is also why we took some commission from universities to give back to students to support their visa application or a part of flight expenses. Nha

Most of the participants quite hesitated to talk about money and finance. It can be explained that this problem is quite sensitive, especially in Vietnamese culture. Secondly, they all

considered profits merely a tool for operating the business and achieving their greater dreams. **Quynh** is the strongest evidence that she did not care much about profit when she was willing to change from real estate to education and OER sector regardless of the potential of getting rich fast from the real estate.

Social Status, Power and Freedom

Many of our informants did not mention power or status as a reason for starting up. However, their answers implied that status, power, or freedom are also crucial to their personal gains.

I used to work for an OER company, but I did not agree with some of the company's tactics, so I opened my own business to have more freedom to do whatever I wanted to do and easy to achieve my life goal. Ha

I think another reason for me to set up a business was that there were not so many companies supporting students on two sides, both in the home country and the country of study destination, so I want to be a leading entrepreneur to do so. Quynh

After leaving the Ministry of education and training in Vietnam, Cam wanted to open his own business to seek power and freedom.

I used to work in the sector in a State environment, but I feel that I was much restricted with many things, and I believe I can develop more if I work for myself. Cam

At the age of 25, Tung started up with full of passion, and one of his ambitions was to achieve his self-actualisation and status and be better than his peers.

Well, I have to say it is also related to my ambition. Not many of my peers dared to take the entrepreneurial challenge at my age, and I wanted to do otherwise. I wanted to try no matter how I could fail or succeed, but I believed I would exceed my limitations and surpass my peers. And the pride when being called “boss” and “director” was also stimulating to me. Tung

4.3.1.4 Resources Utilisation

As mentioned before, some entrepreneurs started to love the OER sector when they started working in that. After working for some companies in the sectors, they decided to start up their own to make use of the knowledge and skills they learned.

*Previously, I had 20 years of teaching English in an international school in Vietnam and 2.5 years of working in an overseas education recruitment company in the UK. At that time, I was a regional manager based in Vietnam. My responsibilities mainly were in sales and marketing, including recruiting students, doing marketing campaigns, and connecting domestic and international partners. **Ha***

Before starting up, **Ha** used to be a teacher for 20 years and 2.5 years in the OER sector, so opening her own business is the way for her not to wait for her skills and knowledge in the sector. Similarly, **Phuong**, **Tra** and **Nha** were also teachers at that time of their entrepreneurship; therefore, their students were also one of their base customers.

*I worked as a lecturer until 2016 before starting up in the OER sector. I had a belief that both jobs are about education, and they can all support and help Vietnamese students achieve their dreams. **Phuong***

*I also wanted to start up in the sector because I had previously worked for some prestigious universities as a Marketing and Business lecturer. So, working in the sector can benefit our company as well as benefit my students! **Tra***

Tung was not a teacher, but he also took advantage of his experiences from three previous companies in the OER sector to start up his own.

*Before starting up, I worked as a leader of a sub-department in charge of the US market; then, when I left the company after four years for another student overseas recruitment company, I also worked in the same position, but at that time, I oversaw Canada market. Therefore, I had accumulated enough knowledge from 2 previous companies with 6-year experience when I started up. **Tung***

In summary, whoever started up has strong motivations to push them forward in the OER sector. Those drives can come from their inner passion or dream, their missions and visions to

help society, their wish to develop themselves financially, power desire, and be able to help their family and beloved people. Their ambition to start up is quite viable because some of them knew how to use knowledge and transferable skills from their previous jobs. However, the entrepreneurial journey was always full of challenges and obstacles, especially during the TEA period.

4.4.2. Subtheme Two: Difficulties and Challenges of starting up in the OER sector.

As mentioned before, the failure rate of entrepreneurship in Vietnam is very high because of the significant challenges at the first stage of starting up. The first difficulty is reputation and brand recognition.

4.3.2.1 Reputation and Trust

In the sector of OER, reputation is extremely vital. The decision to study abroad is never easy for students, and it can cost them and their families a treasure. Therefore, those students usually consider OER agents before sealing the deal with an agent.

My brand recognition was nearly zero. I started up in Hanoi, and do you know that there were around 1000 agents OER companies and so many unofficial companies. Ha

Like many new companies, my company's reputation is nothing at that moment. Meanwhile, in Hanoi, few foreign and domestic companies are successful and known for recruiting students for international schools and overseas universities. Cam

The first challenge I had to face was to build a brand for my company. Tung

The next thing I want to mention is reputation. Our company's marketing recognition was too low in the market when newly starting up, which also led to the shortage of customers at the beginning days of starting up. Phuong

Starting up a little bit earlier without much competition, **Nha** and **Tra** also met difficulties in trust gain because of the scam companies in the sector.

In the 2000s, there were too few genuine companies in the sector, while many scam companies were deceiving many Vietnamese people. Therefore, the reputation of the companies in the sector was very low. Nha

There were many centres recruiting students, but many of them were not genuine, or the directors of those companies were not prestigious enough. Many of them did not only recruit students but also exported labour to other countries. That is why they did not verify students. That is why brand recognition and the bad image of OER companies at that time were also a problem for us. Tra

The worry of building reputation and trust from customers was the first challenge our informants faced when many students and parents had been deceived before or had bad experiences with those kinds of companies in the sector. That is why new companies had to build their brand and do the best to stop prejudice against companies in the OER sector.

4.3.2.2 Challenges in team building

Starting up in any sector requires assembling a great team. Some of our CEO found that finding co-founders to work with was not an easy thing to do.

I struggled a bit in terms of looking for some partners to work with when I decided to open their own business. At that time, I had just graduated, so I wanted to find some people who had more business experience than me to operate with. Besides, I have a good understanding of the UK education system and studying abroad in the UK rather than studying abroad knowledge of other countries, so I had some pressure to find a good team who could support me in other markets. Tra

I had many friends and acquaintances to co-operate with, but I had to evaluate them based on their strengths and the suitability of their characteristics with my team. So, the process was time-consuming and exhausting. Nha

I had difficulty with my co-founders because they all have their own business, so I could not expect their daily support for my new company. Nevertheless, they were all my friends before, so it was comfortable for me to discuss my business activities and propose solutions for my company. Ha

Ha managed to find co-founders, but they hardly had any experiences in the sector, so they could only help her in other matters, so Ha still had to do most things on her own. Meanwhile, **Quynh** is another case. She has two branches; one is in Vietnam and the other one in the UK. She met some challenges in finding a reliable staff to oversee her office in Vietnam, but luckily, she found a way.

When I decided to open an office in Vietnam, the human resource was my biggest issue. I had to contemplate much on who could help me with that, and luckily, one of my cousins with his wife, an English teacher in Vietnam, agreed to co-operate with me.
Quynh

Besides the issue of finding partners, lacking staff at the TEA stage is also a big challenge.

After we rented a small office, my wife and I had to set up everything for the office. We also had to design our logo and website. We had to stay up till 4 am many days to finish those entrepreneurial tasks because of having no staff. Gradually, we recruited more staff to share the heavy workload so that we could deal with more new tasks.
Tung

Another problem was the staff. We didn't have much staff; therefore, I was the only one who did sales, and my vice-director was the only one in charge of marketing. We also hired two more people for admin and marketing. But basically, it was not enough at the time.
Cam

It can be said that building a solid team for an entrepreneur needs patience, time, and effort. It was not only about co-founders but also about beginning staff, who might follow those entrepreneurs for a long time and know all the company's secrets. Therefore, it was understandable that entrepreneurs had to think carefully about this matter.

4.3.2.3 Finance

Surprisingly, not many entrepreneurs asked had to face a severe lack of capital or financing issues. They all said that the OER doesn't require a lot of capital or supplies to start with. Nevertheless, the cost of starting up a business was still a problem that every entrepreneur had to cope with.

My biggest problem with financing is renting a good place for my company because the sector is all about trust and reputation, so I wanted to rent a massive place in the central districts. Luckily, the sector doesn't require too much capital to start up, so I could focus more on renting a venue for my office. Ha

Phuong mentioned many kinds of initial fees she had to cope with because she did not have partners or co-founders to work with from the beginning. Like **Ha**, she also had to find a well-located office to gain reliability and trust from customers. Besides, she also mentioned she did not have to pay much for digital marketing because at the time she started up, it was not popular.

I did not have any co-founders to start with, so it was tough to set up everything because everything needed money to operate. At that time, fees for digital marketing were not that much like nowadays, but the money to rent an office in Hanoi – my first branch was absurd. Because, as I said, there had been some negative rumours about OER companies like us before, we had to invest tremendously in the location and office to gain customer trust. And of course, the other initial fees for starting up were also a big problem for me.

Tra and **Nha** answered quite shortly, but they also mentioned this.

So many issues we had to deal with, such as capital. Tra

I didn't have enough financial requirements to set up the business by myself at that time. Nha

Cam even had to pay a large amount of deposit to the Ministry of education and training, which led to his difficulty in initial capital. Meanwhile, Tung did not have money at first to recruit staff for his company until six months later.

*I had to deposit a tremendous amount of money to the Ministry of education and training because there had been some scam companies before. So, the money will be the guarantee. The sum, combined with my capital for other stuff, was hard for me.
Cam*

I had to design the logo, company images or company name and do them all by myself. I didn't ask for help because the cost would have been too much if I had hired someone to help. As a result, I set up everything in my bedroom until six months later. Tung

Much or less, finance is always a challenge, and it also affects other activities such as staff and the expansion of entrepreneurs. And, of course, it was not the only difficulty; the list still went on.

4.3.2.4 Lack of entrepreneurial and managerial skills

Besides financial, reputation and team forming, managerial and entrepreneurial skills are also vital to new enterprises. However, it was never easy, especially with all the participants that attended my interviews. Their experiences in starting up in the OER sector were all the first.

I met so many difficulties at first. As I mentioned, it was not about expertise but entrepreneurial and managerial skills. Cam

Tung was the youngest entrepreneur when he started up at 24. He did not prepare much for management or entrepreneurial skills. His entrepreneurship was just like the spontaneity of his youth.

Another problem is entrepreneurial skills. I was young at the time of starting up, and I found that no one at my age dared to start up. I, myself, did not even have any plan before starting up. So, I mainly did with my hunch and intuition more than clear strategies for entrepreneurship. Tung

Quynh lives permanently in the UK. So, when she started up her business in Vietnam, she had to go back and forth between Vietnam and UK, which made her struggle with managing her office when she was away. The problem here is about overall performance and sales of staffs.

I was not there [Vietnam] directly, so the main problem is the human resources management. When I was in the UK, the UK staff did better, but the Vietnamese staff did better based on the overall performance and sales when I went back to Vietnam. Quynh

Tra is another story. She also studied in the UK, but she came back to Vietnam to start up in the OER sector. She met challenges in re-adapting to her own country's business and entrepreneurial environment. She also mentioned her youth and inexperience of graduates when coping with entrepreneurship.

Moreover, I studied in the UK and just worked for some small companies in the UK, but not in management. When I came back to Vietnam, some of my working experience was unsuitable for the Vietnamese working environment. And business and management skills applied to Vietnamese entrepreneurship were even more challenging for a young graduate like me at that time. Tra

Even being more complicated, the start-up company of Nha was one of the first ones in the sector back in the 2000s. Under the pressure of the first movers, she did not have many successful cases to follow.

We were new, and there were not many companies like us to learn from their models, so we had to go on our own feet, and when we were wrong, we did it again. Nha

She admitted to making some mistakes, which she did not state clearly. But she said, “going on her own feet” or “learning from the model” can be implied that she had trouble with the **operation, management, or entrepreneurial skills** at the beginning of starting up.

Unlike Ha stopping teaching to open her business, Nha, Tra, and Phuong maintained teaching while starting up their companies. And Phuong shared about how the other job affected her entrepreneurship. She did not mention clearly that the teaching job adversely impacted her entrepreneurial skills; however, it did make her confused and struggle with a different perspective when maintaining two roles.

Another thing is I did not have a co-founder at the beginning period of starting up, and I had to make all entrepreneurial decisions on my own. My perspective was more like a teacher than an entrepreneur because I did not stop teaching while starting up. As a result, I struggled tremendously with two roles and two mindsets. Phuong

Similarly, Tra also expressed quite the same concern at that time.

I was a teacher and entrepreneur at that time, and I realised that some teaching skills could not be transferred to entrepreneurship. Those different perspectives somehow affected my ability to make good decisions for my business. Tra

In short, being young or old, starting up the first time always requires tremendous efforts in which managerial and entrepreneurial skills are vital for later development. The sayings of participants suggest that they all had little experience in these skills, which heavily affected their performance in the first days. However, in the latter parts, they revealed more about who helped them overcome the obstacle of lacking management.

4.3.2.5 Lack of Networks

Every company, regardless of big or small, new or old, networks are inevitable. Nonetheless, the role of the network is even more vital in entrepreneurship. These new enterprises need networks like bloodstreams in the human body. Our participants also expressed their arduousness in terms of finding good networks for their business during the TEA period.

Network of suppliers

If products and suppliers are the input of a typical company, then those companies offering overseas education services count on the number of educational institutions as their suppliers. In the beginning days of starting up, one of many challenges of those companies was not able to sign contracts with those institutions.

I only had four universities to work with at that time, so I could not provide students with many options. So many of my students left my company for others. Cam

Nha studied in Australia and then came back to Vietnam. Hence, she only got some suppliers, which were universities in Australia, which made her feel difficult to offer other country options to her students at the beginning of starting up.

After I left Australia, I started up. Most of my suppliers (universities and colleagues) were from Australia. So, when the customer came to my company to ask about studying abroad in other countries, I had to send them to other companies. Nha

The lack of supplier's issue is also true with Phuong and Tra. Phuong returned from France after her Master course, so most of her first partners offering courses were merely French universities.

I did not have many networks in the sector to start with, and I was worried when there were only 2 French universities agreed to work with me at that time. Those partners were like suppliers for my company, and without many suppliers, it was hard for me to recruit students. Phuong

Meanwhile, **Tra's** university suppliers mostly were from the UK because she graduated there, which made her suffer from a lack of other partners from other countries.

When we had contracts with some universities in the UK, but we did not have all, so many of our students wished to study in different schools/ uni that we did not sign the contract left us for other agents. In some cases, students would like to study in other countries; we were also struggling to find other agents to co-operate so that we still can convert students. It can say that lack of partners in the first period of starting up was our problem. Tra

Besides lack of supplier network, those founders also faced the issue of lack of customers, which was essential to the operation of those entrepreneurs

Network of customers

The lack of customers derives from the low reputation of new start-up companies and the lack of services and options for students, and harsh competition in the market. Both **Ha** and **Phuong** shared the same thoughts on reputation affecting the network of customers.

My brand recognition was nearly zero. I started up in Hanoi, and do you know that there are around 1000 agents OER companies and so many unofficial companies. My clients at first were all my old students and from the networking of other staff. Ha

The third thing I want to mention is the reputation, the marketing recognition of our company was too low in the market, which also led to the shortage of customers at the beginning days of starting up. Phuong

One of many reasons explaining for lack of customers is also from the staff shortage of the company.

I was the only one who did sales, and my vice-director was the only one in charge of marketing. So, it was hard to get many students. Cam

Quynh had started up her OER business in the UK beforehand, and most of the time, she was in the UK. Therefore, she could not consult students directly or face to face in her new office in Vietnam, which led to the low number of students converted.

I struggled to recruit students in Vietnam or develop a network of customers because I could not counsel my customers directly. At the beginning of my startup, my staff did not have enough experience and skills to convert students. Quynh

Nha started up very early; at that time, studying abroad was not blooming like in recent years, which made her suffer from approaching prospective students.

In the 2000s, not so many families could afford to give their children opportunities to study abroad due to the high expenses, so we didn't have much customer base. Nha

Tung is another particular case. He had just set up his business for a year when covid-19 broke out. Therefore, his potential students were significantly reduced.

My company was new, and because of covid-19, the number of students studying abroad in my company reduced by 60% compared to the first year of starting up. Tung

Starting up a business is like assembling a machine with many details. The customer base is critical. However, to operate the new entrepreneurial companies well, other supporting partners or a network of expertise is compulsory.

Network of expertise

Doing business in Vietnam requires an understanding of the business law or legal issues affecting business, especially in the sector of OER involving sending students abroad. Therefore, some participants shared the hardship of having no business law experts to help.

When I set up my business, I did not expect to pay half a billion Vietnam dong to deposit for the Ministry of Education and Training (MOET), as well as many procedures to ensure safety for students from MOET. And I don't know anyone from MOET; therefore, it was hard to follow their stipulations. Tung

Also, tax payment was mentioned as a challenge for new companies regarding business law. **Cam** explained the vital role of having a good network with the staff in the Tax Department because he was struggling.

I had to pay tax quarterly. But in Vietnam, the procedure is complicated and time-consuming. State Departments were bureaucracy at that time, and because I did not know anyone in the tax department, I made many mistakes and had to pay fines. Cam

Apart from business law issues, IT and digital marketing are also vital for the newly OER company in promoting themselves and recruiting students. And most of our informants admitted having suffered tremendously with technology in the first days of starting up.

We started up when social networks and digital marketing were not as common as nowadays. Therefore, we only needed to focus on our website. Although it was not hard to find someone good at the website, we did not have enough finance to hire someone permanently for that position. Therefore, when the website did not work well, we struggled. Nha

Cam shared an interesting story about how he set an enormous amount of money wrongly for Facebook ads due to his stress; therefore, he needed an expert in this to help.

When I first knew about Facebook ads, I once made a mistake when adjusting the money put for a campaign on Facebook. The money was a billion Vietnamese dong- a thousand times compared to a regular campaign. I was too stressful with many tasks at that time, and I realised that I needed more experience experts to help with that. Cam

Studying abroad requires students to take English tests. Many participants admitted that they could not offer the teaching English service to students at the beginning of the start-up.

We could not provide students with English teaching because of staff shortage; therefore, we missed out on the opportunity to get more profit for the company. But only OER service was overwhelming already. Tung

Quynh Nha Ha and Phuong, and Tra could teach English themselves because they used to be English teachers or graduates from English speaking countries. However, they were too busy with the managerial positions, and they even had other jobs teaching students in the universities.

I maintained my job as a teacher at some universities, so I could not teach English. Our company was also newly founded, so I wanted to focus on the OER sector, although I know English is a requisite for students. Tra

I know giving English courses is the way to support students studying abroad, add more value to our company, and bring more profit. But at that time, we did not have enough resources to offer the services. Phuong

The fact that those newly found enterprises struggle to offer extra English teaching services to students because of overwhelming tasks suggested that they lack supporting units or other agencies to help with that.

4.3.2.6 Mental and physical health issues

Like other entrepreneurs, informants mentioned the feeling of being overwhelmed, stressed, disappointed and even depressed sometimes. The pressure of starting up is inevitable.

In the beginning months of starting up, we only had three to five customers signing contracts while so many costs were incurring. I prepared for that already, but that also made me extremely worried and stressed. Cam

If Cam were tired of customer shortage, Quynh even had to suffer both emotional distress and physical health issue when she had to go back and forth between Vietnam and UK to take care of both branches.

The difference in time zone added to my worries about the new Vietnam office made me exhausted. The long flights and pressure of the new branch in Vietnam also made me sick, and I had to take medicine for these periods. Quynh

Tra and **Phuong** maintained two jobs which were both teaching at University and CEO, and they even got more depressed and exhausted because of long days at work.

I had to wake up at 5 a.m some days because some classes in Vietnam started at 7.00 or 7.30. After that, I went back to my office from 8 to 9 p.m. I only had two hours per day myself to prepare for the next day. After the first three months, I got seriously sick and had to change. Tra

I struggled tremendously with two roles and two mindsets. I did not have time to take care of myself and my family. Sometimes, I looked in the mirror, and I could not recognise myself. Luckily, I did not have a baby, but it was still too much. Phuong

Lack of staff and financial shortage led to a heavy workload for Tung and his wife. As a result, they could not sleep soon and adequately; Tung got insomnia after starting up.

We had to stay up till 4 a.m on many days to finish those tasks [entrepreneurial tasks]. The workload was too much, and only our husband and wife dealt with them. After that, I think I got insomnia till now. Tung

Besides pressures, stress, physical health, the guilty feelings, and less time for the family were also troubles for these entrepreneurs. **Nha** divorced her husband while she was starting up, which made her get a breakdown.

I remember I got a shock after year 2 of starting up; when I got divorced from my husband, I was not myself for half a year. I should have focused better on the critical stages, but many things came simultaneously, and I totally collapsed.

Quynh had to fly back and forth between Vietnam and the UK. The time spent with her husband was too little, and she felt sorry for him.

Besides, I did not have proper time for my husband in 3 first months. He sympathised, but I still felt guilty while the role of Vietnamese women usually is staying at home and taking care of family. Quynh

Ha divorced her husband before she started up, but her daughter was just ten years old, and she regretted that she could not spend more time with her.

I only had a regret, which was about my daughter. I do love my daughter dearly. But I was sad that I could not take care of her better when I started up. Some days, when I got home, she slept soundly already. I only could hug her a bit and cry silently. Ha

Last but not least, the pressure of success and the high expectation of those CEO for their business also made them struggle.

I didn't want to fail; therefore, I contemplated and overthought when I met difficulties such as customer and supplier refusals. Cam

Tung started up early at the age of 24, he was not scared of failure, but the fact that he wanted to prove to his peers and people looking down on youngsters like him was conducive to his tiredness and stress.

I was young, so I thought failure was inevitable, alright. However, I still want my peers to admire me, and my older people in my extended family believe that I can do great things at my age. To be honest, I was pretty under heavy pressure with those thoughts created by myself. Tung

In a nutshell, entrepreneurship requires plenty of trade-offs. They are the expectations, the struggles, work-life balance, entrepreneurial hardship involving reputation, finance, human resources, the networks of customers, suppliers, functional teams, experts, and entrepreneurial and management skills. This led to emotional instability, physical health and even depression

for our CEOs. These CEOs will reveal more about who accompanied them to overcome those challenging times in the next chapter.

4.5. Theme Two: Dimensions of personal network multiplexity

As the literature review has shown, every company, especially entrepreneurs, needs networks to develop. It is also argued as one of the powerful assets that businesspeople can process to access information, opportunities, power, and other networks (Elfring and Hulsink, 2004). Compared to the difficulties and challenges our informants had to overcome, networks can nearly deal with most of them. When asked about the role of networks in entrepreneurship success, our informants all agreed that networks made up more than 65% of their success at the TEA (Total Early-Stage Entrepreneurial Activity) of their entrepreneurship (Figure 15).

Figure 15: The percentage of networks contributing to the success of entrepreneurship during the TEA period

It can be seen from the figure some informants confirmed that networks take around 90-95% success of their company. Then when I asked more clearly, I was told that their networks had more than one role in supporting their entrepreneurial process, which was scientifically called “network multiplexity”, which is also my research target in the thesis. I also believe that “network multiplexity” is even more salient than merely one type of relationship in regular networks. The PNM was also considered popular in Eastern society, where many

entrepreneurial relationships were mentioned in the networking in Vietnam and the guanxi concept.

4.5.1. Subtheme One: Strong-tie relationships in personal network multiplexity

Strong-tie relationships are defined as relationships with “close-knit members with frequent interactions, such as family and close friends” (Hu et al., 2019). (Elfring and Hulsink, 2004) suggested the benefit of strong-tie relationships for nascent entrepreneurs to quickly acquire valuable knowledge and critical resources (information, capital, customers). They also highlight the important point that strong-tie relationships can be relied on when entrepreneurs are in good times or bad times. Based on the definitions and explanations of prior researchers, as well as the answers of my participants, I classify these strong ties in the study into two groups: family (father-mother, husband-wife, son-daughter, cousins) and friends (classmates, ex-colleagues, teachers, and students).

4.5.1.1 Family

The first strong ties relation mentioned by my participant is family. Family is considered as the influencing factor providing background experience and inspiration for entrepreneurs (Mustapha et al., 2015).

Motivation

Indeed, Ha’s son and wife of Tung, Quynh’s husband, and Cam’s dad motivated them to start up.

The main direct reason for starting up was that I wanted to help my son study abroad.

Ha

The first thing she did for me was encourage me to start up. She is the biggest motivation for that most significant decision in my life. She knew that I didn’t have many things at hand at that moment. At that time, she also agreed to marry me. It motivated and drove me crazily to achieve my success with the start-up. Tung

My husband, as I said, he doesn’t like doing business; however, he is always the inspiration for my career life. He is a romantic person even though he spends most of his time on science and teaching. Quynh

Another thing contributing to my decision to start up was my dad. He was the deputy minister in a department in the government; therefore, he always asked me to do successful things so that he could be proud of me. And, of course, starting up a business is a pride for both my dad and me. Cam

While Ha was motivated by the motive of helping her son to go abroad, then Tung and Quynh's decision to start up was influenced by their love for their wife and husband. Cam is another case; he wanted to prove his worth to his dad, and meeting the expectation of his dad was also his drive to start up. And the case of Phuong was the special one. Her husband decided to follow her to Vietnam, learned Vietnamese and supported her with the business, motivating her enormously.

My husband decided to follow me back to Vietnam to study Vietnamese and blend into the society, giving me plenty of motivation. Phuong

Co-founding

Besides motivating, many family members of those participants agreed to be their co-founders to share entrepreneurial burdens at the beginning stages of starting up.

My wife is also my only co-founder. She worked as much as I did and I can say that the company, the business is like the first child that we have! Tung

The wife of **Cam** also co-founded with him; however, she did not join in the operation of his company. Nevertheless, she also helped him tremendously during the difficult time of starting up.

When **Quynh** started up his office in Vietnam, her cousin became her co-founder of the business in Vietnam. He not only invested in her company and also directed the company for her. She also stated that she could not believe anyone else except for him for that position.

My cousin, Mr D, once saved my life when I was about to drown when I was young, so I trusted him to help me direct the business in Vietnam. I did not have to worry about trust and assurance issues while away from Vietnam when delegating the job. Quynh

Dean (2016) posited that cofounders are ones involving the initial launch of a start-up. He also argues that the concept of co-founder would usually be decided by the founder or leader.

Commonly, the ones who must take the risk of business failures in order to take credit for the success will be called “co-founders”. I respect the decision of informants to call who was their co-founders.

Operational support

All family co-founders participated actively in the initial launch of my entrepreneurs’ start-up. Tung’s wife was considered the best companion because she also had the same passion and career orientation as her husband

We divided tasks clearly between her and me. She counselled students wishing to study in the UK while I was in charge of cases who would like to study in the US and Canada.

Tung

Tung was lucky because he met his wife in the previous company. Both love the sector and have the same ambition of starting up, so they were able to be their co-founders and the company's staff.

As mentioned before, the wife of **Cam** did not involve in the operation of his starting up. However, because she worked in the bank when Cam started up, she helped him quite a bit with financing and procedures with the bank.

She also worked in a bank at that moment, so she also helped me finance my business quite well, thanks to her expertise and her network in the financial sector. Cam

Quynh’s cousin assisted her tremendously when starting up in the Vietnamese market. He is not only a director, but he also does management tasks, even admin tasks for her business and the representative of her in Vietnam.

Besides being my co-founders, Mr D. was also my admin staff and the company's rep. He welcomed customers to the office and led the visa team to make sure that all the students’ applications sent to educational institutions as well as the home office would be well prepared. He was also there to answer all the questions from customers in Vietnam. Quynh

Some family members who were not co-founders of those entrepreneurs still contributed considerably to the operation of those start-up companies.

Suppose IT was an issue within most companies in Vietnam, where technology just kicked in in recent years. That IT stuff was not only technical issues but also digital marketing, which directly helped sales boost of those companies. **Cam** and **Tra** were fortunate to have the support from their cousin and brother, respectively.

I also have a cousin who graduated from a technology university taught in English. Therefore, he agreed to help me with technology and IT in my company as well as translation. Those are small tasks but take up plenty of time. Later on, he was also given another role as a digital marketer, assisting me in getting an online database of customers. Cam

I have a younger brother who took care of IT issues in my company. He did not only have expertise in IT, helping with technical problems, but he was also in charge of Digital Marketing, helping me with Facebook/ Instagram marketing. In short, he never hesitated to assist me with anything, and I think again, I was lucky to have a brother like that. Tra

Cam's case is mentioned again because he is the one who got plenty of support from his family in the initial launch of his business. Besides his cousin supporting him in IT and digital marketing, he had his sister and brother-in-law assist him with other roles.

When I started up, I did not have much staff, so I counted on my sister and brother-in-law and my cousin. While my sister oversees accounting, my brother-in-law was a chef and my company's security. Cam

Similarly, besides the help from Mr D- the cousin of Quynh, she also received help from his wife. His wife was in charge of the English centre inside the company, which helped Quynh students get IELTS certificates for studying abroad.

My cousin's wife was the headteacher of the English centre that I created in Vietnam to help students prepare for English/ IELTS to enter foreign universities. Quynh

Although not participating directly in the operation of the start-up, but son and daughter of **Ha** and **Nha** worked as consultant staff of those entrepreneurs in contributing to recruiting students and being testimonials for their moms' companies.

My son has always been a successful testimonial student studying in the UK, which helped me easier in recruiting students. Besides, he also helped me consult students. He did not only provide hands-on experience to my customers, but he also assisted me in picking up my students at the airport. Ha

When my daughter studied in Australia, I was more confident in introducing students to Australia. With the case needing a real success story of studying abroad, I usually let them talk to my child. She is very enthusiastic when talking to my students, which helped me quite a few for converting students. Besides, when I need support from Australia or urgent things happening there, I always have a "faithful staff" to count on. Nha

Strategic advice, status and knowledge

Quynh's husband stayed with her in the UK, a lecturer at Cambridge University. Although he is not a business expert, he was still able to give her some knowledge of HEI (Higher education institutions) in the UK, especially Cambridge University. He also helped her excellent apply to Cambridge easier.

He is a professor at Cambridge Uni, so he also assisted me a lot with my students who would like to apply to high-ranking universities like Cambridge or other universities. My students trusted my company more when I introduced him as the company's advisor. So, I made good use of his title and position to help my company. Quynh

With her husband's status being a professor at high ranking University, it was also easier for her to get the trust of her customers. In the case of **Phuong**'s husband, he did not involve in her business operation, but he had experience in teaching and understanding the French educational system and institutions.

He did not involve directly in the company's operation because he had his own jobs at that moment. But whenever I met difficulties or got stuck, he did not hesitate to help, give advice, and be my coach. Phuong

Phuong's husband is also a foreigner, and Vietnamese students love foreigners, so she usually used his status or image to attract her customers to watch promotional videos.

My husband is French, so occasionally, I asked him to be on my advertising clips to be more attractive to my customers. Phuong

Capital support

Regarding financial matters, the family of entrepreneurs are always the first ones they can count on for the first days of starting up.

I did not face many financial matters because I had accumulated for many years. My wife was the one to help me with half of the capital, and the sector doesn't require much for it. Cam

Cam was lucky that his wife invested 50% in his company while working full time at the other job, proving that she truly believed in him. Similarly, Tung's wife did not only work with him but also contributed half of the initial capital to his company.

She also supported me by giving her saving money for the company's capital during the first time starting up, making up 50% of my capital. Tung

If **Cam** and **Tung** received capital support from their wives, Phuong also got financial support from her husband.

He also encouraged and invested in my company, so I can say that he is not my angel investor but also my inspirer and my coach. Phuong

Quynh is another case; Mr D., her cousin, shared her capital for opening the Vietnamese office. Besides, she also received support from her parents.

When I decided to start up in Vietnam, he agreed to help and contribute some capital to my company besides assisting me in directing the company while I was away. Quynh

My parents gave me unconditional love and even money when I started up my business in both the UK and Vietnam. Quynh

New networks and contact support

As mentioned, the network is significant, and at TEA of entrepreneurship, family is also one of the strongest networks to introduce good and reliable new networks.

As mentioned, the son and daughter of Ha and Nha studied abroad at that time, and they actively help their moms recruit students by consulting students and being testimonials for the company of their moms. Besides, they also introduced their classmates as well as the Vietnamese community to the services of their mom's companies.

When my son studied in the UK, he introduced some of his friends to my company to support their parents' visitor visa applications or studying abroad scholarships for their sisters or brothers. Ha

After I started up for a year, my daughter also studied in Australia. And she connected me with the Vietnamese community in Australia, who wanted to help their relatives to study in the AUS. Thanks to those contacts, I could get more clients for my business. Nha

One of the challenges of start-up companies is a lack of suppliers, which is the limited number of universities and courses in the case of OER companies. However, Phuong's husband – who used to be a French and English teacher in France with many contacts in the education sector – helped her overcome the obstacle.

He was both a French teacher and an English teacher, so his networks were mainly education-related. He assisted me quite a few in contacting universities and schools in France, so I quickly got the contracts with them to recruit students. Phuong

Cam's wife introduced her friends and relatives to work for his company regarding staff shortage.

On the first day of starting up, the one who operated my company most of the time with me was my wife's friend. My wife introduced her to me, and I assigned her as the company's marketing manager, then vice-president. Besides introducing that important person to me, my wife also introduced her cousin to work as a receptionist and human resources assistant for me. A year later, she also introduced her former colleague to be admin manager in my company. I could say that I benefit from the broad relationship of my wife. Cam

And because of working directly with **Tung** as a co-founder and directing the company simultaneously with him, all relationship of Tung's wife that she can take advantage of for the business also belongs to Tung's company. It is also true in the case of **Quynh**. Mr D, the cousin-the co-founder and the company's director, also gave all his necessary contacts for her company.

Emotional Support

In some literature reviews, it is hardly seen that networks also support emotionally, but when asked, many entrepreneurs mention the kind of support. And emotional support from family is the most effective way to reduce stress, tension, and overwhelming feelings of those entrepreneurs.

The husband and wife are always considered the most important of the family relationships. Researchers on family relationships in entrepreneurship also posited that spousal support is superior to other social supports (Dehle et al., 2001; Anna et al., 2013). Indeed, Cam's wife not only supported him in the business, but she was also his home, waiting for him during tiring days of starting up.

She also supported me emotionally by taking care of the family very well, like bringing up my children when I was busy and treating my mother as her own mother. You also know that your mother and wife relationship was very complicated and difficult to live together in Vietnamese culture. But she did well, and I did not need to be concerned about that, reducing a lot of stress for me. Cam

The husband of **Phuong**, as mentioned, is French. He did not join in the operation of the company. Still, he has always been standing by her, coaching her, making her worry less about starting-up hardship.

The fact that my husband left his own country and accepted to be with me during the most challenging days of starting up was enough for me. Sometimes, just by seeing him trying hard to study Vietnamese, I felt more motivated and ready to take on more entrepreneurial challenges. Besides, he was my coach at that time, so he always knew whenever I was down or depressed and offered instant help. Phuong

Because of the entrepreneurial nature, Quynh had to go back and forth between Vietnam and the UK many times. Still, she was also lucky to have a sympathetic husband with compassion for her job, and he was also always concerned about her health.

He studied and taught robotics and sciences, so it was hard to ask for romantic things from him. He hardly said some sweet words, but he expressed with actions like caring for my health when I had to go back and forth between Vietnam and the UK. He was also in charge of cooking at home and ensuring that my meals were full of nutrition. Quynh

Spouses of **Quynh, Phuong and Cam** always support them emotionally with all their hearts, although they are not participating directly in their start-up process. In the case of Tung, his wife was the co-founder and shared half of the burden with him, which made him the luckiest among all the mentioned entrepreneurs.

I think two heads are always better than one. With the help of my wife, I had double determination and double motivation with double efforts. And the wonderful thing is when I had a bad day, she always knew what the problem was without needing to ask, and we together overcame those hardships. Tung

When asked about the difficulty of working together as a married couple, he admitted that he was not concerned because of the harmony between the couple.

And unlike other couples, we are so harmonious in working with each other because we know the nature of the sector. We have been so patient and caring and willing to listen to each other, too, and then everything went so smoothly. Tung

Not fortunate like those happy couples, Ha and Nha had to struggle with the feeling of divorce and the hardship of starting up simultaneously. Nevertheless, the love for their children lifted their spirits.

I was a single mom at the time of starting up. Therefore, my two children are the only best thing I can have. As I said, my son was my motivation for me to start up, to look for good studying abroad opportunities for him. When I started up, he was also sent abroad to study. Whenever I felt down, I usually called him to talk and received words of comfort from him. My daughter was small at that time, but she was smart and understood what I had to go through and how busy I was with my startup. Hence, she always tried her best to study and did not let me worry about anything. Ha

Like Ha, Nha also divorced her husband a few years after she started up, so her only daughter is the most beloved family member that she has.

And regarding my divorce and my startup, she knew that I had to deal with so many burdens and stress simultaneously, so she called me every day, talked to me, and shared with me about her study life in Australia so that I could rest assured. Chatting with her made me happier and feel inspired again. Nha

The two above entrepreneurs have a common thing: they were single moms, so their children's role was essential to their life, motivation, and the source of comfort.

Tra was never in a marriage or with any child, so her brother was the only one she could trust and count on, which helped her reduce plenty of stress.

As I mentioned, he supported IT and digital marketing in my company. Nonetheless, he never hesitated to assist me with other things in my company. Sometimes it was hard to delegate many jobs to my co-founders, who are not my family, but I feel so much easier with him and having him helps me much less stress. Tra

4.5.1.2 Friends

Based on the sharing from participants, I classify entrepreneurs' classmates, ex-colleagues, teachers, and students into the friend group. The group of people does not belong to strong-tie relationships as family members. Still, they are also the ones that my entrepreneur can count on. Their network with those entrepreneurs can be considered multiplexity because of the multiple roles they can take in supporting entrepreneurship.

Co-founding support

In the last part, the role of spousal support in co-founding the entrepreneurial business is said to be paramount. However, if entrepreneurs can not manage well, their company and marriage might be easily destroyed (Bruder, 2014). On the other hand, friends are close enough to trust and not too intimate to distract the decisions of entrepreneurs. Hence, three out of seven of my informants said they chose friends to start up with.

SG education was founded in May 2018. It was very challenging since it is related directly to students' futures and involves international factors, so it was impossible for me to start up alone. Therefore, I had to co-op with three other co-founders, my classmates at universities, who are also my friends. They all have a different background, set of knowledge and skills so we could complement each other. Ha

Ha was lucky because she could unite the strengths of four friend co-founders. Similarly, Nha and Tra also had two co-founders to work with at the beginning days of start-up to share their risks.

When I started up, I didn't want to take too many risks myself, so I combined my strengths and will with other friends having the same passion for the OER sector to start up. Those friends were also the ones who studied with me in Australia. Nha

Of course, no one can work alone to start up, especially when I was young when I planned to start up. Therefore, I co-operated with my friends who also studied in the UK and the other one who had experience in starting up for many years in Russia. Three of us united our strengths and passion for making this possible. I can say that a good team is also the reason for my inspiration to start up. Tra

Two of the three female entrepreneurs mentioned were either single moms or single. Therefore, they tend to co-found with their friends to share the entrepreneurial risks, overcome challenges and unite the powers of many heads.

Capital support

Unlike family, who can easily give monetary support to entrepreneurs, capital support from friends usually comes from co-founders of those entrepreneurs.

The second thing is the capital support. I couldn't start up with only my savings accounts as a graduate. Therefore, my co-founders, who are also my friends, did not hesitate to contribute financially to my company, which equals half of the capital. Tra

When I returned to Vietnam to start up in the OER sector, I didn't have enough money to set up the business; I had to maintain the teaching job. Luckily, as I said, my co-founders were my classmates in Australia. And I could ask for help from them in terms of finance and capital, which was not much difficult for them because they are all from wealthy families. Nha

Ha, with the help of three other co-founders in finance, she had not to worry about capital for the business. She also did not need to find an office, which is considered the most expensive thing for entrepreneurs to invest in, given the heavy trust in the sector.

We had four people contributing to finance, so it was not very hard. And the sector doesn't require much money to start up. The second problem for financing business was renting an office. However, I had one of the co-founders who had a big office, so we did not need to rent a new office. What a relief!. Ha

Operational support

Working directly with **Tra**, the friend cofounders used their area of knowledge and different skillsets to help her company

The one in Russia used to start up as a tutor for Russian students, so she had some experience talking to me about staff management, operation, and finance and accounting management. The other one is better at PR, marketing, and sales skills. She was pretty like me, but she was even more eloquent than me. She could give plenty of inspiring stories to students because she got a 100% scholarship from Birmingham University. So, we discussed and distributed our job differently. I was the CEO and director of everything. The one who worked in Russia was in charge of supporting (HR, Finance) and the last one took responsibility for Marketing and Sales. However, it was hard finding students and customers at the first stage, so we all had to find customers for our company.

At the first stage of starting up, those friend co-founders not only worked in one department but also shared the burden of looking for customers, which helped **Tra**'s and **Nha**'s business considerably.

I am the best at sales and marketing and expanding the customers, so I were in charge of customer relations. My other friend is good at analysing documents and information and writing, so She oversaw supporting those activities. And the last one took responsibility for finance, accounting, and legal issues of our companies. Nevertheless, we didn't divide so clearly at the first stage of starting up. Usually, at that time, three of us sat together and discussed each particular case and helped each other. For example, I was not the only one seeking customers, but we all had to do the job. Nha

Unlike **Nha** and **Tra**, **Ha** mentioned earlier that she had three friend co-founders; however, they were directors of other companies, so they co-founded with him but were not directly involved in her company's operation. Instead, she invited her ex-colleagues, who worked with her in the previous company, to be employees.

Some of my staff were ex-colleagues. They also worked with me in an OER company before. I used to be their manager, so it was not a problem for me to work with them smoothly. Two of them helped me with marketing and consulting students, and the other one was in charge of administrative tasks. Ha

In the UK, Cam made friends with a Vietnamese Doctor's Philosophy. When returning to Vietnam, the Dr. lectured for a university and worked as an expert for Cam's company.

I met Dr H when studying in the UK. When coming back to Vietnam, he agreed to help me as an academic consultant and expert for my company. He supported my students in getting conditional offers from good Universities in the UK and even assisted them in writing the statement of purpose to get scholarships. Cam

Phuong and **Tra** also mentioned students as their potential staff, helping them very proactively in operation. Although the group is young and lacks experience, their passion, enthusiasm, and agility made up for it.

Talking about staff, many of them were the students I taught at University in Vietnam. Therefore, the relationship between us was not only employer-staff but also teacher-students. I allowed them to work in an actual business environment to apply their knowledge to reality. Therefore, they devoted heart and soul to our company. They supported the workload in the company. Tra

I should mention the students that I taught when I returned from France. Some of them loved the OER sector or would like to look for scholarships in the future and asked for the opportunity to be my employees or trainees. Although they were young and inexperienced, they were full of enthusiasm and passion, never hesitated to learn and contributed considerably to my company. Phuong

Strategic advice, knowledge, status

Besides friends who supported our entrepreneurs in terms of operation and co-founding, there are also friends assisting my participants passively by giving knowledge and helpful entrepreneurial advice. **Tung** graduated from Law University. Therefore, when he started up, his ex-classmate who worked in the law sector did not mind supporting him.

Luckily for me, I graduated from the University of Law in Vietnam with my BA course, and then I had plenty of friends working at different law firms. So, they did help me a lot with business registration, tax issues and other legal documents. I only need to call; then, they will immediately help me. Tung

Before starting up, **Quynh** joined many classes teaching management skills and the art of doing business, where she met some teachers and influencers. Even after the courses, the coaches were still giving her tips, business strategy advice, and the art of leadership and management.

I participated in some classes about management, leadership, and business strategy, where I met my coaches and my teachers before starting up. Since then, they have kept following me and helped me tremendously with helpful advice and comprehensive business knowledge. Quynh

Tra could utilise the status of her ex-professor in the UK to ease the worry of customers' parents

I recruited some students from universities. Those professors were willing to support them academically and introduce them to activities in the city or university where they work or live. Therefore, I did not need to worry much about the students I sent abroad, which helped those students' parents trust me more. Tra

New network and contact support

Friends can even create more new networks for entrepreneurs than the family because most people that a family member knows, all other members also know. Referrals from friends are also more reliable than others from weak-ties relationships. The first network, which is considered one of the most important, is customers.

It was hard to find students and customers at first stage, so we all had to search for them from our previous networks to support the company's sales. Tra

Friends of **Ha**, who also cofounded with her, were directors of various companies in different sectors. They are also the ones who directly brought many customers to her company. One of them even was a director of a program for kids who are potential customers for Ha' company.

Four of my co-founders were also introducing customers to my company. Everyone had a KPI of recruiting 20 students per year for the company. This will motivate them to commit more to the company. They also have offspring and relatives to introduce as customers to my company. One of my co-founders has organised programs for Kids like CEO-kids so that I have a good source of students to consult. Ha

Besides her friend co-founders, **Ha** used to have colleagues teaching in an English school in Vietnam, so they kept introducing new customers to her.

That I used to work in an English school and had many good colleagues benefited me when I started up. They introduced to me many students and their family members as my customers. Ha

Similarly, Cam also got valuable help in recruiting a customer base from his ex-colleagues at the Ministry of Training and Education.

I had colleagues when I was working at the Ministry of Education; they also introduced customers to me, so they are my old colleagues, friends, potential customers, and marketers. Cam

Apart from peers and ex-colleagues, the customer base also comes from ex-teachers. Tung is an illustration of that.

I suddenly remembered that our teachers and professors at Law University also helped me. During my year of studying at the university, I also actively participated in the Student Youth organisation of my university. So all of them remembered me and have been helping me tremendously, such as introducing our company to students, taking me as a role model of success, and sending their close family members and friends to my company for consultation. Tung

The second important network is suppliers (universities and other educational institution partners). Besides friend co-founders in charge of external activities, foreign professors and ex-lecturers of those entrepreneurs connected them with new universities/ partners for new contracts.

My other friend is good at analysing documents, information and writing, so she was in charge of processing students' applications and writing cooperation letters to get contracts from universities. Nha

I believe professors at the university in the UK helped me get contracts at the first stage of the period. With an inexperienced girl like me at that time, no UK universities were

willing to work with me or sign recruitment contracts with me. Fortunately, my professors referred me to international student recruitment teams in different universities. Thanks to that, I managed to get the first partners to work with. Tra

Besides customers and suppliers, many friends of those entrepreneurs also referred their networks to be company employers.

I did not have to worry about staff shortage much, because I had three friend co-founders with many networks, so they introduced potential as well as talented employers to my company. Ha

Tra and **Nha** did not mention much about this, but it is sure that their friend cofounders also shared the burden of looking for talents, as **Nha** said.

In the first stage of starting up, we didn't divide entrepreneurial tasks so clearly. Usually, at that time, three of us sat together and discussed each case and helped each other. For example, I was not the only one seeking customers or staff, but we all had to do the job.

Emotional support

Not only family could support my entrepreneurs emotionally, but friends also took an important role in comforting those entrepreneurs in the most challenging stage of starting up. **Ha** and **Nha** were single moms, and they received tremendous support from their friend co-founders.

All my friends knew that I was a single mom before I started up, but they put belief in me, trusted me and travelled with me on the entrepreneurial journey. With their help, I did not feel alone when starting up. They also recruited students and shared the workload with me, although they did not involve directly in the operational process, which helped me reduce much less stress. Ha

Nha divorced her husband after two years of starting up, and her friend co-founders assisted her in overcoming that painful period. The definition of friend in the business of **Nha** is that the friend in need is the friend indeed. They did not only comfort her and inspire her again but also operated the company for her so that she could come back stronger.

I think my co-founders are true friends because they were not only beside me when we were successful but also at stake. I remember I got a shock after year two of starting up. When I got divorced from my husband, I was not myself for half a year. I should have focused better on the period, but many things came simultaneously, and I totally collapsed. Luckily, my co-founders helped me operate the company and inspired me to be back to work. And I was grateful to them for that. Nha

Although some friends of **Tung** did not cofound with him, they were also the source of happiness to him besides the help they brought to Tung.

As I mentioned earlier, my friends in law university helped me considerably with legal documents. Moreover, at the weekend, we usually went to the restaurants on the street to drink so that I could release some steams of starting up. Tung

Other participants also mentioned friends as the source of trust. Although they did not state it clearly, I believe that the trust and loyalty that friends bring to the company is also the source of comfort and inspiration for those entrepreneurs to keep going.

In short, strong-tie networks played a vital role in those entrepreneurs' success in the first period of starting up. The network is considered quite a few multiplexity by the different roles in contributing to those entrepreneurs. The graph below shows how the strong tie network multiplexity is illustrated among those entrepreneurs (Figure 16).

- Accordingly, three out of seven participants, **Ha**, **Tra**, and **Nha**, were single moms or single at the time of starting up. Therefore, they counted on their classmates, their peers who shared the same passion for cofounding with.
- **Cam** and **Tung**, the only two male entrepreneurs, started up with their wives and were given plenty of spousal help. Meanwhile, the two entrepreneurial women, **Quynh** and **Phuong**, got advice or emotional support from their husbands. Still, they respected their husbands' jobs and started up alone or with other people.

- **Cam** is the one who got the most help from family tie relationships, including his wife, cousin, sister and brother-in-law, while **Tung** and **Tra** mentioned the “friend” group more, including classmates and ex-professor in terms of helping their business.
- **Phuong** is the only entrepreneur who started up without co-founders, and her husband is the only strong-tie that she mentioned in the interview helping her with entrepreneurial activity.

Figure 16: How the strong tie network multiplexity supported the entrepreneurs

In the next part, those participants will reveal business-tie network multiplexity more.

4.5.2 Subtheme Two: Weak-tie relationship in personal network multiplexity

As mentioned in the literature review, Granovetter (1973) classified strong-tie and weak-tie relationships based on time factors (how long), emotional intensity, intimacy level, and the degree of reciprocity between members. He also argued the strength of weak-tie relationships in looking for new opportunities than strong-tie networks. Hu and colleagues (2019) advocated Granovetter's (1973) and appreciated the role of weak tie networks highly as the crucial bridge transmitting information quickly and widely. They also posited that the weak tie networks are superior in reducing redundant information in the network. Although I realise the vital role of strong-tie relationships in network multiplexity, I still agree with the aforementioned researchers in terms of connecting to new networks and discovering new opportunities and new customers. Let us have a look at how our entrepreneurs received entrepreneurial support from the network.

4.5.2.1 Business partners

Although entrepreneurs might have plenty of networks and partners, I only focus on business partners defined as multiplexity (many roles) by interviewed participants in the study. Hence, the chosen group is the representative (reps) of educational institutions (suppliers) that those entrepreneurs co-operated with. They supported my entrepreneurs in terms of giving information about their courses and assisted things outside of their job description, which made the network multiplexity.

Sharing knowledge, skills and giving advice

Uni or educational reps are the ones who represent the image of the educational organisations that they are working for, which is why they are professional, dedicated, and knowledgeable. Besides, they are also the ones who clearly understand the educational system as well as the various experience in working with different partners. Being a young entrepreneur at the time of starting up, Tung received plenty of support from those uni reps in advising on starting up and counselling skills.

I want to mention Vietnamese Uni reps as well. Their responsibility is merely to support agents and provide accurate and up-to-date information about the University or educational organisations. However, they had known me before I started up in the previous companies. So, they did not hesitate to give me advice on starting up. Tung

Like Tung, **Nha** set up very early in 2000, so she did not have many prior succeeded companies to follow; therefore, she received quite a few entrepreneurial advice from uni reps.

My company has been established for more than 20 years, and I also have been working with some uni reps for that many years. I can say that I have been working and turning old simultaneously with them. They did help me from the beginning not only in terms of jobs but also entrepreneurial advice. Nha

Quynh was fortunate because she set up in Vietnam. Still, she also had a branch in the UK, so she was not supported by Vietnamese representatives but also by foreign representatives in the UK in terms of giving direct training without any delays.

I was lucky that I got help from representatives in both Vietnam and the UK because I was based in the UK mostly. Hence, I could access information more quickly and thoroughly than other agencies that did not have a branch in the UK. The UK representatives work directly on the campus so that they can give me more accurate and up-to-date information and better training sessions than Vietnamese representatives. Nonetheless, I think Vietnamese representatives were easier to approach and more enthusiastic because we shared the same culture. Quynh

On the contrary, **Tra** felt that the Vietnamese representative supported her better in giving important ideas about recruiting students strategy.

I was lucky to meet uni reps, including Vietnamese and foreign people. Uni rep based in Vietnam helped me better in converting students. Tra

Vietnamese reps based in Vietnam and worked directly with Vietnamese agents, thus, **Tra** felt that the support from Vietnamese reps was better and more direct than the foreign counterpart. Like Tra, **Phuong** thought that Vietnamese reps were more like network multiplexity than the counterpart in foreign countries because they could come directly to her office to support her staff and provide important news about courses and university information.

In the first years, there were only few Vietnamese reps, so most uni reps were based in foreign universities. I worked with them mainly over email, fax and rarely phone calls. They did help me much, especially when I visited their university. Later on, when many universities had more Vietnam reps, we co-operated better. Vietnam reps often came to our office, and we quickly became acquainted; I felt that they helped us better than the uni foreign reps. They came to our office more often than the uni foreign reps, and we discussed together to find the best way to recruit and convert students. Phuong

All CEOs mentioned that uni reps proactively supported them in knowledge, skills, and information and even gave helpful advice on recruitment and entrepreneurship based on their understanding of other companies and the overseas educational recruitment market. Besides, many of the CEO even said that the uni reps event supported them in consulting students and converting students for their company. This will be mentioned more clearly in the next part-operational support.

Operational support

Mostly, the operation support from uni reps comes from counselling. Customers (students and parents) usually feel more trusted when being consulted by direct uni reps rather than educational consultants in the company, which is why our CEO used this to ask for help from uni reps.

Because they knew our company and I were young and new, they even helped us convince customers and convert students to my company. Tung

They also helped consult students for us sometimes, which increased the conversion rate for our company too. Besides, they also train our staff very well with the knowledge of the universities they were working with. Ha

They did help me much, especially when I visited their university, and they were also willing to visit Vietnam to train my staff and consult students for my company. Phuong

Besides consulting directly as a counsellor, they worked as trainers of those companies to support new staff in terms of counselling skills and knowledge, as Phuong and Hao mentioned above. **Tra, Quynh, Cam** and **Tung** also received support from uni reps.

Uni rep based in Vietnam helped me better deliver information directly and train my staff at my office. Tra

They visited our office to train my staff in terms of new visa regulations and university programs. Quynh

They even came to our office to train and share counselling skills, as well as professional experiences for us, which I believe, are not relevant to their job description. I believe that this will reduce the time from 5-7 years to 2-3 years to the success route. Tung

They helped me with a lot of knowledge about the country/ uni they represent. Cam

Apart from assisting in consulting students as counsellors and training staff like mentors, those uni reps also helped those entrepreneurs as supporting staff in terms of connecting them with foreign universities. According to Phuong, Cam, and Tra's sharing story, that help is necessary because of the geographical factor and time zone between Vietnam and foreign countries.

In terms of on-the-job content, they are the ones who contacted the uni directly, so it was easier for us because you know it is tough to contact uni when the time zone is different. And Vietnamese uni rep usually knew how to contact the uni better than us. Phuong

Besides counselling, they also worked as a bridge connecting me with university partners when my staff could not contact them, which made the step of processing student applications easier and smoother. Cam

When I wanted to propose any ideas to uni, they really listened to me, and I usually saw the change after the meeting between me and those uni reps. Of course, it was not happening with all uni reps but some of them. Then I realised that the more you can become acquainted with the uni rep, the better you can work with their universities. Tra

The new network, contacts, and opportunity

Uni reps are the weak tie in the social network of those entrepreneurs. Therefore, they did help better find more new contacts, networks, and opportunities than weak-tie relationships. The opportunities mentioned here mostly are exclusive scholarships and information.

Cam and **Nha's** entrepreneurial enterprises were advertised or chosen to send customers introduced by uni reps.

They also sent many students who are their children, relatives, and friends to my company. Cam

They sent students to me, advertised my company and even when they left the sector or the organisation they worked for, they still supported me in the way they could, such as sending the students to me. Do you know why? Because when they worked in the organisation, they had to be fair with other agents. However, when they left, they didn't have to follow any rules of their previous organisation, so they could quickly introduce students to us. Nha

Besides introducing customers, new partners are also usually introduced by those uni reps.

When uni reps left, they moved to the new organisation, usually educational institutions. We could still co-operate. They helped me sign the new contract with that new organisation. Nha

When I started my company without many networks because I was young, some uni reps introduced my company and me to other uni reps. Thanks to that, I could manage to sign new contracts with new uni reps and increase the number of uni partners for my company. Tung

In terms of opportunity, Phuong and Tra used the relationship with uni reps to ask for exclusive scholarships from foreign university partners.

I became acquainted with some of the uni reps, and we soon became friends. Hence, it was easier for us to approach the source of scholarship and essential information from the universities they work with. Phuong

For example, when their universities had a good scholarship scheme, they talked to me early and enthusiastically supported my students. And most of my good students received a scholarship from the scheme that those uni reps introduced. Tra

Besides scholarships, **Quynh and Ha** also mentioned other “opportunities” when they developed deeper relationships with some uni reps.

I only have good relationships with some institutions because I don't have the time and resources for many. For institutions that I focused more on sending students and marketing for, they also gave us more scholarships for students in return. They also gave us more bonus, international trips, gifts, rewards, recognition, and many more visit to our office. Quynh

As I talked about commission, I got more commissions and bonuses, field trips, and scholarship opportunities from the uni partners that I worked with more closely. Ha

Emotional support

Uni reps represent their university and are the primary contact for agencies. The more time they worked with those entrepreneurs, the more they became acquainted and shared sorrow as happiness with my participants. The emotional support is usually mutual and clearer after many years.

My company has been established for more than 20 years, and I also have been working with some uni reps for that many years. I can say that I have been working and turning old simultaneously with them. After 3-4 years, I realised that they became my friends to whom I can easily share my true feelings. Nha

Some of the uni reps I became acquainted with and soon became friends, so it was easier for us to share the happiness of success or sadness of failure. Phuong

Emotional support is also in the form of encouragement, especially for a new and young entrepreneur like **Tung**.

I knew some uni reps before; hence, they were pleased and inspiring when I started up. They encouraged me to keep up and always believed in the success of my company. Therefore, I was really grateful to them! Tung

Or sometimes, emotional support also came from the hospitality and the welcoming attitude of foreign uni reps when my entrepreneurs attended business trips to foreign universities.

On the other hand, when I went abroad to visit universities, foreign uni reps warmly hosted and welcomed me. They even took me and my staff around the city and vice versa. When they visited Vietnam for educational conferences, we also showed our hospitality and warmth to welcome them. Gradually, we have helped each other more than just our partner relationship. Tra

The warm and reciprocal relationships between uni reps and entrepreneurs foster feelings between parties, which is considered good emotional support for our entrepreneurs.

The answers from the aforementioned participants show that emotional support is not delivered immediately like in strong-tie relationships. The support is formed after a period of time after the mutual understanding between parties as well as the efforts of our entrepreneurs in building the relationship with uni reps.

4.5.2.2. Staff

Staff at the beginning of starting up is precious to entrepreneurs. They believe in the success of entrepreneurship and contribute considerably to entrepreneurial enterprises. The story that our participants told below will demonstrate that. Staff not only supported them in terms of

operation but also shared their network, contacts, advertising and marketing for those companies.

Operational support

Ha recruited staff who are students who studied in foreign universities, so they not only understand the process of studying abroad but also had full of hands-on experiences in living and studying abroad to consult clients as well as students properly.

Mainly, I recruit international students coming back to VN to work for me. They not only supported my company with their expertise but also helped me to recruit and share experience in studying and living abroad. Ha

Similar to Ha, Phuong recruited staff who mostly were studying abroad students. It was hard to convince them at first because of the company's small size at the time of starting up. However, knowing her passion in the sector as well as the meaning of the jobs, many of them agreed to help.

The following important people I should mention were my staff. Most of them I selected were students who had studied overseas before because I believed that they were the ones who experienced the overseas study themselves, so it would be easier for them to consult my students and my customers. The first thing they helped me with was the choice they made. They agreed to work with me while they could work in a better environment with their profiles. After they knew my wish and vision to help Vietnamese students, they decided to be on board with me. Phuong

Nha showed difficulty in finding qualified staff because of the bad reputation in the market back in the 2000s; however, she was fortunate to recruit some.

You know, at first, it was challenging to recruit staff for the sector because there were many fake and scam companies back in 2000, as I mentioned before. Many staffs were worried about being deceived or not paid. I was lucky to get them, and they did help

me support company operation at the first stage, including recruiting, promoting, and document supporting.

To save some initial cost of starting up, Tung and his wife managed to work on their own for six months. However, the workload became unbearable, and they did need more operational support from staff.

The workload was too much, and only our husband and wife dealt with them. After that, I think I got insomnia till now. Gradually, we recruited more staff to share the heavy workload so that we could deal with more new tasks. Then we moved from a small office (30 square meters) to a bigger office (100 square meters). Tung

Tung also has a good strategy for recruiting suitable staff for the position he needs to help the company effectively. Tung's company also was able to save some initial costs.

At first, we recruited part-time students who are 3rd or 4th year at some universities in Hanoi for marketing purposes because, due to cost, we couldn't pay much for the full-time employees. My wife and I counselled students directly. But after some months, when we had more customers, I recruited some full-time, experienced staff for counselling positions. Tung

Network, contact, and customers

Introducing new staff

When **Cam** just started his company, he did not have many staffs, especially reliable ones; therefore, he counted on his staff to introduce him to more decent employees.

My staff was also essential at that time, they were not only working for me, but they also helped me to find more new staff. Cam

Tra recruited her students at the university she taught to work for her, and they kept introducing her to new potential friends, so she did not need to be concerned about staff lacking.

To be honest, I didn't have to worry much about the HR problem at that time, thanks to my students. Tra

Recruiting more customers

Staff are important in contributing to direct revenue because they have their own networks to recruit and convert potential clients in their network easier and more effectively.

My staff was also crucial; they generated more revenue for the company by looking for customers. Cam

Employees helped me a lot with connecting with new customers. Quynh

They did help me look for potential customers, and new networks, besides supporting activities for our company at the first stage of starting up. Nha

On top of that, they also introduced our company to their network circle, bringing more customers to our company, which I believe was extremely necessary and vital at the first stage of starting up. Phuong

Tung gave his part-time staff, still students, a flexible and friendly environment and learning opportunity, so they were left with a good impression. As a result, they contributed and introduced new customers to his company.

For the staff who are students, we trained them very well and gave them a young and dynamic environment so that they can develop without any restrictions. Therefore, they not only helped my company with the tasks assigned but also introduced students to us and treated us like brother-sister and trainers too. Tung

Marketing and advertising

During the process of introducing networks to entrepreneurial enterprises, staff also advertised and promoted the good image of those companies to their network.

They were also helping the image of my company to be recognised by many people. I could not advertise my company all the time, which is considered boastful, so my employees were really dedicated and assisted me a lot in that. Quynh

My initial staff introduced my company to their classmates through posts on their personal Facebook and sent me their first acquaintances as customers; gradually, our company image became more recognised. Ha

New ideas and perception

Nha showed her respect and appreciation toward the young staff that she recruited. They gave her better ideas on approaching young customers.

They also gave me plenty of new perceptions because they were young compared to me. So that I can complete myself more and have more ways of access to different types of people, especially young customers. Nha

On the other hand, Phuong recruited students who studied abroad, so they were experienced in convincing and converting students better.

My staff was experienced in studying and living outside of my country, so they knew precisely what students have to cope with and what they will learn and gain after the study abroad. Their new perception was beneficial to my company in recruiting students and clients. Phuong

In short, staffs were vital to those entrepreneurs in the OER sector. They did not only implement their job at operational level but also played as marketers, promoters, and recruiters to support the process of entrepreneurship. Besides, their new ideas and perceptions were also the source of the new approach method to customers and clients of their generation.

Besides staff, the multiplexity of the customer network, which is considered an external factor, also contributed tremendously to the company's development, which will be shown in the next part.

4.5.2.3. Customers

Customers in the thesis include clients, students who would like to study abroad and their parents, based on the sharing of my entrepreneurs. They are not only the ones who directly bring the profit to the companies but also the marketing force for the company's success.

The new network, contact

Besides being the customers, those people kept introducing those entrepreneurial companies to many more customers after their successful results and good service were received.

My students (clients) and their parents helped me to recruit more customers by giving me contacts in their relationship circles. Ha

My students and the parents of students are significant. They are not only my customers, but they also introduce me to plenty of new customers. Quynh

They kept introducing new students to me, and my customer network has continued expanding. Tra

Some customers even became the company's stakeholders and were willing to introduce customers to the company with their trust.

Our beloved customers soon became the company's stakeholders and kept recruiting and introducing new customers to us. Cam

Besides introducing a new network of customers, some clients even gave my participants important contacts in government or in high class, which made it easier for entrepreneurs to do their business.

At that time, students who could study abroad were usually from wealthy families. Therefore, I quickly was able to network with many rich people with good titles in society. So, it was helpful later for me in terms of working with the government and high-class people. Nha

Tung's customers followed him since he worked in previous companies before starting up, so when they knew he decided to start up, they kept being his company's patrons and introduced more new customers to him.

When I left the previous companies, I had to return all the customer data to them. However, some customers still loved the service I had brought to them, so when they knew I started up my own company in the OER sector, they kept contacting me to use my service (training English for their children and helping them with study abroad applications). They also introduced new customers for my wife and me. Many of them were also the reason for my decision to start up my own business, as I said initially.
Tung

Marketing and advertising

Many of Cam's and Quynh's customers agreed for them to use their image and testimonial videos as well as reviews to promote and endorse their company without anything required in return.

My customers were very willing to leave good reviews as well as permitted us to use their interviews after using the service. That is one of many ways new customers knew us and trusted us more. Cam

My customers wrote good reviews for my company and did some videos to endorse my company without asking for anything in return. Quynh

They at that time brought benefits to our company, introduced new customers to our companies, wrote many good reviews so that new customers would trust us more. Nha

Phuong had the innovative strategy to consult students at their houses directly. So, she did not only consult students but also their parents, grandparents, and the entire family. So, she soon got their heart and trust. Therefore, they did not hesitate to introduce and promote the company as the symbol of dedication and profession.

I usually went directly to the customer's house to consult if needed. So, the entire family believed me and kept sending me new customers, and we had a very good relationship; they even brought me plenty of gifts on some occasions. Phuong

Another way of promoting a business is to protect it from attack, wrongly critics, or other people's accusations.

They also defended my company when there were terrible and wrong rumours about my company. Ha

Through the story of those entrepreneurial about their customers, it can be concluded that they are not only the ones who created the value for the company by bringing profit for the company but also advertise, promote even bring more customers and more essential networks for those company. Many customers became patrons, stakeholders willing to protect those companies from critics, bad reviews, or wrongly accusations.

In short, although weak-tie relationships in network multiplexity did not have many overlapping roles in helping entrepreneurs like strong-tie, their support was still valuable in the context of starting up (Figure 17).

- Accordingly, six out of seven participants got help from uni reps in operation (consulting students and training staff) except for Nha. It might be explained that she is the only company starting up from very early back to the 2000s; therefore, the support from the university in terms of uni reps was not sufficient.
- Nha and Tung are the only two entrepreneurs talking about emotional support. The reason for that is that Tung was relatively young and new at starting up. Hence, he shared that he got tremendous support from uni reps as well as their encouragement. On the other hand, Nha set up the company earliest back in 2000 with not so many agencies to compete with; therefore, uni reps could spend more time supporting her company.

- Tung, Tra and Ha mentioned opportunities such as exclusive scholarships and more bonuses and benefits for their companies. Those participants shared that they paid attention, promoted and sent students to those universities more than other partners.
- Regarding staff, although some employees recruited were involved in the operational process, they did more than position titles because of the nature of entrepreneurship. Besides, they also brought new customers to those entrepreneurial companies (five out of seven mentioned the support). Furthermore, they also helped the companies find staff based on their network circle.
- Some elderly entrepreneurs such as Nha and Phuong also highlighted that they benefited from new perceptions and ideas of young staff, supporting them in approaching a younger customer base.
- Regarding customer support, most entrepreneurs posited that customers were not only their source of income but also introduced a network of new customers to them. Besides, they were also the marketing team of the companies, promoting them without the payment needed and willing to protect them from bad rumours in the story of Ha.
- Nha started up quite early, back in 2000, when only rich students and children of government officials could study abroad, whereby she could connect with many new wealthy customers and VIP officials in society. This assisted her tremendously in doing the business.

In the next part, the results as well as achievements that those companies gained from the network multiplexity will be more clearly revealed.

Figure 17: How the weak tie network multiplexity supported the entrepreneurs

4.6. Theme Three: Dimensions of developments

In this part, I wanted to ask quantitative questions to entrepreneurs to compare the first three years of starting up regarding new networks, revenue, reputation measured by interactions on social media and other online platforms, and expansion of the company (staffs, building branches). This will help to see clearly and statistically the development of those companies.

Nevertheless, the limitation of the part is that I could not collect the indexes of the companies fully during three years of starting up involving revenue, profit, and other statistics. Besides, it was hard to expect clear answers from participants because it was sensitive and personal when mentioning profit, money, and revenue. Therefore, all the approximation numbers that my participants provided were all appreciated.

4.6.1. Subtheme One: New networks and contacts

In the previous parts, both strong tie and weak tie relationships in network multiplexity gave those entrepreneurs many quality contacts, which assisted them considerably during the first start-up process. Especially, all the participants mentioned the sharp increase in the number of education partners (suppliers), which is shown in the below graph (Figure 18).

Figure 18: The percentage of increasing the numbers of partners compared to the first year

From the graph, it can say that most of the companies increased remarkably by double and more than that after the first year. Quynh started her company while she had got her company in the UK; therefore, she had got quite a few contacts before that, whereby in the second year, she got a six times increase in the number of partners.

Nha, Tra and Tung did not grow strongly in terms of the contact number may be explained by the following reasons. Nha and Tra started up their company quite early in the 2000s; therefore, there were not many partners interested in the Vietnamese market. In the case of Tung, he was the youngest at the time of start-up, and his co-founder was just a close tie relationship, who was his wife, which is why his number of new partners did not increase strongly like other entrepreneurs.

Most companies did not increase the number of educational partners impressively in year three. After being asked, they all answered that they still wanted to expand to many partners, but they still wanted to focus on essential partners to recruit students to. Therefore, there was a slight decrease in the figure in year 3.

The resources were limited, so I could not invest in all partners or send students to all partners. Therefore, after year 3, I tried to maintain essential networks rather than expand too much. Quality is still over quantity. Ha

I could not be in a good relationship with all Uni; thus, after year two, I just focused on some institutions that are good with us to develop together because, you know, resources are scarce. Quynh

Nevertheless, network or personal network multiplexity did help them develop the impressive quantities of partner networks, ranging from 300% to 900%.

4.6.2. Subtheme Two: The rise of revenue and customer base

In the context of the OER sector, revenue is as vital as the number of students recruited. The primary revenue of the companies was the commission paid by educational institutions for recruiting students. Therefore, when asked about the financial development after three years of starting up, my participants estimated the increase in the revenue as well as the number of

students converted as relatively equally. The graph below was formulated based on those entrepreneur’s estimations rather than exact data (which is considered company secrets).

Figure 19: The percentage of increasing the numbers of students recruited as well as revenue estimated compared to the first year

As can be seen from the graph, most of the company’s revenue and the number of students rose steadily over the first years of starting up. Network or network multiplexity was not the only factor affecting the figure; however, based on the participants' answers before that, the network made up more than 65% of their success at the first period of their entrepreneurship. The figure also reflects quite precisely the same role of network or network multiplexity.

The graph shows that Cam company’s revenue increased impressively by six times in year three compared to the first year, followed by 400% of Quynh’s company. The rise was relatively equivalent to the increase of partners of those two companies. When asked about the revenue surge, Cam also shared that it comes from the number of partners and the strengths of his staff.

In year 3, my number of partners was seven times compared to the first year; therefore, I could give more options to students. Besides, my staff recruited from different universities helped me connect with so many prospective students, which soon became our customer base. Cam

Quynh was based in the UK so that she could expand her number of partners impressively. Still, it can be predicted that she did not base in Vietnam to manage the business directly as well as utilised networks effectively like Cam in Vietnam. Therefore, her revenue increase was lower than he's.

On the other side, the graph witnesses a reduction in revenue in the company of Nha and Tu compared to the second year. In the case of Nha, she divorced her husband during the year 3 of starting up, so it is understandable that it might have affected her emotionally. However, she mentioned the comfort and support from her co-founders as the saviour of her business life, which helped her company keep going till today. In the case of Tu, he was young at the time of starting up with his wife, so he did not have much experience. Besides, year three of his startup was also Covid-19 pandemic period; therefore, the reduction in year three is inevitable. Nevertheless, regardless of difficult periods, both Tu and Nha still managed to overcome difficulties to develop their business, which is worth receiving respect as well as admiration.

4.6.3. Subtheme Three: Reputation by online and offline interactions

Trust and reputation are survival to businesses, especially OER companies. In the era of technology, the interactions on social media will measure quite precisely how popular and trustable a company is. Therefore, the figures are also considered meaningful indexes when mentioning development, shown in the line graph below.

Figure 20: The percentage of increasing the numbers of interactions on social media (Website, Facebook etc.) compared to the first year

As can be referred from the graph, all the companies generally maintained a steady rise in the number of interactions on social media throughout the first three years of starting up; however, there were slight differences.

Tung's company impressed us the most with the surge in interaction on social media. It is not difficult to explain given that he was the latest to start up as well as young enough to approach new marketing social platforms more effectively than other participants. On top of that, his staff were also very young, so they adapted new online social platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and Facebook very fast, which helped connect students easier and more efficiently.

Back in the 2000s, when many social media platforms were not invented or not popular, the reputation and interaction with new customers of Nha and Tra mostly came from websites or word of mouth marketing.

We started up in 2005, so Facebook, Instagram and other online stuff were not popular. But the website traffic has increased remarkably after the second year and third year of starting up. Tra

Facebook has not developed in the 2000s, but the views on our website increased by double each year. And I think word of mouth was also vital to us when technology didn't take any critical role like today. Nha

Like Tra and Nha, Phuong tent to use word-of-mouth marketing and a networking strategy like home consultation to bond better with her prospective students.

We mainly used word-of-mouth and introduction from partners, as well as direct consultation more than online social platforms. Accordingly, I contacted 50 schools and universities around the first three years so that they could advertise for us. We also had a home counselling service so that I could visit clients directly to bond with the entire family. I believe this way will increase our conversion rate. Phuong

In short, regardless of online or offline interactions, the primary purpose of those interactions is trust-building and reputation gain. Nevertheless, in the era of technology, the more effectively a company can utilise online platforms, the more popularity that the company can

gain, which will benefit the company's revenue. The role of network multiplexity in online reputation development was shown by the help from young and tech-savvy staff and networks with digital marketing companies. Meanwhile, the success of traditional offline marketing methods will depend on networks with relevant influencing partners (school, universities, teachers, acquaintances etc.) or staff who have good face to face education counselling skills.

4.6.4. Subtheme Four: Other developments

Besides revenue, customers, new university partners as well as interactions on social media, my participants also mentioned other developments, including the expansion of branches, the proof of reputation (rewards, certificates) (Nha, Phuong, Tra), franchising activity (Quynh), the expansion of office, the increase in the number of staff (Tung, Cam)as well as essential networks for business.

Gradually, we recruited more staff to share the heavy workload so that we could deal with more new tasks. Accordingly, after three years, we had more than 20 permanent employees. We also moved from a small office (30 square meters) to a bigger office (100 square meters). Tung

I also expanded my office from a two-storey rented house to a ten-storey building located on the most prominent street in Hanoi with 40 staff. Cam

While **Tung and Cam** could manage to expand his office with more staff, Quynh franchised her brand to 10 partners in 10 cities in Vietnam, thanks to her network.

Three years after starting up in Vietnam, I also franchised my brand to 10 provinces and cities in Vietnam instead of setting up more offices because it was hard for me to manage given that I had to go back and forth between Vietnam and the UK. Quynh

Nha Tra and Phuong, on the other hand, mentioned more about the expansion of the branches and penetration process into new markets.

After the third year, we kept holding educational fairs and still maintained the leading position in terms of good service. We planned to open another branch in Hai Phong city and develop to Japanese and Korean markets. Nha

Tra focused firmly on recruiting for UK institutions. Therefore, she got recognition as well as many rewards from British Council. After three years of starting up, she also set up another branch in HCM city.

After three years, we also got awards mainly from the British Council, such as Top Performance Agent and Top Emerging Agents. Besides, I also opened another branch in HCM city. Tra

Phuong also expanded her business to HCM city, and she also mentioned the rewards Swiss and French educational institutions granted her for recruiting achievements.

After three years, our companies focused extensively on the French and Swiss markets, so we got plenty of prizes for consulting Vietnamese students in those countries. Thanks to the help from my brother, I also set up another office in HCM city. Phuong

In conclusion, the dimensions of start-up companies' development in the OER sector are not different from other start-ups in terms of figures such as revenue, number of networks, customers gain, and business expansion. Besides, enterprises in the sector also require plenty of trust and reputation. Therefore, interactions on social media platforms or word of mouth methods and recognitions (rewards, certificates...) are also important and considered one of many dimensions of development.

4.7. Theme Four: The dynamism of personal network multiplexity

During the first start-up period, there are always changes and unprecedented events within the network affecting start-up companies. My participants' companies are not exceptions. The changes can derive from many factors such as role changing, time, the need to use service, the strength of networks, and the resources allocated by entrepreneurs. However, there are also some unchanged networks, always standing behind my participants to support their business.

4.7.1 Subtheme One: Inevitable changes in network

Staff changing

It is always understandable when staff changes because they have different motivations, job goals, and plans. Besides, there are some unprecedented events that the entrepreneurs must make redundancy to some staff. The situation was happening with Ha and Tung company because they just started up recently in 2018-2019 with the Covid-19 pandemic.

Because of covid, many staffs were made redundant. I only kept some best staff. However, I still maintain a good relationship with them. Ha

Cam recruited many students in the last year of university when starting up. Therefore, many of them left his company after 2-3 years to pursue a Master course abroad, or some students realised their other true dream job, so they also left him for another job. Nevertheless, they still became his clients or partners and sent him more new students.

Some staff left my company to study abroad or work in a different sector. However, they are still partners sending more customers to us. My vice-director was replaced. However, she still helped me if needed. Cam

Similarly, **Quynh**, **Nha** and **Phuong** accepted the change in the staff because they also skipped some jobs in the past.

I am also the one who skipped many jobs to become an entrepreneur in the sector. Therefore, I respect the decision of my staff if they decide to leave. After three years, I received resignation letters from two important staff because they had different plans. Knowing that I could not keep them, I turned them into partners so that they still can contribute to my company. Quynh

The fact that staff change is inevitable. Nevertheless, after 3- 4 years, nothing changed much. Some of my staff might leave the company, but I still let them work as partners, so they still can get commissioned by sending customers or students to our company. Nha

Staff turnover is inevitable because we believe that everyone has different missions in life. Some of the staff left the company became our partners, sending students and more customers to our company. Phuong

Tra did not mention the leaving of staff. Instead, she talked about the change in the role because she believed that as long as they still could support her business, they were still with her.

My staffs were still with me regardless of their role changes. Some of my staff decided to study abroad, becoming my customers. After that, they came back to my country and became my partners, or referrals, introducing many more customers to me. We might be different in roles, but I always respect, believe, and give value to my networks, so they are still with my company and me. Tra

Customers leaving – is this a bad thing?

Besides the staff changes, customers are also the ones who tend to change to other companies if not supported carefully and adequately. Similar to the staff changes, my participants also believe that the change in the weak network is inevitable.

Many customers still stayed faithful to us but some left. I also knew that it was unavoidable, although we tried our best to retain as many as possible. Cam

Quynh did not answer directly about the situation. Still, she mentioned a good point here: the sector's customers are easy to leave because the demand is not always needed, and the network is relatively weak.

For students and parents, they are also easy to change if they find better service or I don't take care of them enough. However, for ones who believed in our company or were taken care of better, they were still with us. I also know that students and parents don't need us every day but only occasionally, so the tie is not so solid. Therefore, I also had to pay attention to those really in demand of my services. Quynh

Fortunately, **Nha** is the one to start up earliest in the market; therefore, her customer base hardly left her.

I think I am also lucky to start up very early in the sector, so our reputation, patience, and consistency were enough to retain customers after many years. Hardly I lost old customers to other competitors. Nha

Tung has just started up, but it is impressive that he also could retain up to 90% of loyal customers.

Luckily, 90% of our students stayed with me after three years and kept introducing new customers to me. Tung

Phuong, Tra, and Tung mentioned the change in the role of customers as a positive sign. Although they did not use the service or were no longer customers, they still supported the company by becoming advertisers, partners, or even friends.

Because my staffs and I usually counselled customers directly at their house. Therefore, I formed a good bond with the entire family. After 2-3 years, they became my loyal clients, even friends with me. Phuong

Many of my first customers became the advertiser for my company. Tung

My customers were still with me for some years. But their role was different. Some of my customers used my OER service to study abroad. Then when they came back, they became my staff or partner introducing new clients to my company and me. Tra

In short, although the change in the customer network is inevitable, with the good care from my entrepreneurs, the change is not significant. Besides, there were also changes in the role of customers, which transformed the customer networks into staff, advertisers, or partners.

4.7.2 Subtheme Two: Unchanged relationships – Do they remain unchanged?

Besides relationships that constantly change, family, spouses, friends, or co-founders from the beginning days are hard to change. Many of them were willing to support my entrepreneurs during difficult times of starting up; however, there were also some exceptions.

Family

In the section, I am not mentioning the entire family of those entrepreneurs but the ones affecting their business. Not surprisingly, the strong-tie network was hard to break.

Children are everything I have, so I always care for them with my heart, so there is no need to say more. Ha

My wife, my sister and my brother-in-law were the ones who supported me in the business. They were still the same after three years of starting up. They did even help me more than I expected. Cam

My parents and my family group have always supported me and never changed. Quynh

At first, Phuong's husband was not involved in her company's operation, but with her request, he agreed to help to some extent. It can be said that after some years, the strong tie network even helped her better with the new advertising role.

My husband has always been with me since we met. You can watch the most recent videos on Youtube; he even spoke Vietnamese along with me to celebrate the Vietnamese Lunar New year. At first, I told you that he was not involved in my company's operations. But because Vietnamese people love foreigners and my students also wanted to speak to him in English and French, I let him help me. Thanks to his support, I gained plenty of trust from my students and customers. Phuong

In another story, Tra's brother, who used to support her business in digital marketing and IT, left her. Nevertheless, the small change was still positive. It can say that the role is different, but the support is still the same.

My brother, after four years, has started up his own company, but he has always been helping me, and he is also one of my partners in providing digital marketing services and management software. Tra

Unfortunately, Nha divorced her husband after three years of starting up. He was not involved in the process of her entrepreneurship; however, it adversely affected her emotional feelings and work-life balance.

In year three of business, I got divorced from my husband. It affected me emotionally, and I lost a year to think about my private life. Even my husband, who I always thought would stay forever, could leave me someday. So, I don't mind the change at all. Nha

The event was too much for her at the most challenging stage of doing business. Nevertheless, the tragedy led her to awaken stage about life changes.

Co-founders

Co-founders are usually friends, classmates, spouses, or family members; therefore, the change is usually tiny. That statement is quite accurate with the cases of my participants.

My co-founders, as being said, were my classmates. They did have different companies, but they still supported me so that I could achieve my dreams. There were no changes in the group. Ha

My wife, the co-founder of our company, never left me (at least we were still happy at that moment. Tung

As I have mentioned, my co-founders have been with me since the first days of starting up. I know change is inevitable, but they are still with me now. So, I am happy about that. Nha

Nevertheless, there were also changes; even the change might be in the position of co-founders and my entrepreneurs always prepared for it.

My co-founders were still working with me. However, one co-founder whose perception is quite different from ours left the company and eventually ended up in a different sector. But I always understand the break-ups in business. It is normal, and we have to accept the change. I am also a strong woman, so I don't mind at all. Tra

Cam, Quynh and Phuong did not have co-founders when starting up, so they were not mentioned in the section.

In short, even networks that everyone thinks are hardly changed also changed. However, expecting changes, welcoming changes with a positive attitude, and preparing for changes are ways to help my entrepreneurs stand firmly during the challenging period of starting up.

4.8. Theme Five: Personal Network Multiplexity strategy

After understanding the network multiplexity dimensions that my participants utilised to develop their business, I came up with the question about the strategy that those entrepreneurs used to maintain and develop those networks. Fortunately, I received fascinating answers as well as valuable tactics and strategies that will benefit companies who would like to start up in the sector in the future.

4.8.1. Subtheme One: Standard PNM strategy for each type of network

Based on the answers and codes drawn from participants' interviews, the strategies and tactics will be divided into two groups: strong tie networks (family, friends, close acquaintances) and weak tie networks (staffs, clients, uni reps)

4.8.1.1 PNM strategy for strong tie networks -Understanding, Communication, Sacrificing and Unconditional Love

Family

For unchanged networks such as family, most participants gave the group the best things. And it is not about strategy or tactics; it is true love from their heart. **Ha** was a single mom when starting up, so her love for her children was needless to say.

I always care for my children with all my heart, so there is no need to say more. Ha

His wife, sister, and brother-in-law are the ones affecting Cam's entrepreneurship; therefore, he showed respect and true love to them regardless of the difficulty of the process.

I always respect and show my love for my wife as well as my sister and brother-in-law. I never make them sad, even when I am exhausted by starting up. Cam

Quynh believed that love is the most important thing that she could give to her parents as well as her husband, which is more meaningful than other material values.

I spend all the best on my family in terms of money, finance, and love because I think they need more love from me than anything else. Quynh

Tung's wife was the one co-founding with him, so he loved his wife dearest and never forgot the obligations of a husband.

I treasure her [wife] and love her unconditionally, who fought along by my side as my co-founder. Although I was busy with my start-up, I never forgot the responsibilities of a good husband, and I always remembered important days to give gifts and flowers to my wife. Tung

Besides love, satisfying family members' dreams and letting them do whatever they like in their life was also how Tra showed her love to her brother.

My brother is my family, so I wanted good things for him. He had helped me quite a few, so after two years, I invested in him and let him study abroad as he wished in MSc of Computing. At that time, I thought that he had helped me a lot, so if he comes back to Vietnam and wants to work for other companies or any business ideas he proposes, I still support him. But after coming back, he still wanted to help me, and he managed to build a very well-function software to support my business. Tra

Phuong's husband is also mentioned because he also took an important role in her start-up. Her husband is a foreigner; however, she overcame barriers of language and culture and understood her husband deeply to give him the best things in life. She also considered her husband a relationship in a network that needs building and taking care of.

I believe that even though he is my husband, I still have to treat him very well, especially he decided to leave the country for me. Many people think that your partner is yours

already, so that they can mistreat them without any consequences. Many people treat other people very well but do not do it with close family members. I always believe that every relationship needs to be built and reinforced all the time, or it will fade soon.

Phuong

Besides understanding, Phuong also gave surprises gifts and spent the time with her husband on important dates to rekindle the spark back in their marriage.

My husband is French, so he is pretty romantic. He always wanted me to balance work and life and spend time with him and our family besides my work. But you also know that it was challenging to keep that balance, and sometimes my jobs required me to travel. Therefore, I usually make up for him with surprises like gifts, holiday vouchers or dates on special occasions. We are also different from the other couple because he is French with western culture while I am an Eastern Asian lady, so we had to try our best to understand each other.

Phuong

Not everyone was smooth with the family network; Nha divorced her husband during the start-up because she was too busy working and could not manage to balance work and life. But she also learned from the experience and advised other entrepreneurs.

I focused so much on the business that I could not understand my husband's feelings, which gradually led to the break in my marriage. So, my advice was not to try to balance because you will not be able to do so if you decide to start up. Instead, you have to try to communicate, arrange your time more efficiently and spend some of your time with important family members. If you have the business success, but you don't have the one to share your happiness, which would be meaningless.

Nha

Co-founders (friends)

Besides spouse co-founders, some participants also selected friends and classmates as co-founders (Ha, Tra, Nha). The network is quite strong but not as strong as family or spouse co-founders.

Ha's cofounders were her classmates, and they had their own businesses. They let her decide everything on her own. Nevertheless, Ha always tried to involve them in the company activities

as much as possible by asking them ideas before making impact decisions. Besides, she also held parties to gather them up to boost morale.

They were parts of the company, and they were also shareholders. I always have meetings with them when I implement important programs or conferences so that they will join and commit. We also have parties and some offline meetings; however, the frequency is just 2-3 times per year because they are too busy. So most of the time, we had meetings online. Ha

In the case of **Tra**, all her co-founders were her friends, female and married. She understood the burdens and responsibilities that her co-founders had to suffer, especially in the culture of Vietnam. Therefore, she showed sympathy and gave better support to them.

My co-founders are all ladies. I know how difficult women, especially Vietnamese women, have to suffer because you know Vietnam culture is still under the influence of Confucius (from China). Vietnamese women have to take plenty of different roles in their marriage life. That is why I always sympathise with my two co-founders. They got married already at the time of starting up, so I always let them go home earlier so that they could take care of their family better. I, at that time, was still single, so I was willing to devote more time to the company. Besides, we also shared happiness, sorrow, and disappointment in life, which is why we have been together as colleagues and friends for such many years. Tra

Besides sharing the business's success, like Tra, Nha also understood the hardship of Vietnamese women, who were also her co-founders. Therefore, she shared the family burdens with them in many ways.

So, for co-founders, I share success, finance, affection, and stability with them after many years that they have contributed to my company. We help each other in terms of their family issues as well. I also pay attention to their problems in life, their parent, and their children and bring good care to all family members of my co-founders. Nha

4.8.1.2 PNM strategy for weak tie networks

If strong-tie networks are pretty stable and quite unlikely to change, then weak tie networks are not like that. Knowing the characteristics of the group, my participants showed the strategies that they used to maintain and develop the network. Weak-tie networks mentioned here comprised customers, staff, and university reps as well as partners.

Customers

As Quynh mentioned before, customers do not need the service of OER companies all the time because studying abroad consultancy service is not like a daily product that customers have to buy daily. Therefore, our participants always had after-sale cares to maintain the network.

We give commission, vouchers, and news on scholarships for old customers. Maybe they don't need it immediately, but they can introduce our service to their networks. We also have a marketing staff sending emails frequently. I only sent messages and texts only on especially occasions. Ha

Like Ha, Quynh prioritised old customers since she believed they would generate more value for her company.

As to old and current customers and their parents, I gave them more priority over others, such as scholarship information, phone calls, good services, commitment, and promises. Because in the sector, old customers will advertise our company more than new customers. Quynh

Being a young entrepreneur with young and dynamic staff in his company, Tung even supported his old customers regardless of time and considered them friends of his company.

As for customers, most of them were students and relatively young like my wife and me. Therefore, I always considered them friends, and we are companions on the path of their success. We took care of them even after they succeeded in studying abroad. My staff and I are all young, so we never hesitated to help our customers at any time, even outside the working time of our company, which was why we got love from our customers. Tung

Going further than **Quynh, Tung** and **Ha, Nha** even followed the success and achievements of her students studying abroad. Hence, she could connect well with many sides, such as educational institutions, students, and their parents.

With students, I keep following them during their study abroad journey. I posted their success on my Facebook, and I also take the role of the bridge between the uni/school and parents so that I can inform any problems to students' parents in time. If you go to my Facebook, you can see my students' achievements. Nha

Unlike other participants, **Phuong** cared for new customers from the beginning through the in-home overseas education consultancy service. Therefore, she could solidify the network from the beginning.

The way I maintained networks was different from other companies. My staff and I had always been willing to come directly to the house of students so that I could consult both parents, grandparents, and students. It was also the way to form a solid network thanks to face presence because trust is crucial in my country. Phuong

Not mentioning in detail, but **Cam** had a very good philosophy in dealing with customers and the customers' expectation solutions.

I always tried to exceed the expectation of customers a little so that they introduced newer customers to my company. Nevertheless, I did not try to satisfy my customers too much because my company won't be able to do it again, resulting in customers' disappointment. Cam

Staffs

Staff contribute considerably to entrepreneurs, especially at the beginning of starting up because they support those companies in terms of operational activities, the source of networking activities and advertisers for new customers, directly generating revenue. This is mentioned quite clearly in the last part about the multiplexity roles of staff. Hence, the proper strategy to retain staff is crucial in the entrepreneurial period.

A friendly and flexible environment is one of the keywords that my participants mentioned when discussing the strategy to keep talented staff for the company.

I was constantly building a comfortable environment. I didn't force staff to work like other office staff (starting at 8, leaving at 5); they even can work outside to consult students. Ha

I create a professional but comfortable working environment for staff to work. Tra

Specifically, **Tung** and **Phuong** mentioned leadership styles to retain staff effectively, which was encouraging and focusing on results instead of hard management.

I have always created an environment where I am a leader, not a manager. I didn't pressure them to get customers all the time but encouraged them and motivated them to achieve the objectives. Tung

My management style is MBO, meaning management by objectives. We set objectives together and achieved them together. We always discuss first before setting any objectives, and together we dealt with complex cases. I was fortunate that most of my staff were ones who studied and lived outside of Vietnam, so they worked very efficiently and effectively without many reminders. Phuong

In Oriental culture and Vietnam society, relationships are vital in networks; therefore, many participants such as Nha, Phuong, and Cam showed how they tighten the network with staff by creating a family working environment with fairness. Accordingly, besides jobs, difficulties in the personal life of staff and owners were also shared.

With my staff, they were not only the ones working for us, but we treated them like family members. I also had to ensure that our staff would be treated fairly in both branches. Because we have two main branches in Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh city, my co-founders and I took turns flying back and forth between Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh city to inspire staff. Nha

When my staff underperformed, I usually talked to them like family members to understand them. Maybe it was not about their capabilities but their personal life. So, I tried to create an open environment so that we could share anything which might hamper our performance. Phuong

I always tried to build good relationships as a family with my staff. I offered different benefits that I would give to them at different stages of their life, such as marriage, having babies or difficult times in life. Cam

And of course, besides creating a suitable environment for staff, decent salary, commissions, bonuses, foreign farm trips and other studying and training opportunities were benefits in the OER sector that my participant listed.

For staff who stayed longer with us, I gave them more opportunities to develop as well as money, health security, insurance etc. Quynh

We offered our staff with not only a competitive salary but also the opportunity to travel abroad to visit foreign universities to improve their abilities and knowledge. Nha

I gave good commissions to staff and paid fees for their training. Ha

I didn't mind sharing, training and facilitating them with knowledge and skills so that they could have enough tools to work effectively. Tung

I was always very generous with my staff, especially with the staff entering our company when we were new. Because they believed in us when we had nothing, the best thing should be given to them first. So, after two years of entering the company, I gave them the trips abroad. Cam

Like Quynh, Nha, Tung, Cam and Ha, Tra offered good salaries and other benefits to her staff. Besides, she also gave them opportunities to study with good scholarships that her partner rewarded her company. She also said she was willing to re-recruit them if they decide to work for her company again.

Good salary, bonuses, and commissions are essential to retain staff, and I don't mind sharing those. Regarding some staff members who would like to achieve their dream of studying abroad, I didn't keep them but gave them opportunities to access exclusive scholarships that foreign Uni awarded us. I also promised to recruit them again if they still want to work for us. Tra

University reps

There are quite a few partners supporting entrepreneurs in the OER sector. Still, the role of university reps was more multiplex than other partners, and the group was also mentioned more than others by my participants. Therefore, network strategy and tactics for maintaining the partnership network focused mainly on university reps.

The first thing that my entrepreneurs mentioned was the result, the number of good and genuine students converted to education institutions. It is the best way of maintaining relationships with them.

With University and reps, I always want to gain trust from them by sending good and quality students (who are genuine) by verifying students carefully. Besides getting the license for recruiting students, we were lucky to be authorised to conduct Pearson's PTE Test (English test). Our company also participates actively in their promotional activities in Vietnam. Nha

The universities I worked with needed the actual results and reputation, so I brought them the commitment, results, and dedication. Quynh

Like Nha and Quynh, to reach the target with universities and get good results, Ha built well marketing plans and focused on universities investing in her company more. She chose quality over quantity, as shared below.

Regarding my university partners, I am always active and professional. I always had clear marketing plans thorough the year and committed to the KPI with those universities. Coming to the documentation process, My team and I always did it correctly. So, they were happy working with me and maintaining the relationship with me. I also knew that the resources were limited, so I could not invest in all partners or

send students to all partners. Therefore, after year three, I tried to maintain essential networks rather than expand too much. Quality is still over quantity. Ha

Besides committing to the university in terms of results, being well-connected was also how my entrepreneurs ensured strong relationships. The proper connection was expressed in my participant's hospitality when uni reps paid visits to their company

Every time they came to our office, we invited them for dinner, and I also gave small tokens and gifts to them on special occasions. Tung

Regarding uni reps who have always supported me, my company and students, I usually prepared gifts or souvenirs every time they came to our office to train our staff. Tra

I treated them [uni rep] very generously with respect, and I told my staff to do the same. We invited them to dinner after the training whenever they came to our office. I also invited them to join our team-building activities. Phuong

In terms of uni reps, we really valued them, treated them with dinners every time they came to our company and sent them postcards on special occasions like Christmas, New Year, Lunar New Year etc. Nha

as well as online interactions periodically.

I kept in touch with them weekly by sending text messages and calls in terms of uni reps. Cam

Some years, I was so busy that I could not pay any visit to them, so I usually sent text messages/or wrote emails to keep in touch with them. Tra

As suggested by Tra, the online interactions were not very effective compared to traditional networking.

I treated the Vietnamese uni rep a little bit better, or to be exact; I had more time to pay attention to them rather than afar uni reps. Tra

At the highest level of connection, after some years of starting up, many entrepreneurs treated uni reps as colleagues, friends with whom they could share many things in business as well as in life.

We have always shared difficulties as well as happiness with them after a few years, so they know our company well like their company because we also considered them like colleagues. Tung

I even asked them (uni reps) to play sports with me when they have free time as friends. Cam

I even shared my big dream, vision, and mission with them [uni reps] so they could understand us better. They are partners, but I considered them colleagues. Phuong

The time I worked with uni reps made me know them better, and I always tried to treat them as friends, asked them for dinners or hung out with them. Quynh

In short, my entrepreneurs knew and understood very clearly their network, including strong-tie and weak-tie ones, so that they could prioritise and invest their time and efforts into critical networks effectively for the first stage of starting up.

4.8.2. Subtheme Two: Personal Network Multiplexity strategy in unprecedented period (Covid-19)

While the thesis was being completed, Covid-19 appeared and has changed how companies do their business. My participants' companies in the OER sector were not exceptions. Carol (2020) shed light on the study abroad plans of students during the covid 19 period in the following graph (**Figure 21**).

Figure 21: Study abroad plans of students considering COVID-19

Accordingly, in 2020, under the influence of Covid-19, only 13,5% decided to continue their studies, while the rest postponed, cancelled their studies or had no ideas about the next steps of their education. This also affected my participants, especially the entrepreneurs starting up in the period. However, in the limit of the dissertation, I could only ask one more question about the network strategy of those entrepreneurs during the period.

Application of online social platforms

The first and foremost strategy mentioned was taking advantage of technology and online social platforms.

We maintained the network with uni reps by keeping advertising their university. At the same time, we still supported our customers by offering them helpful information on the difficult period of studying abroad through email, phone calls and text. Likewise, we also connected closely with my staff through Facebook and other social media. Ha

Similarly, Cam also uses emails and texts to stay connected with his customers and students as well as staff.

We kept sending news and messages to our customers monthly so that they could update news about studying abroad and the effects of covid on international study. I also kept in touch with my staff frequently to ask them to work again when the time came. Cam

Quynh and **Nha** did not feel that working virtually was trouble because they had their own experience working like that.

To maintain relationships with other partners, oversea educational organisations, and students, we must master technology. We use virtual counselling methods to help customers, and we also use zoom and other online meeting tools (webinar, skype etc.) to update information and maintain relationships with partners. And you also know that in the sector, we had worked virtually before, so it was not really a problem with our company. Nha

Do you know that I have always had experience in controlling and directing my Vietnamese office from the UK? So, it is not a big problem for me to maintain networks during the period. I even believed that we didn't need to maintain an office to do my business in the future. Every day I had to attend 30 online meetings from Monday to Friday. Quynh

Accepting the vital role of online methods, however, Tra showed weaknesses in working online as well as the difficulty in converting customers.

The virtual network is the only way at the period for us to communicate with my networks. The problem here was mainly derived from staff and students. Staff tend to lose motivation and drive when it was challenging to recruit students, and it takes a long time to work at home. Regarding students and customers care, we still had to communicate and consult students online or organise events online. It was not as effective as offline meetings, but I believe it is common now and everyone in the sector has to adapt to this. Tra

Staff being made redundant and old customers cared - quality over quantity

During the Covid-19, staff were mentioned as the least important and easy to be made redundant, or more exact, most of my participants only kept the most talented and versatile staff. However, they still supported the previous staff to maintain the network.

I had to make redundant to some staff and retain only ten core staff. Cam

In terms of supporting staffs, who were not so important, we had to make redundant.

We still supported financially for them for some months while they couldn't find new jobs. Tra

For some core staff, especially salespeople, instead of making redundant, encouraging and motivating was how my participant used to retain talented staff and ensure the sale of their company.

My company and I tried to pay them a full salary for sales staff based on the target. I also increased virtual meetings to inspire them. Tra

It was hard for me to inspire my staff virtually, but I also tried to motivate them by paying in full and letting them choose any kind of work they felt comfortable with. Phuong

We also had a good policy for staff; for example, during the challenging three-month period of COVID working from home, I still paid our staff 100% salary, not like other companies, although our company faced plenty of difficulty during that time. Tung

As for customers, Phuong mentioned an interesting strategy, the 80/20 rule to ensure customer loyalty, while Ha emphasised the importance of dedication and student care for old customers.

We have fewer customers and students than before; instead, I focused more on old customers. I believe in the 80/20 rule in the business, saying that 80% of your profit comes from 20% of your repeated customers. One person might use our service one or two times; however, when we gain their trust, they will introduce more customers to us. Most of the time they were introduced, we converted them easier, and they soon became our new customers. Phuong

I also spent more relaxed time calling and texting old customers. Besides introducing a new service, I also wanted to be a bridge connecting uni, students, and parents effectively, so they can rest assured of their children's study abroad situation. I believe that my dedication and care will be the best way to retain old customers during the covid-19. Ha

Spending more time on self as well as important family and partners

Besides caring for the business, Covid-19 also helped my entrepreneurs step backwards to look back on the essential things and what they should do to develop stronger after the pandemic.

Covid-19 made people change much in terms of perspective. Health is the most important. I did everything online during the covid time. I could manage better with my network because I have more time to talk to them. Quynh

Since I started up, I did not spend enough meaningful time with my wife and my family, so Covid was the time I could make up for them. Cam

I did not have time with my husband before, but now it is time for me to heal my relationship, and we can support each other even more than before. Besides, I could save plenty of travelling time to my workplace so I can use the excessive time to talk to more partners worldwide even better than before. Phuong

Be prepared and positive

Last but not least, my participants showed me how they maintained their coolness and prepared for unprecedented events even before the Covid.

Covid affects all the sectors, and we are not an exception. However, we have been building our company for 20 years, and we always prepare for those incidents by having had a fund for risks. That is why I still could support our staff and my partners at the period. Nha

Cam also mentioned the fund he prepared to cope with the ever-changing business world.

Since I started having profit, I have always put away 10% funds for risk management because of the turbulence of the sector. Cam

Instead of avoiding the covid 19, Tung decided to start up during the Covid -19 period with a positive mindset that he could catch up better with other competitors in the market.

Covid dragged back many companies or made those companies downsize or even leave the market. So, I believed that starting up at the period would help us to reduce the gaps with other current companies. And I also thought that our company would start growing up when the market recovered. Therefore, I tried my best with my thought like that. Tung

In short, although there were obstacles and threats from the pandemic, my entrepreneurs managed to overcome the period with the application of technology, the focus on quality, the good preparation from the beginning, and most importantly, the calmness and positivity.

4.9. Summary of Findings

The purpose of the study was to explore how Vietnamese entrepreneurs utilised personal network multiplexity to develop their businesses. To do so, the questions about their dream jobs, ambitions, and passions were used to understand the nature of Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the sector. Accordingly, the goals of those participants were the desire to be meaningful to themselves, family and society as well as fulfilling their dreams when they were still young.

During the journey of starting up, those participants also expressed difficulties and challenges that they had to cope with, including lack of finance, skills, knowledge, networks and opportunities and even emotional comforts. Fortunately, they knew how to utilise their network multiplexity, including strong ties and weak ties relationships, to overcome these lacks.

With this help, the development of the companies in the sector was shown by attributes like revenue, online and offline interactions, numbers of customers, new networks, as well as other things such as the expansion of the company and number of staff.

Networks are not always permanent after the time of starting up; those entrepreneurs mentioned the changed networks and as well as unchanged ones. They also highlighted the change in roles and degrees of members in the network and how they dealt with the changes properly to keep maintaining their network effectively. Interestingly, some strong-tie networks still changed, and some weak-tie networks remained unchanged or just changed to some extent.

After that, lessons on effective networking multiplexity strategies with different groups were shared by my entrepreneurs. Accordingly, regarding strong-tie networks, entrepreneurs need to allocate the time and efforts similar to weak-ties networks and vice versa. Weak-tie networks need genuine care from entrepreneurs like strong-ties so that the networks can be tightened.

Last but not least, precious experiences with networking tactics during an unprecedented period like the Covid-19 pandemic were also mentioned. They are the master of online applications, the good preparation, and the positive attitudes of entrepreneurs.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSIONS AND ANALYSES

5.1. Overview

The study aimed to shed light on how Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector utilised personal network multiplexity to develop their start-up businesses. The findings in chapter 4 expressed quite clearly and meticulously the process. This chapter will consider the findings in relation to the study's aims and the research questions in the context of the broader literature. After that, recommendations and implications for relevant parties will be indicated. Last but not least, the chapter will end with the updated conceptual framework.

5.2. Implications of the findings for the research questions

Five research questions were given based on the literature before conducting participants' interviews. The findings extracted from their answers will reply to those questions as well as look back at the existing literature.

Q1. Who are actors with various roles in the network of entrepreneurs in the educational recruitment sector?

The finding showed that in the sector of OER, there were two groups of networks that have various types of roles contributing to the success of start-up firms, including weak ties and strong ties relationships. If strong ties networks included family members, such as children, spouses, parents, cousins, relatives, and friends, then weak ties involved the main partners of those companies in the sector such as customers and their parents, staff, and university representatives.

The finding matches Granovetter's (1973) and Naoko's (2012) research on network ties. However, the ties seem to be more complicated than that through the findings extracted. Accordingly, many networks might lie between strong and weak spectrum, such as not so close friends and acquaintances. Besides, strong and weak ties might lead to misunderstanding of the functional role of supporting business. Many existing studies mentioned the better role of strong ties in the beginning days and the better role of weak ties in the latter days of the business (Hu et al., 2019). However, the roles of ties in the sector are also more complicated than they seem to be based on different factors. For example, many of our participants agreed that weak ties networks would generate more new networks and customers than strong ties after some years of starting up. However, reputation and trust are critical in converting students; therefore, strong-tie networks will ensure that the conversion rates are better than weak ties in terms of company revenue and performance, as some participants mentioned.

Q2. What are multiple contents that entrepreneurs in educational recruitment sector and their network members exchange in the system?

The participants shared that they benefited tremendously from the assistance and support of their multiplexity networks. In terms of both strong-tie relationships (including children, spouse, classmates, relatives etc.) and weak tie relationships (uni rep, staff, customers), the entrepreneurs received more than one support from them.

The supporting contents include motivation, emotional support, capital, advice, trust, skills, experience, opportunity, new ideas and perceptions, endorsement, customers, revenue, profit, and new networks. An example of the multiple supporting contents is the case of Phuong. Her husband did not only motivate her and give her advice and networks, but he also directly joined in the process of marketing operation for her company. Even a weak tie network as a uni

representative also assisted Tung in many ways, such as giving him and staff training, advising him about starting up and motivating him to keep going.

Compared to the literature review, Naoko (2012) mentioned money transactions, shared knowledge, values, blood ties and emotional ties as the content that entrepreneurs might receive. Meanwhile, Gulati and colleagues (2000) indicated the opportunities like markets, information, and technologies as the source of support. Apart from that, Sabuhilaki (2016) highlighted new ideas, increasing motivation as necessary as other factors, while Arregle and colleagues (2013) involved the assistance of implementation and facilitation in job activities as one of the benefits of the entrepreneurial network. Carolis, Lisky and Eddleston (2009) mentioned new contacts, risk spreading, and legitimacy.

These points from the researchers were valid with what the participants spoke. Nevertheless, there were two assisting factors that no researchers mentioned as the benefit of entrepreneurial networking: reputation, trust, and new networks. In the context of Vietnam as an Oriental country, trust is also a kind of resource. Many networks did help my participants in terms of their reputation so that their customers believed more in the company. Besides that, new networks are also a vital source of support. Some researchers mentioned new contacts as the content of PNM (Carolis, Lisky and Eddleston, 2009). Nevertheless, my participants went further than that by pointing out the role of new contacts in introducing more new networks to develop their entrepreneurship.

Huggins and Thompson (2016) showed the importance of network multiplexity in innovating the start-up company; however, my participants did not mention it. The reason might be explained that the competition was not too harsh at the time of starting up, and the business model of companies in the sector did not need to change much; therefore, the participants cared for other factors rather than innovation at the first period of starting up.

Q3. What are the development attributes after the process of network multiplexity activities of Vietnamese entrepreneurship in the OER sector?

Findings from participants indicated that the dimensions or attributes of development of entrepreneurs in the OER sector were reflected by the increase of new networks and partners,

the rise of revenue and customers, the reputation measured by interactions online and offline and other growth such as the expansion of the branches or staff increase.

Considering the existing literature, the development attributes are usually based on sales growth, growth of employees, and growth of market share (Krega and Antoncic, 2016). The attributes correspond with the ones that the participants mentioned. However, in the sector, there were more factors contributing to the development of Vietnamese entrepreneurs. Sale growth was significant, but the number of customers was also vital. The high number of students will help the company maintain relationships better with institution partners, whereby the entrepreneurs might get more marketing support from the partners. Besides, more customers can create new networks for entrepreneurs in the sectors.

Also, in the OER sectors, earning new suppliers (university partners) was also as important as getting clients because the more education institution partners that entrepreneurs possess, the more options that their customers can choose, thus increasing the conversion rate of those clients. Apart from that, more educational partners also lead to more marketing support for entrepreneurs.

Another dimension of entrepreneurial growth indicated in the finding but not mentioned in the literature was reputation measured by online and offline interactions. In the technology era, the company that can utilise digital marketing better will have more opportunities to approach customers better. In the sector, offline marketing or simply word of mouth marketing still plays a vital role in doing business in Vietnam, especially in the sector requiring a tremendous amount of trust.

Of all factors mentioned in the literature about attributes of development, growth of market share was not mentioned in the finding because it was hard to identify the market share of the companies in the OER market, given that the business statistics of Vietnam were not well implemented.

Q4. How do the networks develop after the start-up period (dynamism of network multiplexity)?

In the literature, networks are seen as dynamic relationships and changing (Chell and Baines, 2000; Anderson and Jack, 2002; Jack et al., 2010). Based on the findings from the participants, the results are a bit more complicated than the general arguments about the dynamic factor of entrepreneurial networks. Network changes usually happen with weak ties, such as customers and staff, while strong-tie relationships such as family and friends were hardly changed. Granovetter (1985) mentioned need as the factor affecting the volatility of networks. Nevertheless, in the finding found from participants, some network ties such as family members still support the entrepreneurs emotionally and operationally regardless of whether their needs are not met. The opinion is also supported by Jack and his colleagues (2010). Accordingly, they argued that networks that only depend on resources are pretty narrow, but they are based on social factors, affinity, shared attitudes, and trust. This is quite true considering the Vietnamese context, where people put trust ahead of everything.

Although there were changes in the weak tie networks, participants still knew how to maintain them and turn the networks into new networks, such as leaving staff to become new customers or old customers to become staff members. On the other hand, the strong ties relationship might not be changed; however, the entrepreneurs mentioned the degree of change. An example is that an entrepreneur's husband joined in more company activities and supported her better than in the first days of the start-up. So, the degree of change is also worth noticing. Some researchers also mentioned the network changes (Johannisson, 1988; Jack et al., 2010), but not many mentioned the content of change, such as the change in roles and the change in degrees.

Soetanto (2019) was the one who explained the network changes very specifically with many factors (the strength of ties, the density of networks, and the size of the network). Nevertheless, the fact he posited that the number of contacts decreased after the market growth period is not valid in the case of the OER sector, where companies never stop finding new educational institutions to develop their market and they also never stop looking for new customer networks to bring more new customers to them.

Q5. What are personal network multiplexity strategies and recommendations for nascent entrepreneurs in the educational recruitment sector to grow their business?

Participants implemented distinct networking strategies for strong ties and weak ties networks. Strong ties of entrepreneurs mostly were family members and friends; therefore, they tried to

understand the ties by communicating effectively and were willing to sacrifice for them and love them unconditionally by spending the best things on them. Many participants shared that strong-tie networks also need taking care of and spending time on; if not, even strong ties could end up in breakups. Nevertheless, many strong ties networks were willing to sacrifice unconditionally before requiring reciprocity.

In terms of weak ties such as staff, customers, and uni representatives, my entrepreneurs considered them not only stakeholders bringing the benefit to the business but also friends. Therefore, they were willing to support the group in the way they treated friends. As for customers, they kept taking care of them even when their service had ended. Regarding staff, they did not only offer them fairly with a good salary, a comfortable working environment, the training and promotion activities but also treated them as family members by understanding their personal life and even helped their families when needed. For the uni reps, entrepreneurs were also very hospitable and offered gifts as well as dinners to them every time they came to the office. And gradually, the uni reps also became friends with those entrepreneurs. The tendency that weak ties became stronger and strong ties might be weaker was inevitable and depended on the time and efforts that entrepreneurs put in.

There was a little bit of contrast to the literature when Martinez and Aldrich (2011) mentioned that strong ties require high levels of reciprocity, meaning that entrepreneurs need to offer some kind of repayment, either economic or emotional or both, for the help that they receive. It might be true in the Western culture, but in Vietnam – an Oriental country, family members tend to sacrifice for each other such as wives are always willing to sacrifice their jobs to take care of the family, parents, sisters, or brothers are willing to help with low payments and anytime in a day to support entrepreneurs.

5.3 Implications of the findings and recommendations for entrepreneurs using personal network multiplexity in the OER sector

Based on the findings and the existing literature review, the recommendations for entrepreneurs using personal network multiplexity in the OER sector will be given under the PESTEL model. The advice given for the second E is Ethical instead of Environment because the environmental factor does not impact much on the OER industry.

Political factors

Political factors in the business context are about what degree and how government policy affects the economy (PA, 2021). In the sector of OER, the overseas factor is worth paying attention to as much as the political situation in the country because sending clients overseas to study requires working closely with both foreign partners and understanding the political situations of overseas countries.

Therefore, to ensure the sustainable development of the business in the sector, entrepreneurs should build network multiplexity with people who worked in the corresponding government departments, such as officials of the Ministry of Training and Education. The overseas education policies issued by the department will affect the business directly, so knowing those policies before others will help entrepreneurs prepare well for turbulences or take initiatives with opportunities. A good illustration is the case of Cam's company. He had worked in the Education Ministry before starting up, so he could take advantage of his prior networks to update his company on overseas education news fastest compared to other companies in the market.

Besides having a good relationship with the Ministry of Education, entrepreneurs doing business in Vietnam also need to pay attention to business obstacles regarding government-related activities such as business registration, licensing, and permit and relationships with public authorities (Maruichi and Abe, 2019). The best way to do this in Vietnam is to have a good network with people in the public sector in charge of the issues. An example of that is the case of Tung and Cam, they had difficulties in paying taxes in Vietnam, but after that, thanks to their network built with an official in the Tax department, the obstacle was cleared.

Related to the networks to help entrepreneurs update the political situation of the overseas countries or destination countries that then send students to, entrepreneurs should maintain good relationships and frequent communication with university reps based in those destination countries. Besides, if possible, it would be good if entrepreneurs could build and maintain networks with the Vietnamese Embassy in overseas countries to know the political situation better. An example of that is the case of Quynh. She established her entrepreneurial company in Vietnam, but she was based in the UK, so she made use of this to maintain networks with the UK embassy. It gave her plenty of important information on political issues.

Economic Factors

Economic factors have a meaningful impact on how entrepreneurs can make a profit (PA, 2021). Hence, the first piece of advice for entrepreneurs is that they should choose a suitable time for starting up. They should understand the country's economic situation before being in the sector because the business only succeeds when the people in the country are rich enough to send their children abroad to study. Therefore, to know the business situation, the good way is to create networks with economists or experts in the economic sector. The network with those people can help entrepreneurs make good entrepreneurial decisions and help them predict unstable economic situations in the future so that those entrepreneurs might decide to keep investing or stop.

For those entrepreneurial companies already starting up in the sector, they also should know the country's economic situation that they will send the students to because many students wish to study then settle in developed countries rather than developing countries or countries whose economic situation is in decline. The way to get the knowledge is by looking at economic growth indexes (GDP, GNP), exchange rates, inflation, and employment rate. Entrepreneurs can network with their students studying economics in those countries to be updated with important economic news.

Social Factors

Social-cultural factors involve the population's shared beliefs and attitudes (PA,2021). These factors will help entrepreneurs understand the stakeholders of the OER business more and behave appropriately to the social-cultural standards.

The factors were shown clearly in the networking strategies that entrepreneurs implemented with staff, customers, uni reps, and other stakeholders. The philosophy underlining the networking strategy of entrepreneurs is under the influence of Guanxi and Buddhism.

As mentioned before, guanxi means the total ties of entrepreneurs' interpersonal relations. Guanxi is also considered the bloodline of entrepreneurial success in Oriental countries like Vietnam and China, where networks are essential in doing business (Luo,2007). The most important point of guanxi is trust and obligations rather than just reciprocity (Chua et al.,2009). During the interview, entrepreneurs mentioned trust quite a lot when talking about their staff, customers, and especially in the business. One studying abroad trip can cost a customer a treasure. Therefore, the advice for entrepreneurs in the sector in Vietnam is to build networks

by trust or try to be friends first with your stakeholders, turn weak ties relations into stronger ones by spending more time, and efforts on them.

Based on the recommendation and experiences of entrepreneurs, Buddhism's philosophy should be adopted if new entrepreneurs want to sustain their networks. Nowadays, it is not merely a religion but a way of doing successful business. Accordingly, The Buddha teaches people compassion for themselves and those around them, taking care of themselves physically and mentally (Miththapala, 2018). Many entrepreneurs in the OER sector also practised the philosophy in the way they treated their stakeholders in their business network. An example is that some entrepreneurs were always giving first and more than they can receive when dealing with their staff. In terms of customers, they treated them like their children so that they could support them as much as a father or mother can do. They also believed deeply in cause and effect, a core philosophy of Buddhism, by doing their best and bringing the best benefits to their stakeholders before thinking about receiving back. When there were changes in their network, they acknowledged the impermanence and were still full of positivity. Many new entrepreneurs might not believe in Buddhism; however, these recommendations are precious and worth considering for sustainable networks.

In social factors, gender is also an important topic worth mentioning. Of all participants studied, over 70% are women entrepreneurs in the OER sector. ILO (2007) also indicated that female owners in education-related services made up 56% of their male counterparts. Meanwhile, the proportion of women-owned enterprises in Vietnam constituted 22% compared to the men counterpart (IFC, 2017). The less favourable role of women in Vietnam entrepreneurship illustrated by the female/ male entrepreneurs' ratio is inversely proportional to the women entrepreneurs compared to males in OER and the education sector in general. This combines with constraints that Vietnamese women have to suffer compared to men, including access to finance, knowledge skills, family responsibility, and weakness in networking (ILO, 2007; VBCWE, 2021). So, the advice here is that women entrepreneurs should not wait for a better business environment, but be more confident to access resources, raise their voices louder, and unite with other women entrepreneurs to ask for equality in business policies.

Besides guanxi and Buddhism, gender equality in business, knowing the social-cultural factors in the foreign countries that students will be sent to is also paramount to the business's success.

The knowledge will help entrepreneurs work better with foreign partners and help maintain their relationship better with them.

Technological factors

Technology has changed tremendously how companies do business. As for the OER sector, the role of technology, or the internet, is highly significant. One of the essential characteristics of the job is working with foreign partners; therefore, without online internet and online platforms, most operational activities with foreign partners cannot be implemented, which might affect the networking activities with them too.

Besides working online with foreign partners, technology has changed how OER entrepreneurs target potential customers. In the thesis, many entrepreneurs recently started using digital marketing tools to approach customers much more than before. Apart from that, the process of supporting customers' applications can be completed from a distance, reducing the obstacles of location as well as other expenses.

Another application of technology is changing the way of operation in the company. Many entrepreneurs in the OER sector mentioned that they created a flexible working environment for staff because they could use technology or software to manage staff's job effectiveness and efficiency. During the covid-19, all businesses had to use online platforms; therefore, having good technological knowledge would be advantageous for those entrepreneurial companies.

With the vital role of technological factors, new entrepreneurs should utilise technology effectively by networking skills to connect with tech companies and ask for their service. There might be costly but worth investing in because technology will sooner gain competitive advantages over their competitors. Besides, they should recruit and connect with tech-savvy staff or at least have their staff trained with courses about using technology.

Legal factors

PA (2021) explains legal factors as issues of advertising standards, consumer rights and laws and other things that entrepreneurs must comply with. In the case of OER companies,

entrepreneurs need to follow the law of the country they are based in and the countries they send their students or customers to.

In the country where entrepreneurs are based, they must know precisely what kind of the law that they have to follow, such as labour law (to ensure the rights of staff), business law (to ensure the government obligations) and customer laws (through contracts) and other laws.

When the entrepreneurs send their customers abroad to study, they also must know immigration law and visa procedures to consult students properly and legally and ensure the student can enter the country of study and study and live safely and legally there.

To comply with the law strictly and legally, entrepreneurs should seek help from networking with experts in the law sector like the example of Tung's company. He used to study at Law university before starting up; therefore, he had many good networks with lawyers or law professors, which helped him tremendously with things related to law issues.

To understand the law of foreign countries that entrepreneurs send students to, they need to understand visa procedures and immigration law themselves and get someone to be in charge of the visa supporting position, so they can update any news on the rules to ensure the company always complies to the law. Besides, entrepreneurs again need to have good relationships with the Vietnamese embassy because they will have the most up-to-date information on visa procedures and other country situations that entrepreneurs can be updated on.

Ethical Factors

Ethical factors involve ethical principles and problems arising in the business (PA,2021). In the study, not many entrepreneurs in the OER sector mentioned the factors. However, when deciding to start up, most of them prioritised their passion for helping Vietnamese students achieve their studying abroad dreams so that the students can come back again to contribute to the country over the profit, power, or other material achievements.

In the sector, it was shared that there are many opportunities that entrepreneurs in the sector could charge any expensive fee to the students for visa services. However, it depends on entrepreneurs' morality and the wish to network with them again. My advice is to charge a reasonable fee to keep the network is better than over-charge.

Another ethical issue mentioned in the interview with participants is the genuine students sent to partner universities. This is important because there are always students who do not want to study properly. They want to exploit the visa for other purposes, which will affect the reputation of the university partner. The worst consequence is that their right to recruit international students will be revoked. Many entrepreneurs will carefully select genuine students for university partners, but some companies also care only about profit and reaching the target. So, the advice here is to check students' backgrounds carefully and work transparently with foreign partners. Entrepreneurs can earn money more in the future, but there will be nothing if they lose their reputation and trust.

The most important advice learned from the participants' stories is to be kind and transparent and try to apply Buddhism philosophy in doing business: always thinking about others before thinking about yourself. Committing to ethical factors might not lead to the success of your business in terms of profit or material benefits right away. Still, it will ensure the company's sustainability in the long run.

5.4. Updated conceptual framework

Before mentioning the study's contribution, the conceptual framework will be revised as follows. Accordingly, the Total Early Stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) period has been the same, and the context is unchanged. Only one factor in the context, the Buddhism philosophy mentioned by many participants, has been put under the *guanxi* (the Oriental business culture). The dimensions of personal network multiplexity are also shortened based on the findings from participants. So, the role of PNM is classified into strong ties and weak ties with multiple supports (business supports and mental supports). In the updated model, evolved PNM is also mentioned by changed and unchanged relationships. In the dimensions of development in the OER sector of entrepreneurs, many indicators have been pointed out, including the number of students recruited, number of partners, reputation measured by online and offline interactions, and staff growth. Finally, recommendations on PNM strategy will be given based on the standard basis and unprecedented events rather than general advice from the previous framework.

Total Early Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA)

- Entrepreneurship <3.5 years

How is PNM evolved after a period (3.5 years)???

(Dynamism of personal network multiplexity)

- Changed relationships
- Unchanged relationships

BUSINESS GROWTH

- | | | | |
|--|--------------------------------|--|------------------------|
| Numbers of students recruited) and revenue | Staff growth, branch expansion | Reputation by interactions (online, offline) | Number of new partners |
|--|--------------------------------|--|------------------------|

RECOMMENDATION/ STRATEGY

- Standard strategy:
- Strong ties: Treat as weak ties (Have caring plans and spend the time)
 - Weak ties: Treat as the strong ties (like family and friends)
 - Unprecedented event: master online application, funds and positive attitudes

Figure 22: Updated conceptual framework

CHAPTER 6. CONCLUSION

6.1. Theoretical Implications

There were quite a few studies about entrepreneurship, but it is the first time individual entrepreneurs in the OER sector to be set as the main object of research. Normally entrepreneurs will be seen as the entity, but my thesis explored the level of individuality to understand them. Similarly, although there has been a strong increase in the number of international students and universities using educational agents, little research has been done to understand the relationship between parties (Thomson et al., 2013), and hardly can be seen that overseas education consultant agencies are the main objects for research as explained in the academic gap. That is why the findings of the thesis helped fill the gap in the knowledge about the selection of these objects.

That selecting individual entrepreneurs to research also furthers exploring their desire, wishes, and ambitions behind all the entrepreneurial activities. These have been unfolded in the first finding part about the passion of entrepreneurs. Thus, we knew about the motivation and aim behind all entrepreneurial activities, which are meaningful to themselves, family members, and society, as well as fulfilling their dreams when they were still young. The knowledge is meaningful for readers and practitioners to have what kind of passion and motivation to be successful in the OER sector in the long run.

The second gap that the findings helped to fill in is the details of personal network multiplexity of OER entrepreneurs presented in a qualitative method in the nascent period of entrepreneurship. As mentioned earlier, there were some studies about PNM, but they did not research entrepreneurs or businesses during the first period of startup (Ferriani and colleagues, 2012); thus, it was difficult to highlight the critical roles of PNM. Broad (2012) studied individual businesspeople, but he just studied at the single level of network instead of multiplexity. Bliemel and colleagues (2014) and Bratkovič Kregar and Antončič (2016) proved the positive relationships between PNM and firm growth; however, they did not use the qualitative method to understand what stories behind the networking activities of entrepreneurs. In the thesis, the findings indicated specifically the relationships and their role in helping entrepreneurs function in their businesses. Accordingly, weak-ties and strong-ties are the ones mentioned. In fact, the introduction of weak and strong ties is not new and mentioned in the extant literature of networking (Granovetter, 1973; 1983; Naoko, 2012). Nevertheless, the finding went further by

showing specific network contacts in the context of Vietnam- a high collectivism country as well as in the particular OER sector.

In turn, besides parents, children, spouses, siblings, cousins, close friends then, teachers, professors, family-in-law members, ex-colleagues are also strong-tie networks, contributing considerably to the development of companies. In a high collectivism index country like Vietnam, strong networks are not only between parents, spouses, siblings, and children but are also extended to others. Also in the finding, the content of the support is also more diverse and unconditional in some groups. They are not only knowledge, skills, finance, and new networks but also trust, motivation, and emotional support, which were not mentioned carefully in extant literature.

Regarding weak-tie relationships of entrepreneurs in the OER sector, staff, customers, and uni reps were ones supporting the entrepreneurial activities of participants. If staff and customers are popular and considered stakeholders supporting companies by many theories in the literature, then uni reps are new findings in the OER sector that contributed impactfully to the success of new entrepreneurs. According to the finding, uni reps did not only provide knowledge, skills, opportunities in the sector, but they were also companions going further to assist in operations such as training staff, giving business advice, or even consulted clients for entrepreneurs.

The third theoretical implication is found in the finding is the real stories about the dynamism/ evolution of personal network multiplexity after the entrepreneurial period. The concepts have been mentioned since Grannovetter (1983), then some reasons for changes were given (Jack et al., 2010; Rosenblatt, 2018). Soetanto (2019) also explained very carefully the network changes in three dimensions, including the strength of ties, the density of networks and the size of networks. However, the finding approached the change in the context of the OER sector as well as the Vietnamese culture and found out that at the initial resource gathering period, weak ties are also important like strong ties.

After 3.5 years, there have been changes in networks, but also network contacts remain unchanged. Interestingly, there were some weak-tie relationships that did not change and even became stronger; meanwhile, there were very close relationships (husband-wife) who got divorced when starting up. Soetanto (2019) mentioned that the number of contacts would

decrease when the market grows; however, findings showed otherwise that the number of partners and clients kept increasing in the OER sector. The reason was that entrepreneurs in the sector had to keep looking for new partners to provide more options for clients.

The fourth theoretical implication of the finding is the networking strategies of entrepreneurs in the OER sector in unprecedented events such as Covid-19. The appearance of Covid leads to a big gap in the literature about networking activities during the pandemic. Thus, the findings helped to contribute to the theory in terms of contingency plans and methods of entrepreneurs in the OER sector coping with the pandemic. Specifically, the application of online platforms, emotional health preparation, and good network managements are solutions suggested by the findings.

Discussion of the generalisability

Although the study is carried out in one country (Vietnam) and participants represents one country, it is still valid for some results to be generalised to other countries, cultures, contexts, and sectors.

Accordingly, when mentioning the strong and weak tie relationships of Vietnamese entrepreneurs, the way they networked was also affected by the culture and collectivism of Vietnamese people. According to Hofstede (2021), Vietnam scores 20/100 in terms of individualism. This reflects the high collectivism, which also explains well the situation that Vietnamese entrepreneurs received plenty of support coming from extended family members as well as relatives and other networks. The fact might be generalised to some countries with low individualism, such as East Asia (China, Japan, Korea...), East Africa (Kenya, Tanzania...), or South East Asia (Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia...)

Besides countries, the PNM strategies of entrepreneurs drawn from findings can benefit nearly all sectors, especially sectors involving international factors such as import-export companies, tourism, or education. Entrepreneurs in the mentioned sectors can learn from the experience of entrepreneurs in the OER sector in the thesis to develop their own personal network multiplexity strategies. As mentioned in the findings, the strategies were employed with both strong-tie networks (Understanding, Communication, Sacrificing, and Unconditional Love) and weak-tie networks (Treating them as strong-tie, fairness, and dedication)

Finally, as mentioned, the PNM strategies of entrepreneurs in the Covid period can be applied to other unprecedented periods such as economic, political crisis, pandemics, wars, lockdowns, and restrictions where the number of clients will be dramatically reduced. Therefore, some suggestions from the findings can be applied to maintain personal networks effectively for entrepreneurs, especially the ones in the sector involving international factors, which are the application of online platforms, emotional health preparation, and good network management.

6.2 Contribution of the study

This study has proved that personal network multiplexity affected the development of entrepreneurs positively at the beginning of start-up, which is consistent with the arguments of Lee and Tsang (2001), Shipilov (2012), and Bliemel(2014) and Engel (2016). Expressly, all seven participants agreed that PNM contributed from 60% to 80% to the success of their entrepreneurship in the OER sector. Furthermore, they extended the deeper content on how PNM helped them at the entrepreneurial stage. So, **the first contribution of the study is the more profound qualitative method used to understand how PNM and entrepreneurial development related to each other.**

Specifically, PNM from strong-tie relationships (family members, friends) and weak-tie relationships (staffs, customers, uni reps) contributed considerably to the entrepreneurs in the sector, including business support (motivation, capital, advice, trust, skills, experience, opportunity, new ideas and perceptions, endorsement, customers etc.) as well as emotional supports at the TEA period of entrepreneurship. Many prior researchers who studied the role of entrepreneurial networks mentioned these supports. However, not many discussed the complexity and multiplexity feature of personal network entrepreneurial support in detail.

Accordingly, family members and friends (strong ties) actively participated in the entrepreneurial process in the sector by playing many roles such as experts, co-founders, staff, investors, and inspirers to give funds, capital support, knowledge, skills and emotional support. Meanwhile, staff and customers also supported my entrepreneurial participants in multiple roles, although being weak ties in their relationships with entrepreneurs. Those supports

included knowledge, skills, new ideas and perceptions, endorsement revenue, profit, reputation and new networks.

One exciting discovery the thesis mentioned is the role of uni reps (weak-tie). Although they are just the staff of educational institutions (partners), they contributed tremendously to the success of the entrepreneurs mentioned above by giving their knowledge, skills, experience and even opportunities (exclusive scholarship, information, bonuses).

The thesis also indicated that the border between the supports mentioned was unclear. Each entrepreneur received different sources of support from different people; therefore, there are no typical successful recipes for entrepreneurs in selecting personal networks but based on the existing human resources they have.

The choice of topic” entrepreneurs in overseas educational recruitment sector” is the second contribution of the study because hardly any articles were found or any study researched deeply on the topic. The network multiplexity in the sector is quite interesting and complicated because the networks require relationships inside the country and transnationally. Besides, the study also shows who were in PNM of entrepreneurs in the sectors and to what extent they did to support the development of those entrepreneurs. Accordingly, the study can potentially impact on companies who plan to work with foreign partners.

Accordingly, the findings indicated that the role of international educational institutions was reflected by the uni reps, who represented the educational partner's image, reputation, and support to entrepreneurs. The uni reps were also classified into local Vietnamese uni reps and uni reps in the destination countries. Of these two, my participants appreciated the local uni reps more because entrepreneurs can approach those reps more accessibly without any physical restraints like reps from afar. Nevertheless, those who got both offices in local and destination countries can network with both of their resources to maximise the support from educational institution partners, as in the case of Quynh.

The third contribution is that although this study is not a longitudinal study, participants were asked to recall their experiences when they started up. Therefore, the PNM of

entrepreneurs in the sectors could be seen as a dynamic factor rather than a static movement, whereby entrepreneurs or business strategists could implement suitable tactics for the changes in PNM for the better growth of their business. The evolution of the business network theory is also mentioned in the literature (Jack et al., 2010; Rosenblatt, 2018). Nevertheless, they mentioned the reasons for changes rather than explaining the actual changes in business networks and the complex changes in degree and roles found in the study.

Accordingly, the personal networks of the aforementioned entrepreneurs are seen as dynamic regardless of strong-tie or weak-tie networks, although the latter tend to change more. The finding also indicated that strong-tie networks, regardless of stability, still changed, such as the husband-and-wife relationship. On the contrary, although weak, weak-tie networks only changed their roles, they still stayed with the entrepreneurs. Therefore, entrepreneurs need appropriate personal networking strategies to positively maintain or develop the PNM. The finding and the analysis will contribute to new entrepreneurs when seeing the change in personal networks. The process is dynamic and inevitable; therefore, new entrepreneurs should accept the fact and devise strategies to adapt to those changes.

The fourth contribution is the recommendations for entrepreneurs in the OER sector on PNM. The advice was not general but specific, based on different types of networks (strong tie, weak tie, in-country or transnationally). The advice given was also based on the findings as well as the theory of resources-based views and the changing nature of the network (Jack et al., 2010). Accordingly, entrepreneurs should treat strong ties (family, spouse, friends) as weak ties by allocating their time appropriately and fairly. On the other hand, weak ties should be treated like strong ties by caring, respecting, and loving in the same way so that the weak ties will soon become strong and contribute tremendously to the success of the business.

Specifically, as shared by many participants, unconditional love was not enough to strong ties (family members) if those entrepreneurs only talked but did not do anything. Some entrepreneurs had to trade off the business success with personal happiness because they spent too much time on their careers but neglected their marriage obligations. Therefore, allocating time appropriately or balancing work-life is paramount. If it is still difficult, then involving the spousal participant is also a feasible option, like in the case of Phuong and her husband.

Regarding weak ties, many entrepreneurs knew how to maintain and develop the networks by treating them as family members (strong ties). This way will help these networks become less transactional but more sincere; therefore, it will be more effective in the current society where soft powers are dominantly present and in the context of Oriental culture like Vietnam. Expressively, Cam mentioned the life-support scheme for his staff; in turn, he will support the staff differently at each stage, such as being single, married, having babies etc. or in some special stages of their life. Meanwhile, Quynh based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs to support her staff.

Many other participants applied Buddhism Philosophy in personal networking with every stakeholder in their companies regardless of whether they are strong ties or weak ties. Accordingly, they were willing to give first and take later. They also gave those stakeholders more than they received back from them.

Those personal networking strategies are considered contributions because they were proven successful and beneficial to the business growth. New entrepreneurs in the sector as well as in other sectors, can learn from the strategies to develop their personal network multiplexity for their own development.

Considering the change and unprecedented events, the Covid-19 pandemic also asked about strategies that entrepreneurs adopted to maintain and develop PNM. In turn, entrepreneurs must always prepare for the worst by having funds to support their companies and the stakeholders. Besides, they should have a positive attitude and use the challenging times to reinforce their relationship with their loved ones and maintain the current stakeholders' networks. Finally, it is advisable that entrepreneurs master technology and online applications to connect with stakeholders anywhere and anytime.

Besides general advice, the recommendations for entrepreneurs regarding PNM strategy when entering the sector were put in the PESTEL factors, including political, economic, social, technological, ethical and legal factors as the explanations in the previous parts. Thanks to these recommendations, new entrepreneurs will know who and how to connect with crucial people to develop their personal networks, which will benefit their future entrepreneurial success.

The fifth contribution is the advice for international educational institutions. Besides the contributions to new entrepreneurs based on successful entrepreneurs' stories, experiences, and advice, international educational institutions also benefit from the perspective. After reading this, they will know more about the entrepreneurial networks of their agencies working with them, and they will also know how to develop the relationship with those companies effectively. Accordingly, when an international educational institution wants to enter the Vietnamese market, the first thing is to find a local uni rep. The uni rep will be the bridge representing the institution's image to their agencies. Furthermore, they can convey the institutions' updates in Vietnamese and also solve the time zone issue of international institutions. The more acquainted the uni rep is with agencies, the better that institution can market and convert students in Vietnam.

In addition, international educational institutions should invest their time visiting those companies directly in Vietnam now and then to reinforce their personal network. Vietnamese people love foreigners (Pike, 2018), and they also prefer meeting directly to online interactions. Besides business support, Vietnamese agencies also appreciate emotional support; therefore, apart from financial benefit or transactional relationships, encouragement, recognition, awards, and comfort are also crucial.

The choice of a context for the study is the sixth contribution. Vietnam, a country heavily influenced by Oriental culture, was chosen for research. Due to being an Oriental country, the role of networks in business is even more critical and survival than in Western business culture, as mentioned before (Guo and Miller, 2010; Chi and Seock-Jin, 2017). The PNM of entrepreneurs in the sector, mentioned in the study under the social factor of guanxi and philosophy of Buddhism, will contribute to the understanding of Vietnamese business networking culture in general, which will benefit both new enterprises as well as outsiders from Western who would like to set up business in Vietnam as well as other Oriental countries.

Accordingly, guanxi is needed to learn first to do business and create personal networks in Vietnam. Unlike western business culture with formal meetings, in Vietnam, personal meetings, dinners or casual hangouts are more appreciated to create personal network with Vietnamese partners. International enterprises who would like to do their first business in Vietnam can take advantage of personal network multiplexity to receive multiple support from a small number of stakeholders at the entrepreneurial stage. Besides guanxi, when they create

a personal network, they can not only implement a win-win situation but also need to give first and take later or even receive less and give more (Buddhism philosophy) if they want to maintain and develop personal networks effectively in Vietnam.

6.3. Limitations of the study and future research

As mentioned in the methodology part, the first limitation is applying the case study approach in the qualitative method, which is hard to tell that the outcomes are valid for all entrepreneurs in the OER sector. Moreover, the nature of the qualitative method also depends on the interpretation skill of researchers, so the bias in the interpretation process is unavoidable (Mackieson et al., 2018). Also, the translation process from Vietnamese to English might not be smooth in some answers due to the language barriers regardless of the enormous efforts in the researcher's process. Another limitation in terms of research method is related to the Covid-19. The pandemic prevented the researcher from coming back to the country to have face-to-face interviews, affecting the rapport between researchers and participants and resulting in difficulties in arranging meetings and follow-up sessions. Hence, it would be better if the following researchers could use mixed methods to clearly understand the relationship between each tie of personal network multiplexity to the success factor of entrepreneurs in the OER sector instead of only using the qualitative method in my thesis. Besides, it would be more convincing if those researchers could have face to face interviews with participants.

Also, regarding the methodology, due to the short time of the DBA course, it was hard to study entrepreneurs during the entire TEA process (the first 3.5 years), so the researcher had to use cross-sectional data at the time of research even though plenty of data was retrieved from the memory of entrepreneurs. Therefore, proper longitudinal research such as the ethnography approach should be employed in the future so that researchers can follow and track all network ties of entrepreneurs and the dynamism of the network.

The third limitation is that the study was only proposed in the context of Vietnam, where the business and social environment are quite distinctive compared to other countries and cultures. Moreover, it was also hard to get financial reports or important data from entrepreneurial

companies in Vietnam. Therefore, the new personal network multiplexity of entrepreneurs' studies on various cultures and countries is fascinating to discover.

The entrepreneurial companies researched only in the OER sector are also seen as limited situations and do not represent all entrepreneurial companies' networking activities in Vietnam. Therefore, it still has room for further research on the personal networking activities of entrepreneurs in the different sectors in Vietnam.

Entrepreneurs are the only research target in the thesis, while many other actors in the entrepreneurial network can play as main roles in the OER sector in further studies, including the overseas educational institutions, staff, clients, and government. Overseas educational institutions can be researched in networking multiplexity with stakeholders to develop their market internationally. Meanwhile, staff in the OER sector can be studied in employability opportunities with network multiplexity. The fact that network multiplexity can also help clients find suitable overseas study options might be another new topic for future research. And government or VCCI (Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry) can be the research target on strategies to connect entrepreneurs with potential partners.

The focus of the thesis is on the personal network level of only entrepreneurs, while there are still more room for studies on the relationship between organisations level as the research of HÖLSCHER (2019). Or even the personal networks of staff and other stakeholders in the entrepreneurial companies also benefit their survivability at the beginning of entrepreneurship, which is also worth noticing for subsequent studies.

The study was implemented during the entrepreneurs' TEA period (during 3.5 years of entrepreneurship). However, the role of personal network multiplexity can be beneficial for many years after. So, the research on the latter stage of entrepreneurs might also be interesting to see how PNM develops, transforms, and evolves.

Guanxi and Buddhism philosophy in Oriental business culture are also worth mentioning for further and deeper research. They are considered the fundamental base for successful long-term networks and the success of entrepreneurs in the long run.

As mentioned, in the education sector, women entrepreneurship dominated the market more than the male counterpart. However, they have not been treated fairly regarding family responsibility and the underestimation of women's abilities in Oriental society. Therefore, more profound research needs to be implemented on women's entrepreneurship as well as their networkability in the OER sector, where many female entrepreneurs shone and succeeded.

The pandemic Covid-19 took place has totally changed the way of doing business, especially in the OER sector. Of all the participants interviewed, only two agencies were starting up in the period. Therefore, it might be fascinating to study further the ability of OER entrepreneurs in PNM to survive their business under the pandemics (like Covid-19) or other unprecedented events like wars and economic crises.

6.4. Self-reflexivity

My personal and professional interests influenced the choice of the topic as well as the research question. In the aspect of personal interest, I am an open-minded and friendly individual. I have always loved connecting with people and wanted to create an extensive network so that people in the network can help each other in every aspect of life because I always believe that one individual in society cannot do anything without support from others. In Oriental culture, networking is even more critical and complicated in collectivist countries like Vietnam and contributes to any individual's success in society. The passion for being connected and connecting people inspired me to research more deeply on ties and the multiplexity of ties in networks.

In terms of my profession, I have worked as an overseas educational consultant since 2013, after my bachelor's graduation. Starting this career was the key to opening many opportunities for my development later. Besides helping others fulfil their dreams of studying abroad, I was also able to find the chance for myself. Specifically, the networking process when I worked in an overseas educational recruitment company benefited me with a 50% scholarship for a Master course in the UK, whereby I could achieve my dream of overseas study. When I got a placement year in the UK, I decided to work in the OER sector again for another company based in London. Working in both companies during their entrepreneurial period led to my understanding of the challenges and difficulties they had to face and the vital role of networking activities they implemented to navigate their small boats to success. Realising the important

role of networks in the success of entrepreneurs, I decided to stop working and pursue the DBA course to equip myself better with knowledge, skills about entrepreneurial network activities as well as to prepare myself with business models for my ultimate purpose of starting up my own business in the OER sector in the future.

My status as an overseas educational consultant was fortunate that I could find interviewees with few efforts, thanks to my networks in the sector. However, business secrets are critical, so I did not expect to have very detailed answers from participants. Besides, the pandemic which prevented me from flying back to my country made me difficult to access and interview my participants properly and face to face. Sometimes, it was annoying when I could not arrange the time with participants because they were too busy with their business.

Supervision has also been significant because I did not have a very good experience with the former supervisor before. I lost more than six months without any progress because of the miscommunication between the two sides and my lack of research experience. Luckily, I was appointed with another supervisor who has always been encouraging, inspiring to keep up with what I have been doing and caring for my emotional health, especially when I got Covid-19.

In terms of the research process, it was hard for me to write concise literature that can condense out the theory of entrepreneurship, social network, and network multiplexity, which are all broad and numerous. Therefore, I had to choose the most relevant theories to put into the section. The research methodology is also challenging given that the participants are all entrepreneurs and now CEOs. They were all busy, and hard to have free time for sharing. Therefore, I had to use the snowball sampling method and my networks to connect with them. Finally, I stand in the position of an educational consultant but not an entrepreneur, so in the process of interpreting, I might use my perspectives more to interpret than the participant's viewpoints, which can lead to subjectivity and may not have reflected fully what those entrepreneurs intended as I mentioned in the limitations. Nevertheless, I believe that my efforts in the thesis will be recognised. I also hope that the findings and the analysis would benefit both academia and entrepreneurs in the overseas educational recruitment sector, which will help my DBA research become relevant when contributing to academia and industry.

6.5. Summary

There have been myriad theories about social networks in entrepreneurs and the role of personal network multiplexity in the development of entrepreneurs. Nevertheless, not so many qualitative studies were adopted to understand the role of personal network multiplexity in the entrepreneurial stages. The purpose of the study was to explore how Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector utilised personal network multiplexity to develop their businesses. This might benefit future entrepreneurs in understanding the challenges of the entrepreneurial process and the application of using the PNM strategy in developing their business, given that 90% of Vietnamese entrepreneurs failed.

The finding revealed that OER Vietnamese entrepreneurship is formed from passions for education, business, and the desire to contribute to Vietnam society by sending students abroad to study. However, the entrepreneurial process was hardship and full of challenges and obstacles. Fortunately, personal network multiplexity was the saviour for those young entrepreneurs. The personal network of Vietnamese entrepreneurs in the OER sector includes strong ties (family members, spouses, and friends) and weak ties (customers, staff, university representatives). The multiple roles of stakeholders were the primary sources of multiple support (motivation, emotional support, capital, advice, trust, skills, experience, opportunity, new ideas and perceptions, endorsement, customers, revenue, profit, and new networks) to the entrepreneurial companies' growth, resulting in revenue, increased customers and partners, brand reputation by increased online and offline interactions etc.

Findings also indicated that the entrepreneurial personal network is a dynamic factor where the role of actors in the network will change or not change after a period with certain degrees. However, suppose personal network multiplexity strategies are properly and flexibly implemented on different ties. In that case, entrepreneurs can maintain and develop their networks effectively for their growth in the long run.

The study provides a foundation for further studies on the network of entrepreneurs in the OER sectors because the sector requires local networks and relationships with international partners. Besides, the study was put in the context of Vietnam with distinctive social, economic, and cultural backgrounds, so it would be interesting if the topic could be extended to other contexts and other sectors. Gender is also worth noticing in the education sector, where women

exceeded men in the head positions of entrepreneurship. Therefore, further research can be implemented to understand more about the personal network multiplexity of women in the sectors related to education.

Researching on networks and their complexity, such as personal network multiplexity, is never outdated because of their important roles in society. Individual power can never be compared to collective strengths, which is especially true for entrepreneurs who need to capture all types of resources for their survival and development. Further research and interest in networks and entrepreneurship, especially in developing countries, will continue contributing to the success of entrepreneurial individuals and the development of the nation.

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APPENDIX A: PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

NAME OF PARTICIPANT:

Title of the project: An Exploration of HOW VIETNAMESE OVERSEAS EDUCATIONAL ENTREPRENEURS UTILISE PERSONAL NETWORK MULTIPLEXITY TO DEVELOP THEIR COMPANIES

Main investigators and contact details:

1. I agree to take part in the above research. I have read the attached Participant Information Sheet for the study. I understand what my role will be in this research, and all my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
2. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the research at any time, without giving a reason.
3. I am free to ask any questions at any time before and during the study.
4. I understand what will happen to the data collected from me for the research.
5. I have been provided with a copy of this form and the Participant Information Sheet.
6. I understand that quotes from me will be used in the dissemination of the research
7. I understand that the interview will be recorded

Data Protection: I agree to the University¹ processing personal data which I have supplied. I agree to the processing of such data for any purposes connected with the Research Project as outlined to me*

Name of participant (print).....Signed.....Date.....

Name of person
witnessing consent (print).....Signed..... Date.....

PARTICIPANTS MUST BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP
ADD DATE AND VERSION NUMBER OF CONSENT FORM.

I WISH TO WITHDRAW FROM THIS STUDY.

Dissertation [REDACTED]

If you wish to withdraw from the research, please speak to the researcher or email them at the email: [REDACTED]

You do not have to give a reason for why you would like to withdraw.

Please let the researcher know whether you are/are not happy for them to use any data from you collected to date in the write up and dissemination of the research.

APPENDIX B: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Dear Mr/Mrs/Ms.

My name is Viet Anh Nguyen – a current DBA student of UWS in England. At the moment, I am in the period of collecting data for my thesis. Therefore, I am writing this in need of support from dear relevant participants. My topic is to explore HOW VIETNAMESE ENTREPRENEURS IN THE OVERSEAS EDUCATION CONSULTING SECTOR DEVELOPED THE MULTIPLEXITY IN PERSONAL NETWORKS TO ADVANCE THEIR BUSINESSES, 2000-2020. This networking theme is not too new, but it will be deeply viewed and studied in Asian and specific Vietnamese entrepreneurial contexts where network multiplexity is considered complicated and subtle. Your precious responses would be the findings contributing to ones who would like to open their business in the sector of overseas educational recruitment without much prior network experience.

You- my target participants are currently owners or CEO of Small and medium enterprises in Vietnam, taking initiatives in building new relationships and utilising current contacts to develop your company. Hence, it would be my pleasure and privilege for me to listen to your networking story in your beginning days of starting up in the sector of recruiting students for the overseas market. The interview is around 30 min to 1 hour, but please feel free to adjust and discuss the time with me because your comfort is my priority. Before the interview, I also would like your permission to sign the consent form and record and take notes during the process. These responses will be kept confidentially by my supervisors and me. Nevertheless, please rest assured that your name and your company will be kept anonymous, and all the data from the notes or records will be erased after the thesis completion. Last but not least, the thesis on completion will be provided to you if you are interested.

Your participation is voluntary, and you are entitled to withdraw at any time without giving any reason. The topic is merely exploratory; therefore, there are no right or wrong responses. They all reflect your beliefs, experiences, feelings, and perceptions that I –the researcher, would like to find out. I would appreciate it if you could answer all the questions; however, it would be totally fine if you refuse to answer any specific question.

Once again, I would like to express my thankful words for your cooperation and your support in my interview for the completion of my thesis. Please read through this sheet carefully and feel free to contact me at any time if any queries are raised.

Viet Anh Nguyen, DBA student

Email:

APPENDIX C: INTERVIEW PROTOCOL IN ENGLISH

1. Introduce myself
2. Explain the purpose of this interview and the participant's rights briefly.
3. Give the participant the informed consent form to review and sign.
4. Thank you for participating in an interview.
5. Use probing questions as needed.
6. If an interviewee has difficulty answering a question, provide examples or suggestions based on previous entrepreneurs' answers
7. Follow up-questions will be used as needed to invite the participant to elaborate more.
8. Debriefing at the end of the interview.

Interview Questions

1) Please introduce yourself

- What is your name?
- Your company?
- Your education history (your highest degree, your institutions)
- What do you treasure the most in life?

2) Please introduce your company

- What is the name?
- Year of establishment?

- Some achievements so far?
- 3) Can you tell me some experiences about your entrepreneurship?
- What do you think about the Overseas Educational Recruitment (OER) sector?
 - Your motivation for starting up in the OER sector? Why did you decide to start up?
 - What are the difficulties and challenges in starting up in the OER sector?
- 4) Who were the ones who helped you during the first starting up period of your business?
- Can you tell me who were the ones with more than a role to help your business?
 - What are the roles? (e.g., Your wife is not only the one who funds your company, but she is also the one who supports you emotionally, your mother is also the staff in the company cooking lunch for your staff)
- 5) Can you please share with me what kinds of resources you gained from those personal network multiplexity? (money, funding, new network, emotional support, legal advice, customer base etc.) and how it is important to your company?
- 6) How did you develop those personal network multiplexity for each type of group (wife, friends, relatives, parents, partner, supplier, customers, staff etc.)
- 7) How did you feel about the network multiplexity after three years for each type of group?
- 8) What is the strategy and advice for new companies to start up in the OER sector to develop network multiplexity?
- Any advice for the beginning period?
 - How to utilise the personal network multiplexity well during turbulence such as the Covid-19 pandemic?
- 9) Is there anything else that you reckon would be crucial for me to know in understanding the network multiplexity for the company in the OER sector?

APPENDIX D: INTERVIEW PROTOCOL IN VIETNAMESE

1. Người phỏng vấn (tôi) giới thiệu bản thân
2. Người phỏng vấn giải thích mục đích của buổi phỏng vấn cũng như những quyền lợi của người tham gia
3. Người phỏng vấn gửi thư chấp thuận trả lời phỏng vấn cho ứng viên tham gia và ký.
4. Cảm ơn người tham gia phỏng vấn
5. Sử dụng những câu hỏi phụ nếu cần
6. Nếu người phỏng vấn gặp khó khăn trong việc trả lời câu hỏi, một số ví dụ và gợi ý sẽ được đưa ra, tham khảo từ những người đã trả lời trước đó.
7. Sau khi phỏng vấn, những câu hỏi phát sinh thêm sẽ được sử dụng để mời người tham gia phỏng vấn trả lời thêm,
8. Tóm tắt lại ở cuối buổi phỏng vấn

Câu hỏi phỏng vấn

- 1) Xin anh (chị) giới thiệu bản thân
 - Tên?
 - Tên công ty?
 - Lịch sử công ty?
 - Đây là điều anh chị coi trọng nhất trong cuộc sống?
- 2) Xin anh chị hãy giới thiệu công ty của mình
 - Tên
 - Năm thành lập
 - Thành tựu đạt được
- 3) Xin anh chị hãy chia sẻ kinh nghiệm của anh chị về khởi nghiệp
 - Anh chị nghĩ gì về ngành tư vấn du học nước ngoài?
 - Đây là mục tiêu và động lực của anh chị khi lựa chọn ngành này để khởi nghiệp?
 - Đây là những khó khăn và thách thức của anh chị khi quyết định khởi nghiệp ở ngành này?
- 4) Ai là những người đã giúp đỡ anh chị trong những ngày đầu khởi nghiệp?
 - Anh chị có thể nói cụ thể hơn người nào là người đã giúp anh chị ở nhiều vai trò khác nhau lúc anh chị khởi nghiệp?
 - Vai trò đó là những gì (Ví dụ: Vợ của anh không chỉ là người cung cấp vốn cho công ty nhưng cũng là người giúp việc nấu ăn cho nhân viên trong công ty)

5) Anh chị có thể chia sẻ chi tiết những nguồn lực mà anh chị đã nhận được từ những mối quan hệ đó (Có thể đó là tiền, mạng lưới, hỗ trợ cảm xúc, lời khuyên pháp lý, khách hàng...) Và điều này quan trọng thế nào tới sự thành công và phát triển của công ty anh chị?

6) Anh chị đã phát triển những hệ thống mạng lưới quan hệ cá nhân này như thế nào? Anh chị đã phát triển những mạng lưới cá nhân này như thế nào. Làm ơn trả lời chi tiết cho từng nhóm (Vợ/ chồng, gia đình, họ hàng, đối tác, khách hàng...)!

7) Làm ơn hãy chia sẻ về sự thay đổi của các mạng lưới quan hệ cá nhân tới công ty của anh chị sau ba năm với từng nhóm cụ thể!

8) Đâu là những chiến lược cho những công ty mới mà anh chị có thể khuyên để phát triển những mạng lưới cá nhân như anh chị đã từng làm?

- Lời khuyên lúc mới bắt đầu
- Lời khuyên trong giai đoạn khó khăn và biến động, ví dụ như Covid-19

9) Anh chị còn muốn bổ xung thêm điều gì trong chủ đề này để tôi có thể hiểu thêm nữa về mạng lưới quan hệ cá nhân trong ngành tư vấn du học được không?

APPENDIX E: SUB-THEMES AND CODES

Main theme one: Motivation factors and challenges		
	Subtheme	Code
Passion and Motivation	Passion in Business	Business has always been my passion since I was a young girl More passion for setting up my business I realised the meaning of the business
	Passion in Education	Always loved education Always have passion in education Started liking the overseas educational sector
	Social Responsibility	Not able to access the reliable information Confused Help them achieve their dreams Avoid many fraudulent companies Students had to suffer and struggle Help them to have smooth and seamless experience Help more Vietnamese student get scholarships Leading our country to overcome poverty and become rich and powerful country Vietnamese will have more talented people to contribute the value to society and humanity
	Personal gain (Family support, financial profit, Social Status, Power and Freedom)	Help my son study abroad Thought about my sister and my children Profit is also important to survive myself, make wealthier and pay staffs. easily have profit from the beginning

		<p>Benefit us more than domestic counterpart</p> <p>Have more freedom to do whatever</p> <p>To be a leading entrepreneur</p> <p>Develop more if I work for myself</p> <p>Exceed my limitations and surpass my peers</p> <p>Being called “boss” and “director”</p>
	Resource Utilisation	<p>Accumulated enough knowledge</p> <p>Worked as a leader of subdepartment</p> <p>Worked for some prestigious universities</p> <p>Both jobs are about education</p>
Difficulties and Challenges of starting up in OER sector	Reputation and trust	<p>My brand recognition was nearly zero</p> <p>Reputation of my company was nothing</p> <p>The marketing recognition was too low</p> <p>The bad image of OER companies</p>
	Team building	<p>Pressure of find a good team</p> <p>Time consuming and exhausting</p> <p>Contemplated much on whom can help</p> <p>Stay up till 4 am because of having no staff</p> <p>It was not enough</p>
	Finance	<p>My biggest problem was to rent a good place</p> <p>It was tough because everything needs money to operate</p> <p>Not have enough financial requirements to set up the business</p>

	<p>Lack of entrepreneurial and managerial skills</p>	<p>Did not even have any plan Did with my hunch and intuition more than clear strategies The main problem is the human resources management My working experience was not suitable Struggled tremendously</p>
	<p>Lack of Networks (Network of suppliers, Network of customers, Network of expertise)</p>	<p>Only had four universities to work with There were only two French Universities working with me Struggling to find other agents to cooperate My clients at first were all my old students Hard to get many students Struggled to recruit students I did not know anyone in tax department I need more experience experts to help</p>
	<p>Mental and physical health issues</p>	<p>Extremely worried and stressful The long flights and pressure made me sick Took medicine Got a serious sick and I had to change my habit Struggled tremendously Could not recognise myself in the mirror Got insomnia Got a shock Felt guilty Had a regret Contemplated and think too much Under heavy pressure</p>

Main Theme Two: Dimensions of network multiplexity

	Subtheme	Codes
<p>Strong-tie relationships in personal network multiplexity</p>	<p>Family (Motivation, Co-founding, Operational support, Strategic advice, status and knowledge, Capital support, Network and contacts, Emotional support</p>	<p>Help my son study abroad My wife encouraged me to start up My husband always the inspiration Contributing to my decision of starting up was my dad My wife is also my only co-founder My cousin helped me direct the business in Vietnam I divided tasks clearly between me and my wife My wife helped me to finance my business My cousin was also my admin staff and the rep of the company My cousin helped me with technology and IT in my company as well as translation My sister oversees accounting, my brother-in-law was a chef and also the security My daughter was the marketer My husband was the advisor for the company My husband gave advice and be my coach my wife is the helped me with half of the capital My wife gave me her saving money My husband invested financially My parents gave me money</p>

		<p>My son introduced some of his friends</p> <p>My daughter connected me with the Vietnamese community in Australia</p> <p>My husband assisted me in contacting universities and schools in France</p> <p>My wife introduced many staffs for my company</p> <p>My wife took care of the family very well</p> <p>My husband knew whenever I was down or depressed and offer instant help</p> <p>My husband expressed with actions</p> <p>We together overcame those hardship</p> <p>We were harmonious in working with each other</p> <p>We were patience and caring and willing to listen to each other</p> <p>My daughter called me every day, talked to me, shared with me about her study life</p> <p>Whenever I felt down, I usually called my son to talk and received his comfort</p> <p>I felt so much easier and having my brother helped me with much less stress</p>
	<p>Friends (Co-founding support, Capital support, Operational support, Strategic advice, knowledge, status, New network and contact support, Emotional support)</p>	<p>My co-founding friends have different background, set of knowledge and skills</p> <p>I combined strengths and will with other friends having the same passion in OER</p> <p>My co-founding friends contributed financially to my company, which equals to half of the capital</p> <p>I could ask for help from my friend co-founders in terms of finance and capital</p> <p>About finance, we had four co-founding friends contributing to</p>

		<p>My co-founding friend had some experiences about staff management, operation, as well as finance and accounting management</p> <p>My other co-founding friend was in charge of analysing documents, information</p> <p>My co-founding friend took responsibility in finance, accounting, and legal issues of our companies</p> <p>My friend helped me as an academic consultant and expert for my company</p> <p>My students supported the workload in the company</p> <p>My friends at my former university helped me with business registration, tax issues and other legal documents</p> <p>My close coach helped me tremendously with useful advice and comprehensive knowledge about business</p> <p>Co-founding friends introduce new customers to my company</p> <p>My co-founding classmates introduced many students and their family members as customers</p> <p>My old teachers introduced our company to students, taking me as role model of success, and sent their close family member and students to my company for consultation.</p> <p>My co-founding friend was in charge of writing co-operation letters to get contracts from universities</p>
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		<p>My professors referred me to my first partners to work with</p> <p>My cofounding friends introduced potential as well as talented employers to my company</p> <p>helped me reduce much less stress</p> <p>did not feel alone at all when starting up.</p> <p>My cofounding-friends were besides me when we were successful but also at stakes.</p> <p>Released some steams of starting up process with my friends</p>
<p>Weak-tie relationships in personal network multiplexity</p>	<p>Business Partners (University representatives) (Sharing knowledge, skills and giving advice; Operational support; New network, contacts, and opportunity, emotional support)</p>	<p>advice on starting up</p> <p>entrepreneurial advice</p> <p>support agents and provide accurate and up-to date information</p> <p>access information quickly and fully rather than other agencies</p> <p>support from Vietnamese reps better and more direct than the foreign counterpart</p> <p>Vietnamese reps helped us better than the uni foreign reps</p> <p>Convinced customers and converted students</p> <p>Train our staff very well</p> <p>Share counselling skills as well as professional experience</p> <p>Helped in contacted the uni directly</p> <p>Introduced students to the company</p> <p>Advertised my company</p> <p>Helped in signing the new contract with new organisations</p>

		<p>Approaching source of scholarship as well as important information easier</p> <p>More bonus, international trips, gifts, rewards, recognition</p> <p>Became friends</p> <p>Shared true feelings to</p> <p>Shared the happiness of success or sadness of failure</p> <p>Encouraged me to keep up and always believed in my success</p> <p>Hosted and welcomed me very warmly</p>
	<p>Staffs (Operational support, Network, contact, and customers; Marketing and advertising; New ideas and perception</p>	<p>Expertise</p> <p>Recruit students</p> <p>Share experiences in studying and living abroad</p> <p>Promoting, document supporting</p> <p>Shared the heavy workload</p> <p>Find more new staff</p> <p>Generated more revenue</p> <p>Connecting with new customers introduced to their circle of network</p> <p>promoted the image of company</p> <p>introduced to their classmates</p> <p>gave me new perception</p>
	<p>Customers (New network and contacts, Marketing and advertising</p>	<p>Giving me contacts in their relationship circle</p> <p>Introduce me a plenty of new customers</p> <p>Gave network with many rich people with good title</p> <p>leave good reviews</p> <p>Give permission for using their interviews</p>

		Did some videos to endorse my company defended my company when there are bad and wrong rumors
Main theme Three: Dimensions of developments		
	Subtheme	Codes
	New networks and contacts	Increase by x times Surge by x times Maintain stably over those years Doubled by x year Triple compared to the x year
	The rise of revenue and customer base	Increase by x times Surge by x times Maintain stably over those years Doubled by x year Triple compared to the x year
	Reputation by online and offline interactions	Increased remarkably Increased/ rose by double/ triple
	Other developments	Moved from a small office to a bigger office Expanded from a two-storey rented house to a ten-storey building franchised my brand to provinces and cities in Vietnam Maintained the leading position Open another branch Develop to international markets Got some awards
Theme Four: The dynamism of network multiplexity		

Subtheme		Code
Inevitable changes in network	Staff changing	<p>My vice – director was replaced</p> <p>Some staffs left my company for studying abroad</p> <p>Many staffs were made redundant</p> <p>Received resignation letters from two important staffs</p> <p>Turned them into partners</p> <p>Becoming my customers, then after that became my partners, or referrals</p>
	Customer leaving	<p>The tie is not so solid</p> <p>Only using service when needed</p> <p>Many customers still stayed faithful</p> <p>Hardly I lost old customers</p> <p>90% of our students have been stayed</p> <p>Became my loyal clients</p> <p>Became the advertiser</p> <p>Became my staffs</p>
Unchanged relationships – Do they really remain unchanged?	Family (Spouse, children, family members, relatives...)	<p>Still the same</p> <p>Even help me more than I expected</p> <p>No need to say in terms of my children</p> <p>Always been there supporting me and never changing</p> <p>Always helping and become my partners</p> <p>Got divorced</p>

	Cofounders (Friend, classmates)	Sill supported No changes Never leaves me Been with me since the first days Left company because difference perception Break-ups in business
Theme Five: Personal Network Multiplexity strategy		
Standard PNM strategy for each type of network	PNM strategy for strong tie networks - Family	Care for my children with my all hearts Respect and show my love for my wife Money, finance but also love Treasure her and love her unconditionally (wife) Invested in him to study abroad (brother) every relationship needs to be built and reinforced all the time or it will fade soon with surprises like gifts, holiday vouchers or dates Try our best to understand each other Try to communicate, arrange your time more efficiently and spend some parts of your time
	- Cofounders (Friends)	Always have meetings Have parties sometimes Sympathise for my female co-founders let them go home earlier (female co-founders) shared with each other happiness, sorrow, and disappointment

		<p>Share with them success, finance, affection, stability</p> <p>Bring good care to all family members of them</p>
	<p>PNM strategy for weak tie networks</p> <p>- Customer</p>	<p>Give commission, voucher, and news on scholarship</p> <p>have a marketing staff sending email frequently</p> <p>scholarships information, phone calls, good services, commitment and promise (more priority with old customers)</p> <p>Considered them as friends</p> <p>never hesitate to help our customer at any time</p> <p>Also take the role as the bridge between the uni/school and parents</p> <p>Follow the success of students</p> <p>Come directly to the house of students to consult both parents, grandparents, and students</p> <p>Exceed the expectation of customers a little but not too much</p>
	<p>Staffs</p>	<p>Created professional but comfortable working environment</p> <p>A leader not a manager</p> <p>Encouraged and motivated</p> <p>Management by objectives</p> <p>Treated them like family members</p> <p>Ensure fairness among staffs</p> <p>inspired staffs</p> <p>Offered different benefits at different stages</p>

		<p>More opportunities to develop as well as money, health security, insurance</p> <p>Competitive salary and the opportunity to travel abroad</p> <p>Good commissions to staff</p> <p>Pay fees for their training</p> <p>Sharing, training, and facilitating them with knowledge and skills</p> <p>Generous</p> <p>Access exclusive scholarships</p>
	<p>University reps</p>	<p>Sending genuine students by verifying them carefully</p> <p>Participates actively in promotional activities</p> <p>the commitment</p> <p>Result</p> <p>Dedication</p> <p>Committed to the KPI</p> <p>Maintain important networks rather than expanding too much</p> <p>text messages/ write emails to keep in touch</p> <p>Invited them for dinners for each visit</p> <p>Prepared gifts or souvenirs each visit</p> <p>Sending postcards on special occasions</p> <p>Treated them with respect and very generously</p> <p>Shared difficulty as well as happiness</p> <p>shared dream, vision as well as mission</p> <p>treat them as friends</p>

Personal Network Multiplexity strategy in unprecedented period (Covid-19)	Application of online social platforms	Keeping advertising their university online Supported our customers by email, phone calls and text Connected closely staffs through Facebook and other social media. master technology, virtual counselling method use zoom and other online meeting tools (webinar, skype...)
	Staff being made redundant and old customers cared - quality over quantity	made redundant to some staffs and retain core staffs tried to pay staff with full salary based on the target and KPI Let them choose working style Focused more on old and existing customers call and text old customers
	Spending more time on self as well as important family and partners	Care for own health Make up the time for family Heal my relationship Use excessive time on talking to family members
	Be prepared and positive	Should have funds for risks Positive thinking Be calm and always prepare for the worst Turn challenges into opportunities